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A Formalization of Higher-Order Categories in Lean 4

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Abstract

Higher-order categories are a generalization of ordinary category theory in which morphisms can exist at multiple levels. They play a central role in modern mathematics, particularly in algebraic topology and homotopy theory.

This work focuses on the single-sorted and many-sorted presentations of higher-order categories, both finite-dimensional (n -categories) and infinite-dimensional (ω -categories). We study the relations between categories of different dimensions, as well as the relations between these presentations.

On the formal side, we develop a formalization in Lean 4 of these definitions and of some of the relations between them. Along the way, we discuss implementation aspects of the formalization, including design choices and considerations specific to its underlying dependent type theory.

KEYWORDS higher-order categories · formalization · Lean 4

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CHAPTER ONE

1

Introduction

§ 1.1

Motivation and context

Ordinary category theory organizes mathematical information into two levels: objects and the morphisms that relate them. However, in numerous contexts (notably, in algebraic topology and homotopy theory) this two-level structure falls short, and it is natural to also consider morphisms between morphisms, morphisms between these, and so on. Higher-order categories capture precisely this idea: they generalize the classical notion of category by admitting morphisms at an arbitrary number of levels, finite (the n -categories) or infinite (the ω -categories). This viewpoint is today one of the central tools of modern mathematics. There are those who argue, in fact, that higher-order categories are the natural framework for the mathematical objects of the 21st century, in the same way that ordinary categories were for those of the 20th century [Rie21]. The connection with the foundations is, moreover, close: in homotopy type theory, types are interpreted as ∞ -groupoids, a particular case of higher-order category, which places these structures at the center of contemporary foundational proposals [The13].

The mathematical development of this work is articulated around [CCR26, § 5], which we take as the central reference for the mathematical content that we develop and later formalize. There, two distinct presentations of the notion of higher-order category are introduced, which we also adopt. In the single-sorted presentation, all the morphisms of all the dimensions coexist in a single set. In the many-sorted presentation, on the other hand, each dimension has its own set of morphisms. Both ultimately describe the same structure, as we will review in Chapter 5.

To this mathematical development we add a second register: that of formalization. The usual mathematical practice rests on what we will call *informal verification*, that is, peer review and, ultimately, the community’s consensus. It is a reliable procedure, though not infallible, and more fragile the longer and more complex the proofs become. Formal verification responds to this situation by mechanizing the checking of correctness: it requires writing the proofs in sufficient detail that a machine can verify them step by step all the way to the axioms. It is already viable today, as milestones such as the formalization of the four colour theorem [Gon08], that of the Feit–Thompson theorem [Gon+13] or that of the Kepler conjecture [Hal+17] show, to which one can add, already on Lean, the *Liquid Tensor Experiment* [CT24] and the recent formalization of Marton’s PFR conjecture [TDM23]. We will review this panorama in detail in Chapter 6. For now it suffices to note that formalization has become a rapidly expanding area [Avi24].

As far as category theory specifically is concerned, the Lean ecosystem already offers a solid starting point. The Mathlib library includes a mature development of classical category theory (1-categories, functors, natural transformations and even bicategories) on which we will rely for the classical part [Com20]. In the realm of infinite dimensions, the ∞ -Cosmos project, led by Emily Riehl together with Dominic Verity and Mario Carneiro, aims to formalize the theory of $(\infty, 1)$ -categories through the axiomatic route of ∞ -cosmos, the universes in which these structures live as objects [RVC24].

Our formalization defines them from scratch, resorting to Mathlib only for the classical part, as we will discuss in Chapter 7.

§ 1.2

Objectives

The general objective of this work is to formalize in Lean 4 the two presentations of higher-order categories that we develop in Chapter 3 and Chapter 4, the single-sorted and the many-sorted, together with the basic relations between dimensions that each one admits.

This general objective is broken down into the following specific objectives:

- Formalize the single-sorted presentation, in both its finite-dimensional version (*n-categories*) and its infinite-dimensional version (*ω -categories*), together with their functors.
- Formalize, in parallel, the many-sorted presentation in both versions, finite-dimensional and infinite-dimensional, with their corresponding functors.
- Construct the categories of higher-order categories associated with each presentation and dimension.
- Formalize the discretization and underlying transformations between dimensions, in both presentations, and prove their functoriality.

Outside of these objectives lies the formalization of the equivalence between both presentations that we establish in Chapter 5. As we will anticipate there and discuss in detail in Chapter 7, its formalization faces technical obstacles, tied to the handling of the *heterogeneous equality* proper to dependent type theory, which place it outside the scope of a work of this length.

§ 1.3

Structure of the document

The document is organized into two logical parts, articulated around the change of register that takes place at the start of Chapter 6: the first part develops the mathematical content of the work, while the second addresses its formalization in Lean.

The first part, focused on the mathematical development, consists of four chapters:

CHAPTER 2 (PRELIMINARIES ON CATEGORY THEORY) We review the concepts of classical category theory that we will need throughout the document, as well as the set-theoretic foundations we will assume.

CHAPTER 3 (THE SINGLE-SORTED PRESENTATION) We develop the first of the two presentations of higher-order categories that we will study, covering both the finite-dimensional and the infinite-dimensional case.

CHAPTER 4 (THE MANY-SORTED PRESENTATION) In parallel with the previous chapter, we present the second presentation and discuss what distinguishes it from the first.

CHAPTER 5 (EQUIVALENCE OF THE PRESENTATIONS) We state the equivalence between both presentations and anticipate the formal obstacle that will condition the scope of the work.

The second part, focused on the formalization in Lean, consists of two chapters:

CHAPTER 6 (PRELIMINARIES ON FORMAL VERIFICATION) We introduce the basic concepts of the area (proof assistants, the Curry-Howard isomorphism, dependent type theory) and present Lean 4 and Mathlib as the working environment.

CHAPTER 7 (THE FORMALIZATION IN LEAN) The core of the work. We go through the formalization organized by topics, presenting the design decisions alongside the code, and close with the discussion of the obstacle anticipated in Chapter 5.

Finally, in Chapter 8 we gather the conclusions of the work and point out some lines of future work.

The document also includes Appendix A, with a descriptive guide to the [formalization repository](#)¹ and the [project page](#)² that accompanies it.

¹https://github.com/mariovagogmarzal/higher_category_theory

²https://mariovagogmarzal.github.io/higher_category_theory/

CHAPTER TWO

2

Preliminaries on category theory

*Perhaps the purpose of categorical algebra is to show that
which is trivial is trivially trivial.*

— Peter Freyd, *Abelian Categories: An Introduction to the
Theory of Functors* (1964)

The aim of this chapter is to set the theoretical framework on which the mathematical part of the work will be developed. On the one hand, we will fix the set-theoretic foundations we assume: ZFC together with the existence of a Grothendieck universe. On the other hand, we will review the basic notions of category theory that we will need for the development of the following chapters.

§ 2.1

Foundations

In the context of category theory, it is common to speak of *universal* collections of objects of a given kind, such as the set of all sets, the set of all groups or, one of the most relevant examples for our work, the set of all categories. However, it is well known that constructions of this kind are not admissible in ZFC: the collection of all sets is not a set, as Russell’s paradox shows.

When we speak of the set of objects satisfying a certain property, we are in fact invoking the axiom schema of separation, which, given a set A and a predicate $\varphi(x)$, guarantees the existence of a set B whose elements are exactly the elements of A that satisfy φ , typically denoted by

$$\{x \in A \mid \varphi(x)\}.$$

Here the insufficiency of ZFC for talking about such universal collections becomes apparent: there is no set A “large enough” to contain all the standard constructions of set theory without escaping from it. To resolve this issue, we introduce the concept of *Grothendieck universe*.

DEFINITION 2.1.1 (GROTHENDIECK UNIVERSE). A set \mathcal{U} is a *Grothendieck universe* if it satisfies the following properties:

- (U1) If $x \in y$ and $y \in \mathcal{U}$, then $x \in \mathcal{U}$.
- (U2) If $x, y \in \mathcal{U}$, then $\{x, y\} \in \mathcal{U}$.
- (U3) If $x \in \mathcal{U}$, then $\mathcal{P}(x) \in \mathcal{U}$, where $\mathcal{P}(x)$ is the power set of x .
- (U4) If $I \in \mathcal{U}$ and $\{x_i\}_{i \in I} \subseteq \mathcal{U}$, then $\cup_{i \in I} x_i \in \mathcal{U}$.

The existence of a Grothendieck universe is not derivable from the axioms of ZFC. We will therefore assume the following axiom, adopted in [AGV72, Exposé I, appendix *Univers* by N. Bourbaki]:

AXIOM 2.1.2 (TARSKI-GROTHENDIECK AXIOM). For every set A , there exists a Grothendieck universe \mathcal{U} such that $A \in \mathcal{U}$.

In particular, applied to the set of natural numbers \mathbb{N} , this axiom guarantees the existence of a Grothendieck universe with \mathbb{N} as an element. Such a universe also contains all the infinite sets derived in the standard way, such as the integers \mathbb{Z} , the rationals \mathbb{Q} or the reals \mathbb{R} . In short, “ordinary” mathematics is completely contained within it. From now on, we fix one such universe and denote it by \mathcal{U} . All the constructions in this work will by default be developed in it, except for a specific construction in Chapter 5 where we will need to invoke a larger universe, a fact that we will clarify at that point.

Now, using the universe \mathcal{U} as a support for an application of the separation schema, we can speak of the collection of all sets in \mathcal{U} that satisfy a certain property. In particular, we can identify \mathcal{U} itself as “the set of all sets”.

We finally introduce a classical terminological distinction.

DEFINITION 2.1.3. We call *classes* the subsets of \mathcal{U} . A class is a *small set* if it is, additionally, an element of \mathcal{U} ; otherwise, we say it is a *proper class* or *large set*.

From now on, we will always work in ZFC together with this axiom. In this construction we have broadly followed [CCR26], which in turn builds on [Mac98]. The complete description of the axioms of ZFC assumed can be found in [Mac98, § I.6].

§ 2.2

Categories

In the following chapters we will define higher-order categories, which will be the central object of this work. Before that, however, it will be essential to have at hand the classical definitions of category theory, not only to understand the structure we will be generalizing, but because it will be the reference frame for the comparison between higher-order categories.

It is also worth making a terminological clarification from the beginning. Throughout the rest of the work, unless stated otherwise, the terms *category*, *functor*, *natural transformation* and any other concept we define here refer to the classical notions introduced next. The higher-order generalizations will always appear with an explicit qualifier, such as *n-category*, *n-functor*, *higher-order category*, etc.

With this in mind, we first introduce the source/target presentation of a category, as in [Mac98, § I.1].

DEFINITION 2.2.1 (CATEGORY (SOURCE/TARGET PRESENTATION)). A *category* C consists of:

- A set of objects $\text{Ob}(C)$.
- A set of morphisms M .
- Two maps $\text{sc}, \text{tg} : M \rightarrow \text{Ob}(C)$, called *source* and *target*. Given a morphism $f \in M$ with $\text{sc}(f) = A$ and $\text{tg}(f) = B$, we will write

$$f : A \rightarrow B \quad \text{or} \quad A \xrightarrow{f} B.$$

- A map $\text{id} : \text{Ob}(C) \rightarrow M$, called the *identity*, which assigns to each object $A \in \text{Ob}(C)$ a morphism $\text{id}_A : A \rightarrow A$.
- A partial composition operation $\circ : M \times M \rightarrow M$, defined exactly on the pairs of morphisms $(g, f) \in M \times M$ with $\text{sc}(g) = \text{tg}(f)$, which assigns to each pair of composable morphisms $f : A \rightarrow B$ and $g : B \rightarrow C$ a morphism $g \circ f : A \rightarrow C$. The following diagram illustrates composition together with all the objects and morphisms involved:

These data are subject to the following axioms:

- (1) (*Identities.*) For every $f : A \rightarrow B$ and $g : B \rightarrow C$, we have

$$\text{id}_B \circ f = f \quad \text{and} \quad g \circ \text{id}_B = g.$$

Equivalently, the following diagram commutes³:

- (2) (*Associativity.*) For any $f : A \rightarrow B$, $g : B \rightarrow C$ and $h : C \rightarrow D$, we have

$$(h \circ g) \circ f = h \circ (g \circ f).$$

Equivalently, the following diagram commutes:

Although this is the presentation of category on which we will base the definition of higher-order category in the following chapters, [Mac98, § I.8] introduces an alternative presentation via the so-called hom-sets. We give it next.

DEFINITION 2.2.2 (CATEGORY). A *category* \mathcal{C} consists of:

- A set $\text{Ob}(\mathcal{C})$ of *objects*.
- For each pair of objects $A, B \in \text{Ob}(\mathcal{C})$, a set $\text{Hom}_{\mathcal{C}}(A, B)$ whose elements we call *morphisms* from A to B .
- For each triple of objects $A, B, C \in \text{Ob}(\mathcal{C})$, a composition operation

$$\circ : \text{Hom}_{\mathcal{C}}(B, C) \times \text{Hom}_{\mathcal{C}}(A, B) \rightarrow \text{Hom}_{\mathcal{C}}(A, C).$$

These data are subject to the following axioms:

- (C1) (*Identities.*) For each object $A \in \text{Ob}(\mathcal{C})$, there exists a morphism $\text{id}_A \in \text{Hom}_{\mathcal{C}}(A, A)$ such that, for any $f \in \text{Hom}_{\mathcal{C}}(B, A)$ and $g \in \text{Hom}_{\mathcal{C}}(A, C)$, we have

³We say that a diagram *commutes* when, for every pair of vertices, all the directed paths connecting them represent the same morphism upon composing the morphisms they traverse.

$$\text{id}_A \circ f = f \quad \text{and} \quad g \circ \text{id}_A = g.$$

(C2) (*Associativity*.) For any $f \in \text{Hom}_C(A, B)$, $g \in \text{Hom}_C(B, C)$ and $h \in \text{Hom}_C(C, D)$, we have

$$(h \circ g) \circ f = h \circ (g \circ f).$$

The equivalence between these two presentations of category is immediate, as discussed in [Mac98, § I.8]. In particular, given a category in the source/target presentation, we can define $\text{Hom}_C(A, B)$ as the set of morphisms f with $\text{sc}(f) = A$ and $\text{tg}(f) = B$. Similarly, given a category in the hom-set presentation, we can define the set of morphisms as the disjoint union of the hom-sets. All the required properties are verified immediately in both directions.

Once this equivalence is established, we can use either of the two presentations interchangeably. In this work, and diverging from [CCR26] for the first time, we will use the hom-set presentation of category (Definition 2.2.2). The reason for this choice is that this is the presentation used in the Mathlib library for Lean.⁴ Since we will only be defining higher-order categories from scratch and will rely on the library already provided by Mathlib for the classical categorical objects, this presentation will allow a smoother integration.

Before moving on, let us see a classical example of a category.

EXAMPLE 2.2.3 (THE CATEGORY OF SETS). We define the *category of sets* (or *category of small sets*), denoted by Set , as follows:

- The objects of Set are the small sets, that is, $\text{Ob}(\text{Set}) = \mathcal{U}$.
- For each pair of small sets $A, B \in \mathcal{U}$, the set of morphisms from A to B is the set of functions from A to B .

Composition of morphisms is the usual composition of functions, and the identities are the identity functions. It is immediate to check that the axioms of a category are satisfied.

Other classical examples include the category of groups, Grp , whose objects are the small groups and whose morphisms are group homomorphisms; the category of topological spaces, Top , whose objects are the small topological spaces and whose morphisms are continuous functions; and so on. In general, for any kind of mathematical structure that can be defined in terms of sets and functions, it is possible to build a category whose objects are the structures of that kind and whose morphisms are the functions preserving the structure.

We note that, in all the previous examples, the collection of objects is not a small set but only a class: for instance, $\text{Ob}(\text{Set}) = \mathcal{U}$, which is not an element of \mathcal{U} . This motivates a terminological distinction analogous to the one for small and large sets. We will say that C is a *small category* if $\text{Ob}(C)$ is a small set, and a *large category* otherwise. Thus, Set , Grp and Top are examples of large categories.

⁴With a small exception: Mathlib adopts the *diagrammatic* convention for composition, that is, $\circ : \text{Hom}_C(A, B) \times \text{Hom}_C(B, C) \rightarrow \text{Hom}_C(A, C)$, whereas our definition follows the *applicative* convention, $\circ : \text{Hom}_C(B, C) \times \text{Hom}_C(A, B) \rightarrow \text{Hom}_C(A, C)$. The difference is minimal and has virtually no impact on the formalization; we choose the classical applicative order for consistency with our references and with most of the classical literature.

As we have just pointed out, it is common in mathematics to define transformations between two mathematical structures that preserve the relevant information of those structures. In the context of category theory, these transformations are functors.

DEFINITION 2.2.4 (FUNCTOR). Let C and D be two categories. A *functor* $F : C \longrightarrow D$ consists of:

- A map $F : \text{Ob}(C) \longrightarrow \text{Ob}(D)$.
- For each pair $A, B \in \text{Ob}(C)$, a map⁵ $F : \text{Hom}_C(A, B) \longrightarrow \text{Hom}_D(F(A), F(B))$.

These maps are subject to the following axioms:

- (F1) (*Preservation of identities.*) For each object $A \in \text{Ob}(C)$, we have $F(\text{id}_A) = \text{id}_{F(A)}$.
- (F2) (*Preservation of composition.*) For any $f \in \text{Hom}_C(A, B)$ and $g \in \text{Hom}_C(B, C)$, we have

$$F(g \circ f) = F(g) \circ F(f).$$

Remark 2.2.5 (Functors in the source/target presentation). In the source/target presentation of category, a functor $F : C \longrightarrow D$ is defined analogously, but with the morphism part given by a map $F : \mathcal{M}_C \longrightarrow \mathcal{M}_D$ that respects the source, target, identity and composition maps.

From now on we will stop spelling out the source/target variants of the definitions, although they can always be recovered immediately from the hom-set versions.

A simple example is the *forgetful functor* from Grp to Set , which assigns to each group its underlying set and to each homomorphism the map that defines it. It is immediate to check that it respects identities and composition.

PROPOSITION 2.2.6 (IDENTITY FUNCTOR AND COMPOSITION OF FUNCTORS). *Given the categories C, D and E , and the functors $F : C \longrightarrow D$ and $G : D \longrightarrow E$, the following constructions are functors:*

- The identity functor $\text{id}_C : C \longrightarrow C$, which assigns to each object or morphism of C the same object or morphism.
- The composition of functors $G \circ F : C \longrightarrow E$, which assigns to each object $A \in \text{Ob}(C)$ the object $G(F(A))$ and to each morphism $f \in \text{Hom}_C(A, B)$ the morphism $G(F(f))$.

The proof is immediate from the functor axioms.

With this, one of the most paradigmatic examples of a category arises naturally: the category of categories.

DEFINITION 2.2.7 (CATEGORY OF CATEGORIES). The *category of categories* (or *category of small categories*), denoted by Cat , is defined as follows:

- The objects of Cat are the small categories, that is, $\text{Ob}(\text{Cat}) = \{C \in \mathcal{U} \mid C \text{ is a category}\}$.
- For each pair of small categories C and D , the set of morphisms from C to D is the set of functors from C to D .

⁵We commit here a common abuse of notation: we use the same symbol F for the functor itself, for its action on objects and for each of its actions on morphisms. Since no confusion is possible, this identification causes no ambiguity.

Composition of morphisms is composition of functors, and the identities are the identity functors. By Proposition 2.2.6, these choices are well defined and the axioms of a category are satisfied without difficulty.

As in the previous examples, the construction of Cat depends on the fixed universe \mathcal{U} . We also note that Cat is a large category, since its collection of objects is not an element of \mathcal{U} . In contexts where one needs to treat Cat itself as a categorical object, the Tarski-Grothendieck axiom guarantees the existence of a Grothendieck universe \mathcal{U}' such that $\text{Cat} \in \mathcal{U}'$, which allows us to consider the category of \mathcal{U}' -small categories, of which Cat is itself an object. Iterating yields a hierarchy of universes. In this work we will only need one additional level, in the construction of the projective limit of Chapter 5.⁶

§ 2.3

Relations between categories

When comparing two categories, requiring them to be equal turns out to be too strong a condition: very few pairs of categories of interest are literally equal. We will therefore need weaker notions of comparison.

Let us start with the internal case: within a single category we can ask when two objects are “the same” up to the relevant structural information. The classical answer is the notion of isomorphism.

DEFINITION 2.3.1 (ISOMORPHISM). Let C be a category and let $A, B \in \text{Ob}(C)$. A morphism $f \in \text{Hom}_C(A, B)$ is an *isomorphism* if there exists $g \in \text{Hom}_C(B, A)$ such that

$$g \circ f = \text{id}_A \quad \text{and} \quad f \circ g = \text{id}_B.$$

In this case we will say that A and B are *isomorphic* and we will write $A \cong B$.

Applying this definition to the category Cat directly gives the notion of isomorphism between categories.

DEFINITION 2.3.2 (ISOMORPHISM OF CATEGORIES). Given two categories C and D , an *isomorphism of categories* is a functor $F : C \rightarrow D$ for which there exists a functor $G : D \rightarrow C$ such that

$$G \circ F = \text{id}_C \quad \text{and} \quad F \circ G = \text{id}_D.$$

If there exists an isomorphism of categories between C and D , we will say that C and D are *isomorphic* and we will write $C \cong D$.

The question naturally arises whether this notion of isomorphism of categories can be weakened further. The answer is affirmative, and to formulate it we first introduce the notion of natural transformation between functors.

DEFINITION 2.3.3 (NATURAL TRANSFORMATION). Let $F, G : C \rightarrow D$ be two functors. A *natural transformation* $\alpha : F \Rightarrow G$ is a family of morphisms

⁶In [CCR26] only the existence of a fixed universe \mathcal{U} is assumed, an axiom that is strictly weaker than the Tarski-Grothendieck axiom adopted here and does not, in general, allow the construction of a larger universe hosting Cat .

$$\{\alpha_A \in \text{Hom}_D(F(A), G(A))\}_{A \in \text{Ob}(C)}$$

such that, for every morphism $f \in \text{Hom}_C(A, B)$, the *naturality square* holds:

$$G(f) \circ \alpha_A = \alpha_B \circ F(f).$$

Equivalently, the following diagram commutes:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} F(A) & \xrightarrow{F(f)} & F(B) \\ \alpha_A \downarrow & & \downarrow \alpha_B \\ G(A) & \xrightarrow{G(f)} & G(B) \end{array}$$

A first example, which we will use shortly, is the *identity natural transformation* $\text{id}_F : F \Rightarrow F$ of a functor $F : C \rightarrow D$, whose components are the identities $(\text{id}_F)_A = \text{id}_{F(A)}$. The naturality square holds trivially.

With this definition, we can introduce the notion of natural isomorphism between functors and that of equivalence of categories.

DEFINITION 2.3.4 (NATURAL ISOMORPHISM). Given two categories C and D and two functors $F, G : C \rightarrow D$, a *natural isomorphism* is a natural transformation $\alpha : F \Rightarrow G$ such that every component α_A is an isomorphism in D . In this case, we will say that F and G are *isomorphic* and we will write $F \cong G$.

DEFINITION 2.3.5 (EQUIVALENCE OF CATEGORIES). Given two categories C and D , we will say that C and D are *equivalent* if there exist two functors $F : C \rightarrow D$ and $G : D \rightarrow C$ such that $G \circ F \cong \text{id}_C$ and $F \circ G \cong \text{id}_D$. We write $C \simeq D$ to denote this fact.

We now observe that natural transformations admit two composition operations. Beyond their usual interest, these operations will be necessary for formulating the last notion of comparison between categories that we will present, the adjunction. The first of them directly generalizes the composition of morphisms within a category, as we will see below.

DEFINITION 2.3.6 (VERTICAL COMPOSITION OF NATURAL TRANSFORMATIONS). Let $F, G, H : C \rightarrow D$ be three functors and let $\alpha : F \Rightarrow G$ and $\beta : G \Rightarrow H$ be two natural transformations. The *vertical composition* of α and β is the natural transformation $\beta \circ \alpha : F \Rightarrow H$ with components

$$(\beta \circ \alpha)_A = \beta_A \circ \alpha_A$$

for each $A \in \text{Ob}(C)$.

The following diagram collects the functors and transformations involved in the vertical composition:

It is immediate to check that the vertical composition of two natural transformations again satisfies the naturality square, that it is associative, and that it has the identity natural transformations as identity elements. Therefore, once we fix two categories C and D , the functors from C to D together with the natural transformations between them form a new category, the *functor category*, which we denote D^C following [Mac98, § II.4].

The second operation combines natural transformations between functors whose domains and codomains fit together.

DEFINITION 2.3.7 (HORIZONTAL COMPOSITION OF NATURAL TRANSFORMATIONS). Let C, D , and E be three categories and let $F, F' : C \rightarrow D$ and $G, G' : D \rightarrow E$ be functors. Given two natural transformations $\alpha : F \Rightarrow F'$ and $\beta : G \Rightarrow G'$, the *horizontal composition* of α and β is the natural transformation $\beta * \alpha : G \circ F \Rightarrow G' \circ F'$ with components

$$(\beta * \alpha)_A = \beta_{F'(A)} \circ G(\alpha_A) = G'(\alpha_A) \circ \beta_{F(A)}$$

for each $A \in \text{Ob}(C)$, where the equality between the two expressions follows from the naturality of β .

The following diagram illustrates the data involved:

A frequent particular case of the horizontal composition appears when one of the two transformations is an identity.

DEFINITION 2.3.8 (WHISKERING). Let $\alpha : F \Rightarrow F'$ be a natural transformation between functors $F, F' : C \rightarrow D$. Given a functor $H : B \rightarrow C$, we write αH for the horizontal composition $\alpha * \text{id}_H : F \circ H \Rightarrow F' \circ H$. Symmetrically, given a functor $K : D \rightarrow E$, we write $K\alpha$ for the horizontal composition $\text{id}_K * \alpha : K \circ F \Rightarrow K \circ F'$. Both operations are called *whiskering*.

With both compositions defined, we can name the structure formed by categories, functors, and natural transformations: that of the paradigmatic example of a *bicategory*⁷, a notion of higher-order category that we will be generalizing in the following chapters.

⁷Throughout this work, “bicategory” denotes the strict two-dimensional notion, in which all equations (associativity, identities, interchange) hold exactly. It is what [CCR26] and most of the literature call a 2-category.

Remark 2.3.9 (The bicategory of categories). In a bicategory three levels of objects coexist. In our case, the first level is formed by the small categories, the second by the functors between them, and the third by the natural transformations between functors. The vertical composition organizes, for each pair of categories C and D , the functors and the transformations into the category D^C , while the horizontal composition allows composing along intermediate categories. Both operations are compatible through the *interchange law*, which guarantees that the result of composing an arrangement of natural transformations such as the one in the following diagram does not depend on the order in which the vertical and horizontal compositions are carried out:

Explicitly, $(\beta' \circ \beta) * (\alpha' \circ \alpha) = (\beta' * \alpha') \circ (\beta * \alpha)$. The compositions of natural transformations and the interchange law are discussed in [Mac98, § II.5], and the bicategory structure on small categories is introduced in [Mac98, § XII.3].

Let us now return to the comparison between categories. Equivalence weakened isomorphism by replacing the equalities $G \circ F = \text{id}_C$ and $F \circ G = \text{id}_D$ with natural isomorphisms. We can go one step further and require only the existence of two natural transformations, in opposite directions, subject to a coherence condition. This is the notion of adjunction.

DEFINITION 2.3.10 (ADJUNCTION). An *adjunction* between two categories C and D consists of a pair of functors $F : C \rightarrow D$ and $G : D \rightarrow C$ together with two natural transformations

$$\eta : \text{id}_C \Rightarrow G \circ F \quad \text{and} \quad \varepsilon : F \circ G \Rightarrow \text{id}_D,$$

called *unit* and *counit* respectively, satisfying the *triangle identities*

$$(\varepsilon F) \circ (F \eta) = \text{id}_F \quad \text{and} \quad (G \varepsilon) \circ (\eta G) = \text{id}_G,$$

which are equivalent to the commutativity of the following diagrams:

In this case, we say that F is a *left adjoint* of G and that G is a *right adjoint* of F , and we write $F \dashv G$.

The adjunction is, indeed, the weakest of the three comparisons between categories that we have introduced. The following proposition arranges them into a hierarchy.

PROPOSITION 2.3.11. *Let C and D be two categories. If C and D are isomorphic, then they are equivalent. And if C and D are equivalent through the functors $F : C \rightarrow D$ and $G : D \rightarrow C$, then F and G can be completed to an adjunction $F \dashv G$.*

The first implication is immediate: an equality of functors is a particular case of natural isomorphism, since the identity natural transformation is a natural isomorphism. Consequently, an isomorphism of categories is, in particular, an equivalence. The second implication is also a standard result: every equivalence can be adjusted to an adjunction, keeping one of the two natural isomorphisms and modifying the other so that the triangle identities hold. The details of this construction can be found in [Mac98, § IV.4].

We close the section with a construction that gathers a whole system of related adjunctions into a single structure. We will not use it in the mathematical development of the following chapters, and we will recover it only in Chapter 8, when discussing the lines of future work. We introduce it, for completeness, following [Sol99].

DEFINITION 2.3.12 (ALGEBRAIC SQUARE). An *algebraic square* is a diagram of categories and adjunctions

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 & & G \\
 & \longleftarrow & \\
 C & \xrightarrow{\quad \top \quad} & D \\
 \uparrow & \xrightarrow{\quad F \quad} & \uparrow \\
 J \dashv K & (\alpha, \beta) & J' \dashv K' \\
 \downarrow & \xrightarrow{\quad G' \quad} & \downarrow \\
 C' & \xrightarrow{\quad \top \quad} & D' \\
 & \xrightarrow{\quad F' \quad} &
 \end{array}$$

where α and β are a *conjugate pair* of natural isomorphisms

$$\alpha : F' \circ J \Rightarrow J' \circ F \quad \text{and} \quad \beta : G \circ K' \Rightarrow K \circ G'.$$

The condition of being a *conjugate pair* relates α and β through the units and counits of the composite adjunctions $J' \circ F \dashv G \circ K'$ and $F' \circ J \dashv K \circ G'$. Its precise formulation can be found in [Sol99, Definition 4.3.60].

CHAPTER THREE

3

The single-sorted presentation

In this chapter we develop the first of the two presentations of higher-order categories that we will study: the single-sorted presentation. It is worth unpacking the title. On the one hand, “higher-order” refers, as we already anticipated at the end of Chapter 2, to a generalization of the classical notion of category in which, besides objects and morphisms, the so-called 2-morphisms, 3-morphisms, and so on, also appear. On the other hand, “single-sorted” indicates that all these levels coexist in a single set, being distinguished by source, target and composition operations indexed by each dimension.

From this chapter onwards, and until the end of the first part of the work, we follow the development of [CCR26, § 5], adopting, nevertheless, some adaptations of notation and nomenclature of our own. The reason for these adaptations is merely to integrate better with the formalization part, as will be discussed in Chapter 7.

§ 3.1

Single-sorted categories

Before introducing the basic definitions of this chapter, it is worth observing an elementary fact of classical category theory that motivates the approach of the single-sorted presentation.

LEMMA 3.1.1 (UNIQUENESS OF THE IDENTITY). *Let C be a category and let $A \in \text{Ob}(C)$. If $e, e' \in \text{Hom}_C(A, A)$ are both identity morphisms for A , then $e = e'$.*

Proof. Since $e, e' \in \text{Hom}_C(A, A)$, the pair (e, e') is composable. Moreover, since both act as identities for A , we have

$$e = e \circ e' = e'. \quad \square$$

Remark 3.1.2. Lemma 3.1.1 shows that, for each object $A \in \text{Ob}(C)$, the identity id_A is uniquely determined by A . That is, the assignment $A \mapsto \text{id}_A$ is an injection from the set of objects into the set of morphisms and, therefore, allows us to recover the information of $\text{Ob}(C)$ from the subset of morphisms formed by the identities without loss of information.

Remark 3.1.2 is the main idea of the *single-sorted presentation* of a category: since objects can be identified with their identity morphisms, we can dispense with the set of objects as an independent piece of data and describe the entire categorical structure on a single set of morphisms. The source and target maps, instead of sending a morphism to its domain object, send it to the identity of that object. Concretely, they become maps from C to C whose image consists precisely of the identity morphisms. Composition remains a partial operation on pairs of composable morphisms.

Schematically, a morphism f for which we would previously write $f : A \longrightarrow B$ is now reinterpreted as an element $f \in C$ such that $\text{sc}(f) = \text{id}_A$ and $\text{tg}(f) = \text{id}_B$:

$$\text{id}_A = \text{sc}(f) \xrightarrow{f} \text{tg}(f) = \text{id}_B$$

We begin by formalizing this idea in the one-dimensional case, which will capture the usual notion of category rewritten in these terms. We note now that, unlike the previous example, the set of morphisms will be the only underlying data besides the operations.

DEFINITION 3.1.3 (SINGLE-SORTED CATEGORY). A *single-sorted category* C consists of the following data:

- A set C , whose elements we call *morphisms*.
- Two maps $\text{sc}, \text{tg} : C \rightarrow C$, called *source* and *target* respectively.
- A partial composition operation $\# : C \times C \rightarrow C$, defined exactly on the pairs $(g, f) \in C \times C$ such that $\text{sc}(g) = \text{tg}(f)$. In such a case we will say that g and f are *composable* and we will denote their composition by $g\#f$.

These data are subject to the following axioms:

(S1) (*Idempotence.*) For every $f \in C$,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{sc}(\text{sc}(f)) &= \text{sc}(f), & \text{tg}(\text{sc}(f)) &= \text{sc}(f), \\ \text{sc}(\text{tg}(f)) &= \text{tg}(f), & \text{tg}(\text{tg}(f)) &= \text{tg}(f). \end{aligned}$$

(S2) (*Source and target of a composition.*) For every pair of composable morphisms $g, f \in C$,

$$\text{sc}(g\#f) = \text{sc}(f) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{tg}(g\#f) = \text{tg}(g).$$

(S3) (*Identities.*) For every $f \in C$, the pairs $(f, \text{sc}(f))$ and $(\text{tg}(f), f)$ are composable, and

$$f\#\text{sc}(f) = f \quad \text{and} \quad \text{tg}(f)\#f = f.$$

(S4) (*Associativity.*) For any $f, g, h \in C$ with g and f composable and h and g composable, the pairs $(h\#g, f)$ and $(h, g\#f)$ are also composable, and

$$(h\#g)\#f = h\#(g\#f).$$

In this case, we will say that the tuple $C = (C, (\text{sc}, \text{tg}, \#))$ is a *single-sorted category*, or that $(\text{sc}, \text{tg}, \#)$ defines a single-sorted category structure on the set C .

Let us introduce a key notion that will help us better understand the axioms of this structure.

DEFINITION 3.1.4 (CELL). Let C be a single-sorted category. We say that a morphism $f \in C$ is a *cell*, a *source cell* or an *identity* if

$$\text{sc}(f) = f.$$

DEFINITION 3.1.5 (TARGET CELL). Let C be a single-sorted category. We say that a morphism $f \in C$ is a *target cell* if

$$\text{tg}(f) = f.$$

LEMMA 3.1.6 (EQUIVALENCE OF THE CELL NOTIONS). Let C be a single-sorted category. A morphism $f \in C$ is a source cell if, and only if, it is a target cell. In particular,

$$\{f \in C \mid \text{sc}(f) = f\} = \{f \in C \mid \text{tg}(f) = f\}.$$

Proof. Let $f \in C$ be a source cell. We have

$$\text{tg}(f) = \text{tg}(\text{sc}(f)) = \text{sc}(f) = f,$$

where in the first and last equalities we have used that $\text{sc}(f) = f$ and in the second the axiom (S1).

The converse is proved analogously. \square

The concept of cell captures precisely the idea of identifying objects with their identity morphisms: suppose that a morphism were the identity morphism of an object A ; then both its source and its target would be the object A itself. But, since we have identified objects with their identity morphisms, this amounts to saying that the source and target of such a morphism coincide with the morphism itself, i.e., that it is a cell.

Moreover, if we take any morphism, its source and target should represent an object of the category, that is, an identity morphism. Axiom (S1) guarantees precisely this. In fact, axiom (S3) states precisely that, since the source and target of a morphism represent the identity morphism of its “underlying object”, composing a morphism with its source or with its target is like composing with an identity, that is, it does not change the morphism.

Axiom (S2) guarantees that composition concatenates the codomain of a morphism with the domain of the next, returning a morphism whose source is the same as that of the second and whose target is the same as that of the first. The following diagram illustrates this idea:

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 & \text{tg}(f) = \text{sc}(g) & \\
 f \nearrow & & \searrow g \\
 \text{sc}(f) & \xrightarrow{g \# f} & \text{tg}(g)
 \end{array}$$

Axiom (S4) is the usual associativity of composition.

The aim of this chapter, however, is to present the structure that emerges when adding higher dimensions. Thus, in the following definition, we equip a single set of morphisms with a finite family of source, target and composition operations indexed by each dimension, without yet imposing any interaction between different dimensions.

DEFINITION 3.1.7 (FINITE-DIMENSIONAL SINGLE-SORTED PRE-CATEGORY). Let $n \in \omega^8$ and identify, as usual, the ordinal n with the set $\{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}$ with the usual order. A *single-sorted pre- n -category* is a tuple

$$C = \left(C, \left(\text{sc}^k, \text{tg}^k, \#^k \right)_{k \in n} \right)$$

such that, for each $k \in n$, the tuple $\left(C, \left(\text{sc}^k, \text{tg}^k, \#^k \right) \right)$ is a single-sorted category in the sense of Definition 3.1.3.

DEFINITION 3.1.8 (SETS OF CELLS). Let $C = \left(C, \left(\text{sc}^k, \text{tg}^k, \#^k \right)_{k \in n} \right)$ be a single-sorted pre- n -category. For each $k \in n$, the set of *k -cells* of C is the subset of C formed by the morphisms that are cells at dimension k , that is,

$$C_k = \{f \in C \mid \text{sc}^k(f) = f\}.$$

⁸Following [CCR26], as is standard in set theory, we denote by ω the smallest infinite ordinal, which is the order type of the set of natural numbers \mathbb{N} with the usual order.

We further identify the set C itself with the set of n -cells, so that $C = C_n$.

This is a purely structural definition that imposes no kind of coherence between the different dimensions. To capture the notions of interest in higher-order categories we need to impose additional axioms that regulate how the operations of each dimension interact with the others. We first introduce the simplest case in which these interactions appear, that of two dimensions, which will serve as a base for the general case.

DEFINITION 3.1.9 (SINGLE-SORTED BICATEGORY). A *single-sorted bicategory* is a single-sorted pre-2-category

$$C = \left(C, \left(\text{sc}^k, \text{tg}^k, \#^k \right)_{k \in 2} \right)$$

that satisfies the following axioms for every pair of indices $j < k$ in 2:

(SB1) For every $f \in C$,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{sc}^k(\text{sc}^j(f)) &= \text{sc}^j(f), & \text{sc}^j(\text{sc}^k(f)) &= \text{sc}^j(f), \\ \text{sc}^j(\text{tg}^k(f)) &= \text{sc}^j(f), & \text{tg}^k(\text{tg}^j(f)) &= \text{tg}^j(f), \\ \text{tg}^j(\text{tg}^k(f)) &= \text{tg}^j(f), & \text{tg}^j(\text{sc}^k(f)) &= \text{tg}^j(f). \end{aligned}$$

(SB2) (*Distributivity of source and target over composition.*) For every pair of morphisms $g, f \in C$ composable at dimension j , the pairs $(\text{sc}^k(g), \text{sc}^k(f))$ and $(\text{tg}^k(g), \text{tg}^k(f))$ are also composable at dimension j and

$$\begin{aligned} \text{sc}^k(g \#^j f) &= \text{sc}^k(g) \#^j \text{sc}^k(f), \\ \text{tg}^k(g \#^j f) &= \text{tg}^k(g) \#^j \text{tg}^k(f). \end{aligned}$$

(SB3) (*Interchange.*) For any $f_1, f_2, g_1, g_2 \in C$ such that

- g_2 and f_2 are composable at dimension j ,
- g_1 and f_1 are composable at dimension j ,
- g_2 and g_1 are composable at dimension k and
- f_2 and f_1 are composable at dimension k ,

it holds that $g_2 \#^j f_2$ and $g_1 \#^j f_1$ are composable at dimension k , $g_2 \#^k g_1$ and $f_2 \#^k f_1$ are composable at dimension j and

$$(g_2 \#^j f_2) \#^k (g_1 \#^j f_1) = (g_2 \#^k g_1) \#^j (f_2 \#^k f_1).$$

In other words, composing first at dimension j and then at dimension k produces the same result as composing first at dimension k and then at dimension j .

In this specific case, since the set of indices is the ordinal $2 = \{0, 1\}$ and $j < k$, we have $j = 0$ and $k = 1$, so that the previous axioms specialize to their instances for that pair. We keep, however, the general formulation with generic j and k , since it will be useful to recognize the structure of each axiom in the final definition of single-sorted n -category.

Intuitively, axiom (SB1) ensures that the operations of each dimension “see” the others coherently; (SB2), that operations of higher dimension respect compositions of lower dimension; and

(SB3), that the order in which compositions at different dimensions are carried out is irrelevant. These intuitions are reflected visually in the usual diagrams of bicategory theory. For example, we can picture a morphism $f \in C$ as a “2-cell” between two parallel 1-cells:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} & \text{sc}^1(f) & \\ & \curvearrowright & \\ \text{sc}^0(f) & f \Downarrow & \text{tg}^0(f) \\ & \curvearrowleft & \\ & \text{tg}^1(f) & \end{array}$$

In this schema, the morphisms $\text{sc}^0(f)$ and $\text{tg}^0(f)$ are the 0-cells (objects) and $\text{sc}^1(f)$, $\text{tg}^1(f)$ are the 1-cells (morphisms) between them. We can think of f as a 2-cell that mediates between the previous 1-cells. Axiom (SB1) is precisely what guarantees that this diagram is coherent: the source and target at dimension 0 of $\text{sc}^1(f)$ and $\text{tg}^1(f)$ are the same.

With the bicategory as a concrete case, generalizing to n dimensions is now immediate: it suffices to require that each pair of levels forms a bicategory.

DEFINITION 3.1.10 (FINITE-DIMENSIONAL SINGLE-SORTED CATEGORY). Let $n \in \omega$. A *single-sorted n -category* is a single-sorted pre- n -category

$$C = \left(C, \left(\text{sc}^k, \text{tg}^k, \#^k \right)_{k \in n} \right)$$

such that, for every pair of indices $j, k \in n$ with $j < k$, the tuple⁹ $\left(C, \text{sc}^j, \text{tg}^j, \#^j, \text{sc}^k, \text{tg}^k, \#^k \right)$ is a single-sorted bicategory, in the sense of Definition 3.1.9.

We note that for the case $n = 1$, since there are no pairs of indices $j < k$, the bicategory condition is satisfied vacuously, so the notion of single-sorted 1-category coincides with that of single-sorted category or pre-1-category. On the other hand, for $n = 2$, the notion of single-sorted 2-category coincides with that of single-sorted bicategory. Moreover, for any dimension n , it is obvious that every single-sorted n -category is also a single-sorted pre- n -category. This last observation lets us speak of the concept of k -cells defined earlier.

So far, all the notions considered live in a finite number of dimensions. However, it is easy to check that, replacing the ordinal n with the ordinal ω , we would obtain a notion of higher-order category with infinitely many dimensions. However, an additional axiom is needed in this case, as we will see next.

DEFINITION 3.1.11 (SINGLE-SORTED OMEGA CATEGORY). A *single-sorted ω -category* is a tuple

$$C = \left(C, \left(\text{sc}^k, \text{tg}^k, \#^k \right)_{k \in \omega} \right)$$

such that, for each $k \in \omega$, the tuple $\left(C, \text{sc}^k, \text{tg}^k, \#^k \right)$ is a single-sorted category and, for every pair of indices $j, k \in \omega$ with $j < k$, the tuple $\left(C, \text{sc}^j, \text{tg}^j, \#^j, \text{sc}^k, \text{tg}^k, \#^k \right)$ is a single-sorted bicategory.

⁹Here we commit an abuse of notation and identify $\left(C, \left(\text{sc}^i, \text{tg}^i, \#^i \right)_{i \in \{j,k\}} \right)$ with a tuple of the form $\left(C, \text{sc}^j, \text{tg}^j, \#^j, \text{sc}^k, \text{tg}^k, \#^k \right)$.

Additionally, the following axiom is required:

(ω S1) For every $f \in C$, there exists $k \in \omega$ such that f is a k -cell, that is, $\text{sc}^k(f) = f$.

Axiom (ω S1) has no analogue in the finite-dimensional case: in a single-sorted n -category there are no operations above dimension $n - 1$ and the set C is directly identified with the cells of dimension n . In the infinite-dimensional case, by contrast, nothing in the level structure prevents the existence of morphisms whose dimension “does not stabilise”, that is, that there is some $f \in C$ such that $\text{sc}^k(f) \neq f$ for every $k \in \omega$. The additional condition rules out this situation by requiring that the hierarchy $\{C_k\}_{k \in \omega}$ covers the whole set C .

§ 3.2

Single-sorted functors

Having established the structures, we now turn to the maps that preserve them. It is worth noting beforehand that, since in the single-sorted presentation a category is given by a single set of morphisms, a functor between two such structures reduces to a map between those sets. No family of maps, one for each kind of morphism, is needed, as would be the case in the classical presentation.

We first define the finite-dimensional case.

DEFINITION 3.2.1 (FINITE-DIMENSIONAL SINGLE-SORTED FUNCTOR). Let $n \in \omega$ and let C and D be two single-sorted n -categories. A *single-sorted n -functor* from C to D is a map $F : C \rightarrow D$ that, for each $k \in n$, satisfies the following axioms:

(SF1) (*Preservation of source and target.*) For every $f \in C$,

$$F(\text{sc}^k(f)) = \text{sc}^k(F(f)) \quad \text{and} \quad F(\text{tg}^k(f)) = \text{tg}^k(F(f)).$$

(SF2) (*Preservation of composition.*) For every pair $g, f \in C$ composable at dimension k , the pair $(F(g), F(f))$ is composable at dimension k in D and

$$F(g \#^k f) = F(g) \#^k F(f).$$

The infinite-dimensional case is defined analogously, replacing the ordinal n with ω and requiring the previous axioms in every dimension.

DEFINITION 3.2.2 (SINGLE-SORTED OMEGA FUNCTOR). Let C and D be two single-sorted ω -categories. A *single-sorted ω -functor* from C to D is a map $F : C \rightarrow D$ that satisfies the axioms of Definition 3.2.1 for every $k \in \omega$.

To close, we check that both the identity and the composition of maps fit into this framework.

PROPOSITION 3.2.3 (IDENTITY AND COMPOSITION OF SINGLE-SORTED FUNCTORS). *Let C be a single-sorted n -category (resp. ω -category). The identity map on C is a single-sorted n -functor (resp. ω -functor) from C to itself. Moreover, if $F : C \rightarrow D$ and $G : D \rightarrow E$ are single-sorted n -functors (resp. ω -functors), their composition $G \circ F : C \rightarrow E$ is also a single-sorted n -functor (resp. ω -functor).*

Proof. For the identity on C , the equalities of axioms (SF1) and (SF2) are trivial, since the map sends every morphism to itself. For composition, given $f \in C$ and k in the corresponding index set, we have

$$(G \circ F)(\text{sc}^k(f)) = G(F(\text{sc}^k(f))) = G(\text{sc}^k(F(f))) = \text{sc}^k(G(F(f))) = \text{sc}^k((G \circ F)(f)),$$

where we have used axiom (SF1) for F and G in turn. Preservation of the target and of composition follow analogously. \square

§ 3.3

The categories of single-sorted categories

Just as ordinary categories and the functors between them organize themselves into the category Cat , single-sorted n -categories and n -functors are gathered into an analogous category. As before, for the construction to be consistent with the set-theoretic foundations fixed in Chapter 2, we must restrict ourselves to the structures whose underlying set of morphisms is a small set, that is, an element of the Grothendieck universe \mathcal{U} .

DEFINITION 3.3.1 (CATEGORY OF FINITE-DIMENSIONAL SINGLE-SORTED CATEGORIES). Let $n \in \omega$. The *category of (small) single-sorted n -categories*, denoted by $n\text{Cat}$, is defined as follows:

- The objects of $n\text{Cat}$ are the single-sorted n -categories with underlying set of morphisms $C \in \mathcal{U}$.
- For each pair $C, D \in \text{Ob}(n\text{Cat})$, the set of morphisms from C to D is the set of single-sorted n -functors from C to D .

Composition of morphisms is the usual composition of maps, and the identities are the identity maps. As we have just checked, these choices are well defined and the axioms of a category are satisfied without difficulty.

Analogously, we can define the omega version of this category.

DEFINITION 3.3.2 (CATEGORY OF SINGLE-SORTED OMEGA CATEGORIES). The *category of (small) single-sorted ω -categories*, denoted by ωCat , is defined as follows:

- The objects of ωCat are the single-sorted ω -categories with underlying set of morphisms $C \in \mathcal{U}$.
- For each pair $C, D \in \text{Ob}(\omega\text{Cat})$, the set of morphisms from C to D is the set of single-sorted ω -functors from C to D .

Composition of morphisms is the usual composition of maps, and the identities are the identity maps. As in the finite-dimensional case, these choices are well defined and the axioms of a category are satisfied without difficulty.

As with Cat , the categories $n\text{Cat}$ and ωCat are large categories, and their construction depends on the fixed universe \mathcal{U} .

Remark 3.3.3. Observe that at no point have we excluded the value $n = 0$. In that case, the ordinal 0 is exactly the empty set \emptyset and thus the family of operations is empty. Consequently, the axioms

of a single-sorted category are vacuously satisfied and, for every set $C \in \mathcal{U}$, the tuple $C = (C, ())$ is a single-sorted 0-category. Moreover, every map between two sets is a single-sorted 0-functor. In fact, the forgetful functor from 0Cat to Set , sending each single-sorted 0-category to its underlying set and each single-sorted 0-functor to the underlying map, is an isomorphism of categories; hence 0Cat is canonically isomorphic to Set .

We finally fix a notational convention that will be useful later on.

Remark 3.3.4. In what follows, we will write $n \in \omega + 1$ to treat uniformly the finite-dimensional case ($n \in \omega$) and the infinite-dimensional case ($n = \omega$). As an ordinal, $\omega + 1 = \omega \cup \{\omega\}$ with the usual order and ω as the maximum element. In particular, given $n \in \omega + 1$, when referring to $n\text{Cat}$ we may be talking about the finite-dimensional version if $n \in \omega$ or about the omega version if $n = \omega$. By extension, the same applies when we refer to single-sorted n -categories or n -functors.

§ 3.4

Discretization transformations

In [CCR26, p. 109] a single-sorted category is said to be *discrete* if every morphism is a cell. Later, in [CCR26, Remark 5.1.4], it is asserted that, given a single-sorted n -category, we can think of it as a single-sorted ω -category in which all the dimensions m , with $n \leq m$, are discrete.

In this section, we present a generalization of these observations, building a transformation that, for each $n \in \omega + 1$, raises the dimension of any single-sorted n -category to an arbitrary dimension $m \in \omega + 1$ with $n \leq m$ by declaring the upper dimensions to be discrete. Moreover, we will extend this construction to functors and check that it is a functorial transformation: the *discretization* of a single-sorted category.

DEFINITION 3.4.1 (DISCRETIZATION OF A SINGLE-SORTED CATEGORY). Let $n, m \in \omega + 1$ with $n \leq m$ and let

$$C = \left(C, \left(\text{sc}^k, \text{tg}^k, \#^k \right)_{k \in n} \right)$$

be a single-sorted n -category. The *discretization of C at dimension m* , denoted by $C \uparrow^m$, is the single-sorted m -category with underlying set C and operations, for each $k \in m$, defined as follows:

- If $k < n$, the operations sc^k , tg^k and $\#^k$ coincide with those of C .
- If $n \leq k$, the operations $\text{sc}^k(f) = \text{tg}^k(f) = f$ for every $f \in C$; it follows that $\#^k$ is defined exactly on the pairs (f, f) with $f \in C$ and we define $f \#^k f = f$.

It is immediate to check that this construction satisfies the axioms of a single-sorted m -category: the levels $k < n$ inherit the whole structure of C and the levels $n \leq k$ are trivial by construction, with all equations reducing to identities of the form $f = f$. In the case $m = \omega$, moreover, every $f \in C$ is a k -cell for any $k \geq n$, so (ωS1) is satisfied.

We now define the discretization for functors.

DEFINITION 3.4.2 (DISCRETIZATION OF A SINGLE-SORTED FUNCTOR). Let $n, m \in \omega + 1$ with $n \leq m$ and let $F : C \rightarrow D$ be a single-sorted n -functor. The *discretization of F at dimension m* ,

denoted by $F\uparrow^m: C\uparrow^m \rightarrow D\uparrow^m$, is the map $F: C \rightarrow D$, now viewed as a single-sorted m -functor from $C\uparrow^m$ to $D\uparrow^m$.

Once again, the verification of axioms (SF1) and (SF2) is direct: for $k < n$ they are inherited from F and for $n \leq k$ they reduce to $F(f) = F(f)$.

Remark 3.4.3. When $n = m$, the discretization of a single-sorted category or functor coincides with the category or functor itself, respectively.

We finally consider the discretization transformation as a functor (in the classical sense) between the categories of single-sorted categories.

DEFINITION 3.4.4 (SINGLE-SORTED DISCRETIZATION FUNCTOR). Let $n, m \in \omega + 1$ with $n \leq m$. The *discretization functor*, denoted by $\mathcal{D}^{(m,n)}$, is the functor

$$\mathcal{D}^{(m,n)} : n\text{Cat} \rightarrow m\text{Cat}$$

that assigns to each n -category C its discretization $C\uparrow^m$ and to each n -functor F its discretization $F\uparrow^m$.

The preservation of identities and composition is immediate, since discretization leaves the underlying map between sets of morphisms unchanged.

Remark 3.4.5. By Remark 3.4.3, the discretization functor $\mathcal{D}^{(n,n)}$ is the identity on $n\text{Cat}$, $\text{id}_{n\text{Cat}}$, for every $n \in \omega + 1$.

§ 3.5

Underlying transformations

In contrast to the discretization transformation of Section 3.4, we now present a transformation that, for each $n \in \omega + 1$, lowers the dimension of any single-sorted n -category to an arbitrary dimension $m \in \omega + 1$ with $m \leq n$ by keeping only the subset of m -cells and birestricting¹⁰ the operations to this subset. Moreover, we will extend this construction to functors and check that it is a functorial transformation: the *underlying transformation* of a single-sorted category.

As we have just anticipated, in order to define the underlying transformation we need to birestrict the operations to a set of cells of a lower dimension. We thus present first the lemmas that guarantee the existence of such birestrictions, one for source and target and another for partial composition.

LEMMA 3.5.1 (BIRESTRICTION OF SOURCE AND TARGET). Let $n \in \omega + 1$, $C = \left(C, \left(\text{sc}^k, \text{tg}^k, \#^k \right)_{k < n} \right)$ a single-sorted n -category and $k, m \in \omega + 1$ with $k < m < n$. The maps sc^k and tg^k admit a birestriction to C_m as maps $C_m \rightarrow C_m$.

¹⁰Given a map $f: A \rightarrow B$ and subsets $A' \subseteq A, B' \subseteq B$ with $f[A'] \subseteq B'$, the *birestriction* of f to A' and B' , denoted by $f|_{A'}^{B'}$, is the map $A' \rightarrow B'$ that agrees with f on A' . Although the domain of a map can always be restricted, it is necessary to check that the image of a domain stays within a subset of the codomain for the corestriction to be well defined. The concept extends analogously to partial maps.

Proof. Let $f \in C_m$, that is, $\text{sc}^m(f) = f$. By axiom (SB1) applied to the pair $k < m$,

$$\text{sc}^m(\text{sc}^k(f)) = \text{sc}^k(f),$$

so $\text{sc}^k(f) \in C_m$. The proof for $\text{tg}^k(f)$ is analogous. \square

LEMMA 3.5.2 (BIRESTRICTION OF COMPOSITION). *Let $n \in \omega + 1$, $C = (C, (\text{sc}^k, \text{tg}^k, \#^k)_{k < n})$ a single-sorted n -category and $k, m \in \omega + 1$ with $k < m < n$. The partial composition operation $\#^k$ admits a birestriction to $C_m \times C_m$ as a partial operation $C_m \times C_m \rightarrow C_m$.*

Proof. Let $g, f \in C_m$ be composable at dimension k . By axiom (SB2),

$$\text{sc}^m(g \#^k f) = \text{sc}^m(g) \#^k \text{sc}^m(f) = g \#^k f,$$

where the second equality uses that $g, f \in C_m$. Therefore, $g \#^k f \in C_m$. \square

With these results, we are in a position to define the underlying transformation of a single-sorted category.

DEFINITION 3.5.3 (UNDERLYING OF A SINGLE-SORTED CATEGORY). Let $n, m \in \omega + 1$ with $m \leq n$ and let

$$C = (C, (\text{sc}^k, \text{tg}^k, \#^k)_{k \in n})$$

be a single-sorted n -category. The *underlying* of C at dimension m , denoted by $C \downarrow_m$, is the single-sorted m -category with underlying set C_m , the set of m -cells of C , and operations

$$\text{sc}^k \upharpoonright_{C_m}^{C_m}, \quad \text{tg}^k \upharpoonright_{C_m}^{C_m}, \quad \#^k \upharpoonright_{C_m}^{C_m}.$$

Lemma 3.5.1 and Lemma 3.5.2 guarantee that the birestrictions are well defined, and the axioms (S1)–(S4) and (SB1)–(SB3) are immediately inherited from C by birestricting the domain to C_m .

To extend the underlying transformation to functors, we check that a single-sorted functor also admits a birestriction to the set of cells of a lower dimension.

LEMMA 3.5.4 (BIRESTRICTION OF A SINGLE-SORTED FUNCTOR). *Let $n \in \omega + 1$, C and D be two single-sorted n -categories and $F : C \rightarrow D$ a single-sorted n -functor. For every $m \in \omega + 1$ with $m < n$, F admits a birestriction to C_m as a map $C_m \rightarrow D_m$.*

Proof. Let $f \in C_m$, that is, $\text{sc}^m(f) = f$. By axiom (SF1),

$$\text{sc}^m(F(f)) = F(\text{sc}^m(f)) = F(f),$$

so $F(f) \in D_m$. \square

DEFINITION 3.5.5 (UNDERLYING OF A SINGLE-SORTED FUNCTOR). Let $n, m \in \omega + 1$ with $m \leq n$ and let $F : C \rightarrow D$ be a single-sorted n -functor. The *underlying* of F at dimension m , denoted by $F \downarrow_m : C \downarrow_m \rightarrow D \downarrow_m$, is the birestriction $F \upharpoonright_{C_m}^{D_m}$.

Lemma 3.5.4 ensures that the birestriction is well defined, and the axioms (SF1) and (SF2) for each $k < m$ are those inherited from F .

Remark 3.5.6. When $m = n$, the underlying of a single-sorted category or functor is precisely the original category or functor, respectively.

We finally consider the underlying transformation as a functor (in the classical sense) between the categories of single-sorted categories.

DEFINITION 3.5.7 (SINGLE-SORTED UNDERLYING FUNCTOR). Let $n, m \in \omega + 1$ with $m \leq n$. The *underlying functor*, denoted by $\mathcal{U}^{(m,n)}$, is the functor

$$\mathcal{U}^{(m,n)} : n\text{Cat} \longrightarrow m\text{Cat}$$

that assigns to each n -category C its underlying $C \downarrow_m$ and to each n -functor F its underlying $F \downarrow_m$.

The preservation of identities and composition follows immediately from the definitions: restricting the identity map gives the identity on C_m , and composition commutes with restriction.

Remark 3.5.8. By Remark 3.5.6, the underlying functor $\mathcal{U}^{(n,n)}$ is the identity on $n\text{Cat}$, $\text{id}_{n\text{Cat}}$, for every $n \in \omega + 1$.

CHAPTER FOUR

4

The many-sorted presentation

In this chapter we develop the second of the two presentations of higher-order categories that we will study: the many-sorted presentation. In contrast to the approach of Chapter 3, where all morphisms lived in a single set and the different dimensions were distinguished internally through the operations of the structure, which in turn gave rise to the internal classification by cells, the many-sorted presentation takes a more direct route: each dimension has its own set of morphisms and the relations between different dimensions are defined by the operations. In particular, the identity morphisms, which in the single-sorted case were identified with the cells, will now be given by maps that go up from one dimension to a higher one.

As in the previous chapter, we follow the development of [CCR26, § 5], also introducing adaptations of notation and nomenclature, motivated by a better integration with the formalization of Chapter 7. A more careful comparison between both presentations and the question of their equivalence will be discussed in Chapter 5. In this chapter we limit ourselves to developing the many-sorted structure by itself, maintaining, as far as possible, the parallelism with Chapter 3.

§ 4.1

Many-sorted categories

As in the single-sorted case, we begin with the one-dimensional case, which will capture the usual notion of category rewritten in these new terms. The essential difference with respect to the single-sorted presentation is structural: now each dimension lives in its own set, and the source, target and identity maps explicitly relate some sets to others. In particular, the identity goes from being an internal property of the set of morphisms to being an explicit datum of the structure: a map that goes up from the lower dimension to the higher one.

DEFINITION 4.1.1 (MANY-SORTED CATEGORY). A *many-sorted category* C consists of the following data:

- Two sets C_0 and C_1 , whose elements we call *0-morphisms* and *1-morphisms* respectively.
- Two maps $sc, tg : C_1 \rightarrow C_0$, called *source* and *target* respectively.
- A map $id : C_0 \rightarrow C_1$, called *identity*.
- A partial composition operation $\# : C_1 \times C_1 \rightarrow C_1$, defined exactly on the pairs $(g, f) \in C_1 \times C_1$ such that $sc(g) = tg(f)$. In such a case we will say that g and f are *composable* and we will denote their composition by $g\#f$.

These data are subject to the following axioms:

(M1) (*Source and target of a composition.*) For every pair of composable morphisms $g, f \in C_1$,

$$sc(g\#f) = sc(f) \quad \text{and} \quad tg(g\#f) = tg(g).$$

(M2) (*Source and target of an identity.*) For every $f \in C_0$,

$$sc(id(f)) = f \quad \text{and} \quad tg(id(f)) = f.$$

(M3) (*Identities.*) For every $f \in C_1$, the pairs $(f, id(sc(f)))$ and $(id(tg(f)), f)$ are composable, and

$$f\#id(sc(f)) = f \quad \text{and} \quad id(tg(f))\#f = f.$$

(M4) (*Associativity*.) For any $f, g, h \in C_1$ with g and f composable and h and g composable, the pairs $(h\#g, f)$ and $(h, g\#f)$ are also composable, and

$$(h\#g)\#f = h\#(g\#f).$$

In this case, we will say that the tuple $C = ((C_0, C_1), (\text{sc}, \text{tg}, \text{id}, \#))$ is a *many-sorted category*, or that $(\text{sc}, \text{tg}, \text{id}, \#)$ defines a many-sorted category structure on the pair of sets (C_0, C_1) .

Axioms (M1), (M3) and (M4) are the direct analogues, in this context, of axioms (S2), (S3) and (S4) of Definition 3.1.3. Axiom (M2), by contrast, has no direct version in the single-sorted case: there, no separate datum for identities appeared, since the identity morphisms were identified with the cells themselves of the single underlying set. The structure we have just defined is, then, a direct translation of the classical presentation of a category from Chapter 2, with C_0 as the set of objects and C_1 as the set of morphisms.

It is worth highlighting an immediate consequence of axiom (M2) that is the direct analogue of the uniqueness of identities in the classical case discussed in Lemma 3.1.1.

PROPOSITION 4.1.2 (INJECTIVITY OF THE IDENTITY). *Let C be a many-sorted category. The map $\text{id} : C_0 \longrightarrow C_1$ is injective.*

Proof. Let $f, g \in C_0$ with $\text{id}(f) = \text{id}(g)$. Applying axiom (M2) to both sides,

$$f = \text{sc}(\text{id}(f)) = \text{sc}(\text{id}(g)) = g. \quad \square$$

The aim of this chapter, however, is to present the structure that emerges when adding higher dimensions. Thus, in the following definition, we will equip a finite family of sets with the corresponding source, target, identity and composition operations between each pair of dimensions, without yet imposing any interaction between different pairs.

DEFINITION 4.1.3 (FINITE-DIMENSIONAL MANY-SORTED PRE-CATEGORY). Let $n \in \omega$ and identify the ordinal $n + 1$ with the set $\{0, 1, \dots, n\}$ with the usual order. A *many-sorted pre- n -category* is a tuple

$$C = \left((C_k)_{k \in n+1}, \left(\text{sc}^{(j,k)}, \text{tg}^{(j,k)}, \text{id}^{(k,j)}, \#^{(j,k)} \right)_{j,k \in n+1, j < k} \right)$$

such that, for each pair of indices $j, k \in n + 1$ with $j < k$, the tuple $\left((C_j, C_k), \left(\text{sc}^{(j,k)}, \text{tg}^{(j,k)}, \text{id}^{(k,j)}, \#^{(j,k)} \right) \right)$ is a many-sorted category in the sense of Definition 4.1.1. We will call the elements of each C_k the *k -morphisms* of C . Moreover, given a pair $j, k \in n + 1$ with $j < k$, we will say that two k -morphisms $g, f \in C_k$ are *(j, k) -composable* when they are so in the many-sorted category associated to the pair (j, k) ; that is, when $\text{sc}^{(j,k)}(g) = \text{tg}^{(j,k)}(f)$.

As in the single-sorted case, this is a purely structural definition that imposes no kind of coherence between the different dimensions. To capture the notions of interest in higher-order categories, we need to impose additional axioms that regulate how the operations between different pairs of dimensions behave among themselves. We first introduce the simplest case in which these

interactions appear, that of three¹¹ dimensions, which will serve as a base for the general case.

DEFINITION 4.1.4 (MANY-SORTED BICATEGORY). A *many-sorted bicategory* is a many-sorted pre-2-category

$$C = \left((C_k)_{k \in 3}, \left(\text{sc}^{(j,k)}, \text{tg}^{(j,k)}, \text{id}^{(k,j)}, \#^{(j,k)} \right)_{j,k \in 3, j < k} \right)$$

that satisfies the following axioms for every triple of indices i, j, k in 3 with $i < j < k$:

(MB1) For every $f \in C_k$,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{sc}^{(i,j)} \left(\text{sc}^{(j,k)}(f) \right) &= \text{sc}^{(i,k)}(f), & \text{sc}^{(i,j)} \left(\text{tg}^{(j,k)}(f) \right) &= \text{sc}^{(i,k)}(f), \\ \text{tg}^{(i,j)} \left(\text{tg}^{(j,k)}(f) \right) &= \text{tg}^{(i,k)}(f), & \text{tg}^{(i,j)} \left(\text{sc}^{(j,k)}(f) \right) &= \text{tg}^{(i,k)}(f). \end{aligned}$$

(MB2) (*Distributivity of source and target over composition.*) For every pair $g, f \in C_k$ that are (i, k) -composable, the pairs $(\text{sc}^{(j,k)}(g), \text{sc}^{(j,k)}(f))$ and $(\text{tg}^{(j,k)}(g), \text{tg}^{(j,k)}(f))$ are (i, j) -composable, and

$$\begin{aligned} \text{sc}^{(j,k)} \left(g \#^{(i,k)} f \right) &= \text{sc}^{(j,k)}(g) \#^{(i,j)} \text{sc}^{(j,k)}(f), \\ \text{tg}^{(j,k)} \left(g \#^{(i,k)} f \right) &= \text{tg}^{(j,k)}(g) \#^{(i,j)} \text{tg}^{(j,k)}(f). \end{aligned}$$

(MB3) (*Composition of identities.*) For every $f \in C_i$,

$$\text{id}^{(k,j)} \left(\text{id}^{(j,i)}(f) \right) = \text{id}^{(k,i)}(f).$$

(MB4) (*Distributivity of the identity over composition.*) For every pair $g, f \in C_j$ that are (i, j) -composable, the pair $(\text{id}^{(k,j)}(g), \text{id}^{(k,j)}(f))$ is (i, k) -composable, and

$$\text{id}^{(k,j)} \left(g \#^{(i,j)} f \right) = \text{id}^{(k,j)}(g) \#^{(i,k)} \text{id}^{(k,j)}(f).$$

(MB5) (*Interchange.*) For any $f_1, f_2, g_1, g_2 \in C_k$ such that

- g_2 and g_1 are (j, k) -composable,
- f_2 and f_1 are (j, k) -composable,
- g_2 and f_2 are (i, k) -composable and
- g_1 and f_1 are (i, k) -composable,

it holds that $g_2 \#^{(i,k)} f_2$ and $g_1 \#^{(i,k)} f_1$ are (j, k) -composable, the pairs $g_2 \#^{(j,k)} g_1$ and $f_2 \#^{(j,k)} f_1$ are (i, k) -composable, and

$$\left(g_2 \#^{(i,k)} f_2 \right) \#^{(j,k)} \left(g_1 \#^{(i,k)} f_1 \right) = \left(g_2 \#^{(j,k)} g_1 \right) \#^{(i,k)} \left(f_2 \#^{(j,k)} f_1 \right).$$

In this specific case, since the set of indices is the ordinal $3 = \{0, 1, 2\}$ and $i < j < k$, we have $i = 0, j = 1$ and $k = 2$, so that the previous axioms specialize to their instances for that triple. We keep, however, the general formulation with generic i, j and k , since it will be useful to recognize the structure of each axiom in the final definition of many-sorted n -category.

¹¹When we speak of $n + 1$ dimensions we are referring to an n -category, counting the dimensions 0, 1, ..., n . In this sense, the three-dimensional case corresponds to a 2-category or, as we will define next, a bicategory.

The interpretation of these axioms is analogous to that of the single-sorted bicategory (cf. Definition 3.1.9).

With the bicategory as a concrete case, generalizing to n dimensions is now immediate: it suffices to require that each triple of levels forms a bicategory.

DEFINITION 4.1.5 (FINITE-DIMENSIONAL MANY-SORTED CATEGORY). Let $n \in \omega$. A *many-sorted n -category* is a many-sorted pre- n -category

$$C = \left((C_k)_{k \in n+1}, \left(\text{sc}^{(j,k)}, \text{tg}^{(j,k)}, \text{id}^{(k,j)}, \#^{(j,k)} \right)_{j,k \in n+1, j < k} \right)$$

such that, for every triple of indices $i, j, k \in n+1$ with $i < j < k$, the operations of the pairs (i, j) , (i, k) and (j, k) define a many-sorted bicategory structure on (C_i, C_j, C_k) , in the sense of Definition 4.1.4.

We note that for the cases $n = 1$ and $n = 2$ this definition simplifies. For $n = 1$, since there are no triples of distinct indices, the condition is satisfied vacuously and the notion of many-sorted 1-category coincides with that of many-sorted pre-1-category; in this case, moreover, fixing the unique pair $(0, 1)$, the many-sorted pre-1-category is nothing but a many-sorted category in the sense of Definition 4.1.1. For $n = 2$, since there is only one possible triple, the just stated notion of many-sorted bicategory coincides with the previous one. Moreover, for any dimension n , it is obvious that every many-sorted n -category is also a many-sorted pre- n -category.

So far, all the notions considered live in a finite number of dimensions. As in the single-sorted case, the generalization to the infinite-dimensional case is direct: it suffices to replace the ordinal $n+1$ with the ordinal ω of natural numbers.

DEFINITION 4.1.6 (MANY-SORTED OMEGA CATEGORY). A *many-sorted ω -category* is a tuple

$$C = \left((C_k)_{k \in \omega}, \left(\text{sc}^{(j,k)}, \text{tg}^{(j,k)}, \text{id}^{(k,j)}, \#^{(j,k)} \right)_{j,k \in \omega, j < k} \right)$$

such that, for each pair of indices $j, k \in \omega$ with $j < k$, the operations of the pair (j, k) define a many-sorted category structure on (C_j, C_k) and, for every triple of indices $i, j, k \in \omega$ with $i < j < k$, the operations of the pairs (i, j) , (i, k) and (j, k) define a many-sorted bicategory structure on (C_i, C_j, C_k) .

It is worth observing a notable difference with respect to the single-sorted case: Definition 4.1.6 does not require any additional axiom analogous to $(\omega S1)$. In the many-sorted presentation, each morphism belongs, by construction, to a single set C_k of predetermined dimension, so that the dimension of a morphism is given and need not be characterized as a property of the structure.

§ 4.2

Many-sorted functors

Having established the structures, we now turn to the maps that preserve them. Unlike the single-sorted presentation, where a category was given by a single set of morphisms and a functor reduced,

in essence, to a single map between those sets, in the many-sorted case each dimension has its own set. A functor will therefore now consist of a *family* of maps that coherently preserve all the operations of the structure.

We first define the finite-dimensional case.

DEFINITION 4.2.1 (FINITE-DIMENSIONAL MANY-SORTED FUNCTOR). Let $n \in \omega$ and let C and D be two many-sorted n -categories. A *many-sorted n -functor* from C to D is a family of maps $F = (F_k : C_k \longrightarrow D_k)_{k \in n+1}$ that, for each pair of indices $j, k \in n+1$ with $j < k$, satisfies the following axioms:

(MF1) (*Preservation of source and target.*) For every $f \in C_k$,

$$F_j(\text{sc}^{(j,k)}(f)) = \text{sc}^{(j,k)}(F_k(f)) \quad \text{and} \quad F_j(\text{tg}^{(j,k)}(f)) = \text{tg}^{(j,k)}(F_k(f)).$$

(MF2) (*Preservation of the identity.*) For every $f \in C_j$,

$$F_k(\text{id}^{(k,j)}(f)) = \text{id}^{(k,j)}(F_j(f)).$$

(MF3) (*Preservation of composition.*) For every pair $g, f \in C_k$ that are (j, k) -composable, the pair $(F_k(g), F_k(f))$ is (j, k) -composable in D and

$$F_k(g \#^{(j,k)} f) = F_k(g) \#^{(j,k)} F_k(f).$$

The infinite-dimensional case is defined analogously, replacing the ordinal $n+1$ with ω and requiring the previous axioms for every pair of dimensions.

DEFINITION 4.2.2 (MANY-SORTED OMEGA FUNCTOR). Let C and D be two many-sorted ω -categories. A *many-sorted ω -functor* from C to D is a family of maps $F = (F_k : C_k \longrightarrow D_k)_{k \in \omega}$ that satisfies the axioms of Definition 4.2.1 for every pair $j, k \in \omega$ with $j < k$.

As in the single-sorted case, we check that both the identity and the componentwise composition of families of maps fit into this framework.

PROPOSITION 4.2.3 (IDENTITY AND COMPOSITION OF MANY-SORTED FUNCTORS). *Let C be a many-sorted n -category (resp. ω -category). The family of identity maps $(\text{id}_{C_k})_k$ on each C_k is a many-sorted n -functor (resp. ω -functor) from C to itself. Moreover, if $F : C \longrightarrow D$ and $G : D \longrightarrow E$ are many-sorted n -functors (resp. ω -functors), the family $G \circ F = (G_k \circ F_k)_k$ is also a many-sorted n -functor (resp. ω -functor).*

Proof. For the identity, the equalities of axioms (MF1)–(MF3) are trivial, since each F_k sends every morphism to itself. For composition, given $f \in C_k$ and a pair $j < k$ in the corresponding index set, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (G_j \circ F_j)(\text{sc}^{(j,k)}(f)) &= G_j(F_j(\text{sc}^{(j,k)}(f))) = G_j(\text{sc}^{(j,k)}(F_k(f))) \\ &= \text{sc}^{(j,k)}(G_k(F_k(f))) = \text{sc}^{(j,k)}((G_k \circ F_k)(f)), \end{aligned}$$

where we have used axiom (MF1) for F and G in turn. Preservation of the target, of the identity and of composition follow analogously. \square

§ 4.3

The categories of many-sorted categories

In parallel with what was done in Chapter 3, the many-sorted n -categories and n -functors also organize themselves into a category. For the construction to be consistent with the set-theoretic foundations fixed in Chapter 2, we will require that the family¹² $(C_k)_k$ of underlying sets be made up of small sets, that is, of elements of the Grothendieck universe \mathcal{U} .

DEFINITION 4.3.1 (CATEGORY OF FINITE-DIMENSIONAL MANY-SORTED CATEGORIES). Let $n \in \omega$. The *category of (small) many-sorted n -categories*, denoted by $n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$, is defined as follows:

- The objects of $n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ are the many-sorted n -categories such that $C_k \in \mathcal{U}$ for every $k \in n + 1$.
- For each pair $C, D \in \text{Ob}(n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}})$, the set of morphisms from C to D is the set of many-sorted n -functors from C to D .

Composition of morphisms is the componentwise composition of families of maps, and the identities are the families of identity maps. As we have just checked, these choices are well defined and the axioms of a category are satisfied without difficulty.

Analogously, we define the omega version of this category.

DEFINITION 4.3.2 (CATEGORY OF MANY-SORTED OMEGA CATEGORIES). The *category of (small) many-sorted ω -categories*, denoted by $\omega\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$, is defined as follows:

- The objects of $\omega\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ are the many-sorted ω -categories such that $C_k \in \mathcal{U}$ for every $k \in \omega$.
- For each pair $C, D \in \text{Ob}(\omega\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}})$, the set of morphisms from C to D is the set of many-sorted ω -functors from C to D .

Composition of morphisms is the componentwise composition of families of maps, and the identities are the families of identity maps. As in the finite-dimensional case, these choices are well defined and the axioms of a category are satisfied without difficulty.

Like Cat , $n\text{Cat}$ and ωCat , the categories $n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ and $\omega\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ are large categories, and their construction depends on the fixed universe \mathcal{U} .

Remark 4.3.3. As in the single-sorted case (cf. Remark 3.3.3), at no point have we excluded the value $n = 0$. In that case, the index $0 + 1 = \{0\}$ is a singleton, so there are no pairs $j < k$ and the family of operations is empty. Consequently, the axioms of a many-sorted category are vacuously satisfied and, for every set $C_0 \in \mathcal{U}$, the one-element family $C = ((C_0), ())$ is a many-sorted 0-category. Moreover, for every map $F_0 : C_0 \rightarrow D_0$, the one-element family (F_0) is a many-sorted 0-functor. In fact, the forgetful functor from 0Cat_{ms} to Set , sending each many-sorted 0-category to its single underlying set and each many-sorted 0-functor to its single underlying map, is an isomorphism of categories; hence 0Cat_{ms} is canonically isomorphic to Set , and in particular to 0Cat .

Finally, exactly as in the single-sorted case, given $n \in \omega + 1$ (cf. Remark 3.3.4), when referring to $n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ we may be talking about the finite-dimensional version if $n \in \omega$ or about the omega version

¹²When we write $(C_k)_k$ without specifying the index set, we refer indistinctly to $(C_k)_{k \in n+1}$ or $(C_k)_{k \in \omega}$, depending on whether we consider the finite-dimensional or the omega case.

if $n = \omega$. Hence, when indexed over $\omega + 1$, the symbol $n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ will not always refer to the finite-dimensional version.

§ 4.4

Discretization transformations

We again briefly diverge from [CCR26] and present an original construction, in parallel to what was done in the single-sorted case (cf. Section 3.4). In this section, we present a construction that, for each $n \in \omega + 1$, raises the dimension of any many-sorted n -category to an arbitrary dimension $m \in \omega + 1$ with $n \leq m$ by declaring all the added dimensions to be trivial. Moreover, we will extend this construction to functors and check that it is a functorial transformation: the *discretization* of a many-sorted category.

The only difference, with respect to the single-sorted construction, is structural: since each dimension now has its own set, it is not enough to define new operations; we also need to specify which set each added dimension uses. The natural choice is to replicate, in each new dimension, the set of the original top dimension.

DEFINITION 4.4.1 (DISCRETIZATION OF A MANY-SORTED CATEGORY). Let $n, m \in \omega + 1$ with $n \leq m$ and let C be a many-sorted n -category over the family $(C_k)_{k \in n+1}$. The *discretization of C at dimension m* , denoted by $C \uparrow^m$, is the many-sorted m -category over the family $(C_k \uparrow^m)_{k \in m+1}$ defined by

$$C_k \uparrow^m = \begin{cases} C_k & \text{if } k \leq n, \\ C_n & \text{if } n < k \leq m, \end{cases}$$

and with operations, for each pair $j < k$ in $m + 1$, given by:

- If $k \leq n$, the operations $\text{sc}^{(j,k)}$, $\text{tg}^{(j,k)}$, $\text{id}^{(k,j)}$ and $\#^{(j,k)}$ coincide with those of C .
- If $k > n$ and $j < n$, the operations $\text{sc}^{(j,k)}$, $\text{tg}^{(j,k)}$, $\text{id}^{(k,j)}$ and $\#^{(j,k)}$ are defined, respectively, as $\text{sc}^{(j,n)}$, $\text{tg}^{(j,n)}$, $\text{id}^{(n,j)}$ and $\#^{(j,n)}$ of C .
- If $n \leq j$ (and, therefore, $k > j \geq n$), $\text{sc}^{(j,k)}(f) = \text{tg}^{(j,k)}(f) = \text{id}^{(k,j)}(f) = f$ for every $f \in C_n$, and $\#^{(j,k)}$ is defined exactly on the pairs (f, f) with $f \in C_n$, with $f \#^{(j,k)} f = f$.

It is immediate to check that this construction satisfies the axioms of a many-sorted m -category: in each case, the equations (M1)–(M4) and (MB1)–(MB5) either involve only indices less than n and reduce to axioms of C , or involve higher indices whose operations coincide with those of dimension n and also reduce to axioms of C , or are trivial and reduce to equalities of the form $f = f$.

We now define the discretization for functors.

DEFINITION 4.4.2 (DISCRETIZATION OF A MANY-SORTED FUNCTOR). Let $n, m \in \omega + 1$ with $n \leq m$ and let $F = (F_k)_{k \in n+1} : C \rightarrow D$ be a many-sorted n -functor. The *discretization of F at dimension m* , denoted by $F \uparrow^m : C \uparrow^m \rightarrow D \uparrow^m$, is the family $(F_k \uparrow^m)_{k \in m+1}$ defined by

$$F_k \uparrow^m = \begin{cases} F_k & \text{if } k \leq n, \\ F_n & \text{if } n < k \leq m, \end{cases}$$

viewed as a many-sorted m -functor from $C\uparrow^m$ to $D\uparrow^m$.

Once again, the verification of axioms (MF1)–(MF3) is direct: for pairs of indices less than n they reduce to those of F itself, and for pairs with higher indices they reduce to trivial identifications.

Remark 4.4.3. When $n = m$, the discretization of a many-sorted category or functor coincides with the category or functor itself, respectively.

We finally consider the discretization as a functor (in the classical sense) between the categories of many-sorted categories.

DEFINITION 4.4.4 (MANY-SORTED DISCRETIZATION FUNCTOR). Let $n, m \in \omega + 1$ with $n \leq m$. The *discretization functor*, denoted by $\mathcal{D}_{\text{ms}}^{(m,n)}$, is the functor

$$\mathcal{D}_{\text{ms}}^{(m,n)} : n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}} \longrightarrow m\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$$

that assigns to each n -category C its discretization $C\uparrow^m$ and to each n -functor F its discretization $F\uparrow^m$.

Preservation of identities and composition is immediate, since the discretization extends the underlying family without altering its components in the dimensions less than n and replicates the top component in the new dimensions.

Remark 4.4.5. By Remark 4.4.3, the discretization functor $\mathcal{D}_{\text{ms}}^{(n,n)}$ is the identity on $n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$, $\text{id}_{n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}}$, for every $n \in \omega + 1$.

§ 4.5

Underlying transformations

In contrast to the discretization transformation of Section 4.4, we now present a transformation that, for each $n \in \omega + 1$, lowers the dimension of any many-sorted n -category to an arbitrary dimension $m \in \omega + 1$ with $m \leq n$ by discarding all the dimensions above m . Moreover, we will extend this construction to functors and check that it is a functorial transformation: the *underlying* of a many-sorted category.

Unlike the single-sorted case, where the underlying transformation required checking that the operations admitted birestrictions to the subset of m -cells (cf. Lemma 3.5.1 and Lemma 3.5.2), in the many-sorted presentation no preliminary result is needed: since each dimension already has its own set, it suffices to restrict the family to the desired index and discard the operations above it.

DEFINITION 4.5.1 (UNDERLYING OF A MANY-SORTED CATEGORY). Let $n, m \in \omega + 1$ with $m \leq n$ and let C be a many-sorted n -category over the family $(C_k)_{k \in n+1}$. The *underlying of C at dimension m* , denoted by $C\downarrow_m$, is the many-sorted m -category over the restricted family $(C_k)_{k \in m+1}$, with the operations $\text{sc}^{(j,k)}$, $\text{tg}^{(j,k)}$, $\text{id}^{(k,j)}$ and $\#^{(j,k)}$ (for each pair $j < k$ in $m + 1$) inherited directly from C .

The axioms (M1)–(M4) and (MB1)–(MB5) of $C \downarrow_m$ are, literally, the corresponding axioms of C restricted to the pairs and triples of indices $\leq m$.

We now define the underlying for functors.

DEFINITION 4.5.2 (UNDERLYING OF A MANY-SORTED FUNCTOR). Let $n, m \in \omega + 1$ with $m \leq n$ and let $F = (F_k)_{k \in n+1} : C \rightarrow D$ be a many-sorted n -functor. The *underlying of F at dimension m* , denoted by $F \downarrow_m : C \downarrow_m \rightarrow D \downarrow_m$, is the restricted family $(F_k)_{k \in m+1}$.

Once again, the axioms (MF1)–(MF3) of $F \downarrow_m$ are those of F restricted to the pairs of indices $\leq m$.

Remark 4.5.3. When $m = n$, the underlying of a many-sorted category or functor is precisely the original category or functor, respectively.

We finally consider the underlying as a functor (in the classical sense) between the categories of many-sorted categories.

DEFINITION 4.5.4 (MANY-SORTED UNDERLYING FUNCTOR). Let $n, m \in \omega + 1$ with $m \leq n$. The *underlying functor*, denoted by $\mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(m,n)}$, is the functor

$$\mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(m,n)} : n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}} \longrightarrow m\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$$

that assigns to each n -category C its underlying $C \downarrow_m$ and to each n -functor F its underlying $F \downarrow_m$.

Preservation of identities and composition follows immediately: restricting the identity family gives the identity family on the retained sets, and restriction commutes with the componentwise composition.

Remark 4.5.5. By Remark 4.5.3, the underlying functor $\mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(n,n)}$ is the identity on $n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$, $\text{id}_{n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}}$, for every $n \in \omega + 1$.

CHAPTER FIVE

5

Equivalence of the presentations

Throughout the two previous chapters we have developed two distinct presentations of the notion of higher-order category. Although the definitions differ in form (a single set of morphisms with operations indexed by dimension, in the single-sorted case, as opposed to an indexed family of sets of morphisms with operations typed by pairs of dimensions, in the many-sorted case), we have suggested on several occasions that both presentations describe the same structure. The purpose of this chapter is to make this claim precise: we will construct a pair of functors between $n\text{Cat}$ and $n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ and prove that these functors establish an equivalence of categories in the sense of Definition 2.3.5. We will also see the mechanism by which we can extend this equivalence to the infinite-dimensional case of ω -categories.

We again follow the development of [CCR26, § 5]. However, as we will anticipate at the end of this chapter and discuss in detail in Chapter 7, the formalization in Lean of this equivalence presents certain technical obstacles that place it outside the scope of this project. We present this chapter as the closing of the mathematical thread that we have developed in the work, so that, without entering into the specific details of each proof, one has a precise idea of how the equivalence is constructed and that allows us to develop the discussion about its formalization that we mentioned. We will indicate at each point where the complete details of each construction and each proof can be found in [CCR26].

§ 5.1

Graduation

We begin with the construction that goes from the single-sorted presentation to the many-sorted one. As we have mentioned repeatedly in Chapter 3, given a single-sorted n -category C , the sets of k -cells naturally endowed C with a hierarchy over its underlying set of morphisms C . To construct a many-sorted n -category we must provide an indexed family of underlying sets. With the previous observation in mind, the choice is natural: for each $k \in n$, the set of k -cells of C is taken as the underlying set of k -morphisms of the many-sorted n -category we are trying to construct. The set of n -morphisms is identified with C itself, as we already anticipated in Definition 3.1.8. It remains to see how we define the source, target, identity and composition operations of the resulting many-sorted n -category.

On the one hand, the identity operation is the one that assigned to each j -morphism a k -morphism of higher dimension which acted as the identity for composition of dimension j . But, since the single-sorted presentation started from identifying each j -morphism with its k -morphism identity, to define this operation it suffices to “undo” this identification, that is, the identity of a j -cell f is nothing but f viewed as a k -cell through the canonical inclusion of C_j into C_k , given by axiom (SB1).

The source, target and composition operations admit, in turn, an equally direct description. The idea is now the opposite of that of the identity: the single-sorted operations already range over the entire underlying set C and, in particular, act on the k -cells of each dimension, so it suffices to restrict them to the appropriate subsets. Concretely, for each pair of indices $j < k$ in $n + 1$, the source $\text{sc}^{(j,k)}$ is defined as the birestriction of sc^j to the domain C_k and codomain C_j , and, analogously, the target $\text{tg}^{(j,k)}$ as the birestriction of tg^j to the same sets. That both birestrictions are well

defined follows from axiom (S1). For the partial composition, $\#^{(j,k)}$ is defined as the birestriction of $\#^j$ to $C_k \times C_k$ and C_k , a birestriction that is well defined thanks to axiom (SB2).

This process, which produces a many-sorted n -category from a single-sorted n -category, will be called *graduation*.

DEFINITION 5.1.1 (GRADUATION OF A SINGLE-SORTED CATEGORY). Let $n \in \omega$ and let

$$C = \left(C, \left(\text{sc}^k, \text{tg}^k, \#^k \right)_{k \in n} \right)$$

be a single-sorted n -category. The *graduation* of C , denoted by $\text{Gd}^{(n)}(C)$, is the many-sorted n -category with family of underlying sets $(C_k)_{k \in n+1}$, where, for each $k \in n$, C_k is the set of k -cells of C and, moreover, C_n is identified with C . For each pair of indices $j, k \in n+1$ with $j < k$, the operations are defined as follows:

- The identity $\text{id}^{(k,j)} : C_j \rightarrow C_k$ is the canonical inclusion of C_j into C_k .
- The source $\text{sc}^{(j,k)} : C_k \rightarrow C_j$ is the birestriction of sc^j to C_k and C_j .
- The target $\text{tg}^{(j,k)} : C_k \rightarrow C_j$ is the birestriction of tg^j to C_k and C_j .
- The composition $\#^{(j,k)} : C_k \times C_k \rightarrow C_k$ is the birestriction of $\#^j$ to $C_k \times C_k$ and C_k .

In the previous definition we have called $\text{Gd}^{(n)}(C)$ a many-sorted n -category. The following proposition confirms that this denomination is correct.

PROPOSITION 5.1.2. *In the situation of Definition 5.1.1, $\text{Gd}^{(n)}(C)$ is a many-sorted n -category in the sense of Definition 4.1.5.*

In Chapter 4 we already mentioned the relation between the axioms of the many-sorted presentation and those of the single-sorted presentation. The proof of this proposition follows easily from these relations. The details can be found in [CCR26, Proposition 5.5.2].

We now extend the construction to functors. The idea is the same as in the case of objects: given a single-sorted n -functor $F : C \rightarrow D$, it suffices to take, in each dimension $k < n$, the birestriction of F to C_k and D_k , and the map F itself in dimension n . That these birestrictions are well defined follows from axiom (SF1).

DEFINITION 5.1.3 (GRADUATION OF A SINGLE-SORTED FUNCTOR). Let $n \in \omega$, let C and D be two single-sorted n -categories and let $F : C \rightarrow D$ be a single-sorted n -functor. The *graduation* of F , denoted by $\text{Gd}^{(n)}(F) : \text{Gd}^{(n)}(C) \rightarrow \text{Gd}^{(n)}(D)$, is the family of maps $(F_k : C_k \rightarrow D_k)_{k \in n+1}$ where, for each $k \in n$, F_k is the birestriction of F to C_k and D_k and $F_n = F$.

Again, we have called $\text{Gd}^{(n)}(F)$ a many-sorted n -functor. The following proposition confirms that this denomination is correct.

PROPOSITION 5.1.4. *In the situation of Definition 5.1.3, $\text{Gd}^{(n)}(F)$ is a many-sorted n -functor in the sense of Definition 4.2.1.*

Analogously to the case of categories, the proof follows from the relation between the axioms of a many-sorted n -functor and those of a single-sorted n -functor together with the definition of the graduation. The details can be found in [CCR26, Proposition 5.5.4].

Finally, we organize the graduation as a functor between the categories of categories of each presentation.

DEFINITION 5.1.5 (GRADUATION FUNCTOR). Let $n \in \omega$. The *graduation functor* is the functor

$$\mathrm{Gd}^{(n)} : n\mathrm{Cat} \longrightarrow n\mathrm{Cat}_{\mathrm{ms}}$$

that assigns to each single-sorted n -category C its graduation $\mathrm{Gd}^{(n)}(C)$ and to each single-sorted n -functor F its graduation $\mathrm{Gd}^{(n)}(F)$.

Once again, we have called $\mathrm{Gd}^{(n)}$ a functor. The following proposition confirms that this denomination is correct.

PROPOSITION 5.1.6 (FUNCTORIALITY OF THE GRADUATION). For every $n \in \omega$, $\mathrm{Gd}^{(n)} : n\mathrm{Cat} \longrightarrow n\mathrm{Cat}_{\mathrm{ms}}$ is a functor in the sense of Definition 2.2.4.

Preservation of identities and composition follows immediately from the fact that the birestriction of the identity map is the identity on the corresponding subset and from the fact that birestriction commutes with composition. The details can be found in [CCR26, Proposition 5.5.5].

§ 5.2

Unification

We now move on to the opposite construction: from the many-sorted presentation to the single-sorted one. As we saw in Chapter 3, a single-sorted n -category rests on a single underlying set C that gathers all the morphisms of the n -category, on which the operations of each dimension act. Given a many-sorted n -category C with family of underlying sets $(C_k)_{k \in n+1}$, we must then provide a single underlying set for the single-sorted n -category that we are trying to construct. The choice is again natural: since the identities $\mathrm{id}^{(n,k)}$ allow us to view each k -morphism of C as an n -cell in C_n , we take C_n as the underlying set. It remains to see how we define, for each $k \in n$, the source, target and composition operations of the resulting single-sorted n -category.

On the one hand, the source and target operations at dimension k assign to an n -cell f its k -source and k -target, respectively. In the many-sorted presentation these operations are given by $\mathrm{sc}^{(k,n)}$ and $\mathrm{tg}^{(k,n)}$, but their images live in C_k , so we must again identify each k -morphism with its associated n -cell through $\mathrm{id}^{(n,k)}$. We thus define

$$\mathrm{sc}^k = \mathrm{id}^{(n,k)} \circ \mathrm{sc}^{(k,n)} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathrm{tg}^k = \mathrm{id}^{(n,k)} \circ \mathrm{tg}^{(k,n)}.$$

The partial composition at dimension k , in turn, already operates on n -cells, so it suffices to take $\#^k = \#^{(k,n)}$.

This process, which produces a single-sorted n -category from a many-sorted n -category, will be called *unification*.

DEFINITION 5.2.1 (UNIFICATION OF A MANY-SORTED CATEGORY). Let $n \in \omega$ and let

$$C = \left((C_k)_{k \in n+1}, \left(\text{sc}^{(j,k)}, \text{tg}^{(j,k)}, \text{id}^{(k,j)}, \#^{(j,k)} \right)_{j,k \in n+1, j < k} \right)$$

be a many-sorted n -category. The *unification* of C , denoted by $\text{Uf}^{(n)}(C)$, is the single-sorted n -category with underlying set C_n and operations, for each $k \in n$, given by

$$\text{sc}^k = \text{id}^{(n,k)} \circ \text{sc}^{(k,n)}, \quad \text{tg}^k = \text{id}^{(n,k)} \circ \text{tg}^{(k,n)}, \quad \#^k = \#^{(k,n)}.$$

In the previous definition we have called $\text{Uf}^{(n)}(C)$ a single-sorted n -category. The following proposition confirms that this denomination is correct.

PROPOSITION 5.2.2. *In the situation of Definition 5.2.1, $\text{Uf}^{(n)}(C)$ is a single-sorted n -category in the sense of Definition 3.1.3.*

As in the case of the graduation, the proof follows from the relation between the axioms of the single-sorted presentation and those of the many-sorted presentation together with the definition of the unification. The details can be found in [CCR26, Proposition 5.6.3].

We now extend the construction to functors. Unlike the case of the graduation, where a single-sorted n -functor gave rise to a family of maps birestricted to each dimension, here a single map suffices: the dimension- n component of the many-sorted n -functor, since it is this one that acts between the underlying sets C_n and D_n of the respective unifications.

DEFINITION 5.2.3 (UNIFICATION OF A MANY-SORTED FUNCTOR). Let $n \in \omega$, let C and D be two many-sorted n -categories and let $F = (F_k)_{k \in n+1} : C \longrightarrow D$ be a many-sorted n -functor. The *unification* of F , denoted by $\text{Uf}^{(n)}(F) : \text{Uf}^{(n)}(C) \longrightarrow \text{Uf}^{(n)}(D)$, is the map $F_n : C_n \longrightarrow D_n$.

Again, we have called $\text{Uf}^{(n)}(F)$ a single-sorted n -functor. The following proposition confirms that this denomination is correct.

PROPOSITION 5.2.4. *In the situation of Definition 5.2.3, $\text{Uf}^{(n)}(F)$ is a single-sorted n -functor in the sense of Definition 3.2.1.*

Analogously to the case of categories, the proof follows from the relation between the axioms of a single-sorted n -functor and those of a many-sorted n -functor together with the definition of the unification. The details can be found in [CCR26, Proposition 5.6.5].

Finally, we organize the unification as a functor between the categories of categories of each presentation.

DEFINITION 5.2.5 (UNIFICATION FUNCTOR). Let $n \in \omega$. The *unification functor* is the functor

$$\text{Uf}^{(n)} : n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}} \longrightarrow n\text{Cat}$$

that assigns to each many-sorted n -category C its unification $\text{Uf}^{(n)}(C)$ and to each many-sorted n -functor F its unification $\text{Uf}^{(n)}(F)$.

Once again, we have called $\text{Uf}^{(n)}$ a functor. The following proposition confirms that this denomination is correct.

PROPOSITION 5.2.6 (FUNCTORIALITY OF THE UNIFICATION). *For every $n \in \omega$, $\text{Uf}^{(n)} : n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}} \rightarrow n\text{Cat}$ is a functor in the sense of Definition 2.2.4.*

Preservation of identities and composition follows immediately from the fact that the unification takes the dimension- n component of the corresponding families and, at this level, the identities and compositions of families of maps reduce to the identities and compositions of their components. The details can be found in [CCR26, Proposition 5.6.6].

§ 5.3

Equivalence between the finite-dimensional presentations

By means of the graduation and unification transformations, we have constructed a pair of functors between $n\text{Cat}$ and $n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ and vice versa, for each $n \in \omega$. We will now see that this is a situation of equivalence of categories in the sense of Definition 2.3.5.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} & \text{Gd}^{(n)} & \\ & \curvearrowright & \\ n\text{Cat} & & n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}} \\ & \curvearrowleft & \\ & \text{Uf}^{(n)} & \end{array}$$

The situation is, in fact, somewhat stronger. If we start from a single-sorted n -category C and apply the graduation, the underlying set of dimension n is C itself and the operations of each lower dimension are birestrictions of those of C . Upon unifying, the underlying set becomes C again and the operations, when replacing the birestrictions by the original operations, reduce exactly to sc^k , tg^k and $\#^k$. For a single-sorted n -functor $F : C \rightarrow D$ the argument is identical: the graduation decomposes it into a family of birestrictions whose dimension- n component is F itself and the unification keeps precisely that component. One of the two compositions thus coincides with the identity.

PROPOSITION 5.3.1. *For every $n \in \omega$,*

$$\text{Uf}^{(n)} \circ \text{Gd}^{(n)} = \text{id}_{n\text{Cat}}.$$

The details appear in [CCR26, Proposition 5.7.1].

In the other order, the composition no longer coincides with the identity. Given a many-sorted n -category C with underlying family $(C_k)_{k \in n+1}$, its unification has C_n as its sole underlying set. Upon graduating again, the resulting underlying sets, $(C'_k)_{k \in n+1}$, are subsets of C_n formed by the k -cells in the single-sorted sense of the unification, that is, the images of $\text{id}^{(n,k)}$, and, in general, $C'_k \neq C_k$. This difference, however, reduces to a natural isomorphism: in each dimension $k < n$, the inclusion $\text{id}^{(n,k)} : C_k \rightarrow C'_k$ admits as inverse the corresponding birestriction of $\text{sc}^{(k,n)}$. Indeed, axiom (M2) applied to the pair (k, n) gives the first identity

$$\text{sc}^{(k,n)} \circ \text{id}^{(n,k)} = \text{id}_{C'_k},$$

and the second,

$$\mathrm{id}^{(n,k)} \circ \mathrm{sc}^{(k,n)} = \mathrm{id}_{C'_k},$$

follows from the previous one and from the very definition of C'_k as image of $\mathrm{id}^{(n,k)}$: every $f' \in C'_k$ is of the form $\mathrm{id}^{(n,k)}(f)$ for some $f \in C_k$, so $\mathrm{id}^{(n,k)}(\mathrm{sc}^{(k,n)}(f')) = \mathrm{id}^{(n,k)}(f) = f'$.

PROPOSITION 5.3.2. *For every $n \in \omega$,*

$$\mathrm{Gd}^{(n)} \circ \mathrm{Uf}^{(n)} \cong \mathrm{id}_{n\mathrm{Cat}_{\mathrm{ms}}}.$$

The previous intuition materializes, for each many-sorted n -category C , in a pair of mutually inverse many-sorted n -functors

$$\alpha^C : C \longrightarrow \mathrm{Gd}^{(n)}(\mathrm{Uf}^{(n)}(C)) \quad \text{and} \quad \beta^C : \mathrm{Gd}^{(n)}(\mathrm{Uf}^{(n)}(C)) \longrightarrow C,$$

given, at each dimension, by

$$\alpha_k^C = \begin{cases} \mathrm{id}^{(n,k)} & \text{if } k < n, \\ \mathrm{id}_{C_n} & \text{if } k = n \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_k^C = \begin{cases} \mathrm{sc}^{(k,n)} & \text{if } k < n, \\ \mathrm{id}_{C_n} & \text{if } k = n. \end{cases}$$

That they are inverses follows from the identities we have just mentioned and, in turn, the naturality of the family $\alpha = (\alpha^C)_{C \in \mathrm{Ob}(n\mathrm{Cat}_{\mathrm{ms}})}$ follows from the preservation of identities by the many-sorted n -functors, as axiom (MF2) establishes. The naturality of $\beta = (\beta^C)_{C \in \mathrm{Ob}(n\mathrm{Cat}_{\mathrm{ms}})}$ then follows automatically, since it is the pointwise inverse of α . The details can be found in [CCR26, Proposition 5.7.2].

Combining the two previous results with the notion of equivalence of categories introduced in Definition 2.3.5, we obtain the main result of this chapter.

THEOREM 5.3.3 (EQUIVALENCE BETWEEN THE FINITE-DIMENSIONAL PRESENTATIONS). *For every $n \in \omega$, the categories $n\mathrm{Cat}$ and $n\mathrm{Cat}_{\mathrm{ms}}$ are equivalent. Moreover, by Proposition 2.3.11, $\mathrm{Gd}^{(n)}$ is both a left and a right adjoint of $\mathrm{Uf}^{(n)}$.*

§ 5.4

The equivalence in the infinite-dimensional case

The passage to the infinite-dimensional case requires mechanisms distinct from those of the finite-dimensional case in each of the two constructions. For the graduation, the infinite-dimensional functor is built from the finite-dimensional ones by means of a universal property of $\omega\mathrm{Cat}_{\mathrm{ms}}$ as the projective limit of the finite-dimensional categories. For the unification, on the other hand, we no longer have a top dimension that serves as a single underlying set and it is necessary to construct it from scratch, as a quotient of the coproduct of the levels. We briefly summarize both; the details appear in [CCR26, § 5.8 and § 5.9].

We begin with the graduation. The basic tool is the following structural property of $\omega\mathrm{Cat}_{\mathrm{ms}}$, which is not developed in the previous chapters and which can be found in more detail in [CCR26, § 5.4]. The underlying functors $\mathcal{U}_{\mathrm{ms}}^{(m,n)} : n\mathrm{Cat}_{\mathrm{ms}} \longrightarrow m\mathrm{Cat}_{\mathrm{ms}}$ are compatible among themselves,

in the sense that $\mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(m,n)} \circ \mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(n,p)} = \mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(m,p)}$ for every $m \leq n \leq p$ in ω . The family¹³ $(\cdot)\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}, \mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(\cdot, \cdot)}$ thus obtained forms a projective system in a category of categories¹⁴, and $\omega\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$, together with the omega underlyings $(\mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(n, \omega)})_{n \in \omega}$, is its projective limit. That is, for every category L and every family of functors $(F_n : L \rightarrow n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}})_{n \in \omega}$ compatible with the underlyings, that is, such that $F_m = \mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(m,n)} \circ F_n$ for every $m \leq n$ in ω , there exists a unique functor $\langle F_k \rangle_{k \in \omega} : L \rightarrow \omega\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ that factors each F_n through the omega underlying, as illustrated in the following diagram:

We apply this universal property to the family formed by the finite-dimensional graduations preceded by the single-sorted underlying. For each $n \in \omega$, the composition $\text{Gd}^{(n)} \circ \mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(n, \omega)} : \omega\text{Cat} \rightarrow n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ is a functor, and these compositions fit together with the many-sorted underlyings: for every $m \leq n$ in ω it holds that

$$\mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(m, n)} \circ \text{Gd}^{(n)} \circ \mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(n, \omega)} = \text{Gd}^{(m)} \circ \mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(m, \omega)}.$$

The universal property of $\omega\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ then produces a unique functor

$$\text{Gd}^{(\omega)} : \omega\text{Cat} \rightarrow \omega\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$$

that factors each $\text{Gd}^{(n)} \circ \mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(n, \omega)}$ through the omega underlying $\mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(n, \omega)}$. What this path contributes, compared to a direct construction dimension by dimension, is that the functoriality and well-definedness of the result are guaranteed by the uniqueness of the factorizer, without the need to check by hand that the axioms of a many-sorted category are satisfied in each dimension.

Although the construction is implicit, it admits an explicit description as in the finite-dimensional case. Given a single-sorted ω -category C , $\text{Gd}^{(\omega)}(C)$ is the many-sorted ω -category with underlying family $(C_k)_{k \in \omega}$ formed by the sets of k -cells of C and with operations obtained by birestriction dimension by dimension, exactly as in the finite-dimensional case. The graduation of a single-sorted ω -functor is, analogously, the family of its birestrictions to each C_k .

Let us move on to the unification. In the finite-dimensional case, the underlying set of the unification was C_n , that of the top dimension, accessible via the identities $\text{id}^{(n, k)}$ from any lower dimension. In the infinite-dimensional case no such top dimension exists and we need to produce a single set that gathers the whole family $(C_k)_{k \in \omega}$. The idea is to identify each k -morphism with all

¹³We identify $(\cdot)\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ with $(n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}})_{n \in \omega}$ and $\mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(\cdot, \cdot)}$ with $(\mathcal{U}_{\text{ms}}^{(m, n)})_{m, n \in \omega, m \leq n}$.

¹⁴Strictly speaking, $n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ is not an object of the category Cat from Chapter 2, since it is not a small category in \mathcal{U} . By the Tarski-Grothendieck axiom, there exists a universe \mathcal{U}' with $\omega\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}} \in \mathcal{U}'$. The category of \mathcal{U}' -small categories, which contains all the $n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ and also Cat , is the ambient category we are referring to here. This is the only construction in this work in which we need to invoke a universe larger than the base universe \mathcal{U} .

its images via $\text{id}^{(k',k)}$ in the dimensions $k' > k$: two elements that are obtained from one another by repeatedly raising through identities must represent the same morphism in the unification. Formally, we take the coproduct $C_\omega = \coprod_{k \in \omega} C_k$, whose elements are pairs (f, j) with $f \in C_j$, and we quotient it by the equivalence relation Θ that identifies (f, j) with (g, k) precisely when $j < k$ and $g = \text{id}^{(k,j)}(f)$, $j = k$ and $f = g$, or $k < j$ and $f = \text{id}^{(j,k)}(g)$. We therefore define the underlying set of $\text{Uf}^{(\omega)}(C)$ as

$$[C_\omega] = C_\omega / \Theta.$$

The relation Θ is reflexive and symmetric by construction. Its transitivity follows from the composition of identities (MB3) together with the injectivity of the identity maps (Proposition 4.1.2, applied to each pair of dimensions), so that Θ is indeed an equivalence relation.

Equivalently, $[C_\omega]$ is the inductive limit in Set of the system given by the family $(C_k)_{k \in \omega}$ and the many-sorted identities between contiguous dimensions $(\text{id}^{(k+1,k)})_{k \in \omega}$, which is illustrated in the following universal-property diagram, valid for any $j < k$ in ω :

The source, target and composition operations on $[C_\omega]$ are then induced from those of C by working with representatives in sufficiently high dimensions: every class $[f]_j$ admits a representative in each dimension $j' \geq j$, so that, given two classes, we can always choose a common level from which to apply the original many-sorted operations and project back to the quotient. Axiom (ω S1), which distinguished the single-sorted ω -category from the single-sorted n -category, is satisfied automatically: each class $[f]_j$ admits a representative (f, j) in C_j , and the definition of sc^k on $[C_\omega]$ then gives $\text{sc}^j([f]_j) = [f]_j$, which stabilizes the dimension from a finite index onwards.

Once both constructions are established, the proofs that they are functorial and (quasi)-inverses reproduce the pattern of the finite-dimensional case, with a nuance worth highlighting. In the finite-dimensional case we had the strict equality $\text{Uf}^{(n)} \circ \text{Gd}^{(n)} = \text{id}_{n\text{Cat}}$, whereas now the corresponding composition is only naturally isomorphic to the identity. The reason is clear: the underlying set of $\text{Uf}^{(\omega)}(\text{Gd}^{(\omega)}(C))$ is a quotient of a coproduct and, therefore, not identical to the original set C . The other composition, $\text{Gd}^{(\omega)} \circ \text{Uf}^{(\omega)}$, is naturally isomorphic to the identity, just as in the finite-dimensional case.

THEOREM 5.4.1 (EQUIVALENCE BETWEEN THE INFINITE-DIMENSIONAL PRESENTATIONS). *The categories ωCat and $\omega\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ are equivalent. Moreover, by Proposition 2.3.11, $\text{Gd}^{(\omega)}$ is both a left and a right adjoint of $\text{Uf}^{(\omega)}$.*

Recalling now the convention introduced in Remark 3.3.4, we can synthesize the previous results in a single statement.

COROLLARY 5.4.2. *For every $n \in \omega + 1$, the categories $n\text{Cat}$ and $n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ are equivalent.*

§ 5.5

The technical obstacles

Throughout the previous sections we have constructed a pair of functors between $n\text{Cat}$ and $n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ and proved that these establish an equivalence of categories. The verifications that make up the proof are, for the most part, substitutions of equals and direct applications of the relations between the axioms of both presentations that we have already made explicit in previous chapters. Nevertheless, their formalization in Lean encounters obstacles that place it outside the scope of this project.

The main difficulty originates in how the underlying sets of each dimension are formalized in the many-sorted presentation. In Lean, these are encoded as an *indexed family of types* $(C_k)_{k \in n+1}$, that is, a function that assigns to each index k a type C_k . In Lean's dependent type theory, since each type C_k is distinct from the others, an equality between elements of C_k and C_j with $k \neq j$ ceases to be an equality in the classical sense and becomes what we call a *heterogeneous equality*, whose handling demands specific mechanisms of the system that add considerable technical complexity to each step of the proofs. It is worth emphasizing that the difficulty is purely technical and does not introduce any real mathematical complexity.

Theorem 5.3.3 crosses this frontier in a systematic way. The construction of the many-sorted n -functors α^C and β^C that establish the natural isomorphism between $\text{Gd}^{(n)} \circ \text{Uf}^{(n)}$ and the identity of $n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ requires, at each dimension $k < n$, identifying the original set C_k with the set C'_k obtained upon graduating the unification, the latter defined as the image of $\text{id}^{(n,k)}$ inside C_n . In the classical proof, the equality $\text{id}^{(n,k)} \circ \text{sc}^{(k,n)} = \text{id}_{C'_k}$ is justified by observing that every $f' \in C'_k$ is of the form $\text{id}^{(n,k)}(f)$ for some $f \in C_k$ and substituting f by $\text{sc}^{(k,n)}(f')$. In the formalization, however, C_k and C'_k are distinct types: one is the k -th component of the underlying family, the other a subtype of C_n . The substitution of equals in the classical proof ceases to be a free step and becomes an explicit transport along an equality of types.

To this main obstacle other difficulties of the same order are added. The validity of the signatures of the many-sorted operations, restricted to pairs of indices $j < k$, must be conveyed to Lean in each definition and each lemma, whether by means of subtypes or of dependent types. Added to this is an exhaustive case analysis over the dimension indices that, while mathematically trivial, turns out to be tedious in formal practice.

The complete discussion of these issues is found in Chapter 7, where we will go into more detail on each of the concepts that we have mentioned here.

CHAPTER SIX

6

Preliminaries on formal verification

It soon became clear that the only real long-term solution to the problems that I encountered is to start using computers in the verification of mathematical reasoning.

— Vladimir Voevodsky, *Univalent Foundations* (2014)

With this chapter we begin the second part of the work, dedicated to the formalization in Lean of the mathematical content developed in the first part. The aim of this chapter is to provide a basic context on what formal verification is and how it is concretely carried out in Lean 4, the system that we will use in our formalization.

We articulate the chapter in a gradual way. We will begin by explaining what we understand by *formal verification* and what role the so-called *proof assistants* play in it. Next we will introduce the conceptual pillars of this discipline: type theory, the Curry-Howard isomorphism and, for the specific case of Lean, dependent type theory. In the last sections, we will present Lean 4 as a proof assistant, going through its basic functioning and its most relevant features, and the mathematical library Mathlib.

§ 6.1

Formal verification

Before speaking of formal verification, it is worth talking about its counterpart: *informal verification*, which is the one we in fact use in usual mathematical work. We tend to think that the mathematics we do is already “formal”, since we work with precise definitions and demand rigour at each step. However, an ordinary mathematical proof is not formal in the sense that interests us here. It is not a sequence of elementary inferences chained back to the axioms, written in an artificial language with a fixed repertoire of rules, but rather a natural-language text, addressed to a competent reader, that omits the routine steps and rests on the shared understanding of the community [Hal08]. What we call *mathematical rigour* is the well-founded conviction that those omitted steps could be completed if necessary, by reducing them to those elementary inferences.

The correctness of a proof of this kind is established, in practice, through a social process: peer review and, ultimately, the community’s consensus. It is what we here call informal verification. The procedure is reliable and has sustained the bulk of mathematics, but it is not infallible. As proofs grow in length and complexity, human review becomes more fragile: it is easy to overlook a case, to take for granted an implicitly assumed hypothesis or not to notice a poorly justified leap. Indeed, there is no shortage of examples of proofs accepted for years that later turned out to have gaps, nor of theorems whose proof is so extensive that no reviewer can check it completely with guarantees.

Formal verification responds to this situation in the most direct way: mechanizing the checking of correctness. Instead of leaving the ultimate judgement in the hands of a human reviewer, the proof is required to be written in sufficient detail that one can check, step by step, that each inference follows from the previous ones all the way to the axioms [AH14]. In this way, we can reduce the problem of validating a proof to something that, for instance, a computer would execute in a purely mechanical way, eliminating any subjective judgement.

Although the idea of mechanizing the correctness of a proof may seem recent, its origins are old. Russell and Whitehead’s *Principia Mathematica* (1910–1913) are a first attempt, made by hand and with a notation that today is hardly manageable, to derive mathematics from a completely explicit axiomatic system. The appearance of computers made viable, decades later, what could then only be tackled by hand. A clear formulation of this idea is the *QED Manifesto* [Ano94], published

anonymously in 1994, which proposed as a long-term goal a repository of the bulk of mathematical knowledge completely formalized and machine-verified. Subsequent development has been less centralized than that proposal, but the underlying idea persists and is, to a large extent, gradually materializing [Avi24].

The concrete way in which formal verification is carried out today rests on a simple architecture: the correctness of each proof is checked by a deliberately small software *kernel*, whose only task is to verify that each proposed term is really an inhabitant of the type ascribed to it. That the kernel be small is important, since it is the only piece that must be reliable for the whole system to be so. Everything else can be arbitrarily complex, since its output is again submitted to the kernel. This principle, according to which the basis of trust reduces to a small and auditable verifier, is known as the *de Bruijn criterion* [Har08].

The tools that put this architecture into practice are *proof assistants* (also called *interactive theorem provers*, ITP): systems in which the user constructs a proof that the kernel verifies simultaneously. There are several in active use, among which Lean, Coq (recently renamed Rocq), Agda, Isabelle or HOL Light stand out. Each rests on distinct logical foundations and has been oriented towards distinct communities and problems; in this work we focus exclusively on Lean, and in particular on version 4.

It is worth mentioning, finally, some milestones of the last two decades that show the practical viability of all this. The four colour theorem was formalized by Gonthier in Coq, completed in 2005 and described in [Gon08], probably the first example of relevance in pure mathematics. A few years later, the same Gonthier coordinated the formalization of the Feit–Thompson theorem on the solvability of groups of odd order [Gon+13]. In parallel, Hales completed in 2014 the *Flyspeck* project, which formalizes the Kepler conjecture in Isabelle and HOL Light and was published in [Hal+17]. More recently, in Lean, the *Liquid Tensor Experiment* formalized a central theorem of condensed mathematics, proposed as a challenge by Peter Scholze [CT24], and the formalization of Marton’s PFR conjecture, a result of Gowers, Green, Manners and Tao, was completed within weeks of the proof being announced, in an effort led by Tao himself [TDM23]. These last two examples give an idea of the level of complexity that the ecosystem can address today.

The combination of increasingly ambitious mathematical libraries (in the case of Lean, Mathlib) with the growing integration between proof assistants and artificial intelligence has made formalization a rapidly expanding area [Avi24].

§ 6.2

Type theory

In Chapter 2 we assumed the usual framework¹⁵ of set theory. It is the language in which we usually think mathematics: a single universe of sets, related by membership, on top of which everything else is constructed. It is a comfortable and flexible language for us, but it is not the one that machines do best. The reason is that set-theoretic membership, $a \in A$, is a proposition: asserting that a belongs to A is to state something that can be true or false and that, in general, has to be

¹⁵With the Tarski–Grothendieck axiom (cf. Axiom 2.1.2).

proved. There is no way to decide mechanically, by the mere analysis of a and A , whether the membership holds or not.

Type theory is another way of grounding mathematics, and it has the advantage of being, precisely, the language that computers usually speak. In it, each object belongs to a single *type*, which acts as its primary container and is fixed at the moment of constructing the object. This contrasts with the set-theoretic approach, where the same object can be an element of many sets at once. The difference is deeper than it seems: checking that an object has a given type is not proving a proposition, but applying an algorithm. It is, in fact, the same type-checking on which the kernel of a proof assistant rests, as we saw in the previous section. This is why type theory, and not set theory, is the natural foundation of these systems.

Historically, type theory was born at the beginning of the 20th century as a response to Russell's paradox. The *ramified theory of types* that Russell and Whitehead employed in the *Principia Mathematica* stratified the mathematical universe into disjoint levels: the objects of one level could only be combined to produce objects of the next level, which ruled out from the root the self-referential definitions responsible for the paradoxes. The system was simplified over time. The modern version starts with Church's *simply typed λ -calculus*, of 1940 [Chu40], which adds a type discipline to the λ -calculus, the calculus of functions that he himself had introduced. It is this line, and its subsequent refinements, that gives rise to the contemporary type theories; a classical and accessible introduction to all this development is that of Nederpelt and Geuvers [NG14].

The central concept is the *typing judgement* $a : A$, which reads “ a is a term of type A ”. It is worth insisting on its difference from set-theoretic membership. The proposition $a \in A$ can be true or false and is an object of proof; the judgement $a : A$, by contrast, is an intrinsic datum of a , fixed by its construction and checkable through syntactic analysis of the term. Put another way, in type theory we do not ask “is a of type A ?” as if it were a problem to be solved: the type of an object is determined and, at most, checking it reduces to executing an algorithm.

Together with the basic types, the theory has *constructors*, which produce new types from others. We now describe the most common ones.

The most elementary one is the *function type* $A \rightarrow B$, whose terms are the functions from A to B . From it the two fundamental operations of the λ -calculus are derived. The first is *abstraction*: given an expression b that depends on a variable $x : A$, abstraction produces the term $\lambda x.b$ of type $A \rightarrow B$, that is, the function that sends each x to the value b . The second is *application*: given $f : A \rightarrow B$ and $a : A$, application produces the term $f a : B$, the result of evaluating f at a . Abstraction and application are, at bottom, the principles of the notion of function: one constructs it and the other uses it.

From the function type, two other constantly used constructors arise. The *product type* $A \times B$ has as terms the ordered pairs (a, b) with $a : A$ and $b : B$, and captures the idea of having a datum of each type at the same time. The *sum type* $A + B$, in turn, has as terms the injections of an element of A or of an element of B , and captures the idea of having a datum of one of the two types, knowing which of them it comes from. To these are added two extreme types that should be kept in mind: the *empty type*, which has no terms, and the *unit type*, which has only one.

With these ingredients, the basic types and some constructors, one can already represent a good part of the usual structure of mathematics, without resorting to sets as a base. In fact, type

theory can be taken as a foundational alternative to the set-theoretic framework that we assumed in Chapter 2. This is important, since the formalization in Lean that we will develop in Chapter 7 rests on type theory, not on set theory.

§ 6.3

The Curry-Howard isomorphism

The *Curry-Howard isomorphism*, also known as the *propositions as types* correspondence, is the central connection between logic and type theory and is the central idea on which the functioning of a proof assistant is based. The starting idea is to identify propositions with types: each proposition is read as a type and, under this reading, having a proof of the proposition is equivalent to having a term of the type that represents it. Proving thus becomes constructing a term.

Let us see it first with implication, which is the most illustrative case. In logic, proving that A implies B consists in giving a procedure that, from a proof of A , produces a proof of B . But this is just what a function does: a function from the type that represents A to the type that represents B sends each term of A to a term of B , that is, each proof of A to a proof of B . This is why the implication $A \Rightarrow B$ corresponds to the function type $A \rightarrow B$. Proving the implication is then nothing more than finding one of these functions, that is, exhibiting a term of type $A \rightarrow B$.

The same intuition applies to the rest of the connectives:

- The conjunction $A \wedge B$ corresponds to the *product type* $A \times B$. Proving $A \wedge B$ is proving A and proving B at the same time, that is, providing a proof of each; and a term of $A \times B$ is precisely a pair (a, b) with $a : A$ and $b : B$.
- The disjunction $A \vee B$ corresponds to the *sum type* $A + B$. Proving $A \vee B$ is proving one of the two, knowing which; and a term of $A + B$ is the injection of a term of A or of a term of B , which keeps the information of which of the two sides it comes from.
- The falsity \perp corresponds to the *empty type*, the type with no terms: a proposition that admits no proof at all.
- The truth \top corresponds to the *unit type*, the type with a single term: a proposition that is proved trivially, without contributing any information.

An especially illustrative case is that of negation. If we define $\neg A$ as $A \Rightarrow \perp$, a proof of $\neg A$ is a function that transforms any proof of A into a proof of falsity; in other words, a witness that A cannot be proved, since if we could do so we would obtain a term of the empty type. It is worth noting, moreover, that this reading fits with intuitionistic logic: a proof is always an explicit construction, as the case of disjunction makes clear, where it does not suffice to know that one of the two sides holds, but one must say which.

We collect this correspondence in Table 6.3.1.

The practical consequence is clear. If proving a proposition is constructing a term of its type, verifying a proof reduces to checking that the proposed term does indeed have that type: *type-checking*, a mechanical and decidable task. Proving and programming become, under this reading, the same activity, and a single theory serves at once as a logic and as a programming language. It is precisely this that allows the kernel of a proof assistant to verify proofs simply by checking types.

LOGIC	TYPE THEORY
implication $A \Rightarrow B$	function type $A \rightarrow B$
conjunction $A \wedge B$	product type $A \times B$
disjunction $A \vee B$	sum type $A + B$
falsity \perp	empty type
truth \top	unit type

TABLE 6.3.1. The Curry-Howard dictionary between the connectives of intuitionistic propositional logic and the constructors of type theory.

The correspondence was independently observed by Curry, in his work of the fifties on combinatory logic, and by Howard, in a 1969 manuscript that circulated informally for years and was not published until 1980 [How80]. A modern exposition, focused precisely on these intuitions, is that of Wadler [Wad15]; for an in-depth treatment one can consult [SU06].

§ 6.4

Dependent type theory

The simple types that we have handled so far turn out to be insufficient to express the usual mathematical constructions. The reason is that, in mathematics, it is frequent that the type of an object depends not only on other types but on concrete *values*. The paradigmatic example is that of vectors of fixed length: for each natural number n , the set \mathbb{R}^n of vectors of length n depends on the value n , not only on the type \mathbb{R} of its components. Another familiar example are predicates over a type A : a property P on the elements of A is an assignment that sends each $a : A$ to a proposition $P(a)$. *Dependent type theory* generalizes type theory to accommodate this kind of dependencies.

The generalization is realized in two new constructors. Given a family of types $B(x)$ indexed by $x : A$, the *dependent product type* $\prod_{x:A} B(x)$ has as terms the functions f that assign to each $x : A$ a term $f(x) : B(x)$. When $B(x)$ does not depend on x , this type reduces to the ordinary function type $A \rightarrow B$. Dually, the *dependent sum type* $\sum_{x:A} B(x)$ has as terms the pairs (a, b) with $a : A$ and $b : B(a)$, and generalizes the Cartesian product $A \times B$ of the simple case.

Under the Curry-Howard isomorphism, these two constructors have a direct logical reading. The type $\prod_{x:A} B(x)$ corresponds to universal quantification $\forall x : A, B(x)$: a proof of “for all x in A , $B(x)$ holds” is a function that sends each $x : A$ to a proof of $B(x)$. Analogously, the type $\sum_{x:A} B(x)$ corresponds to existential quantification $\exists x : A, B(x)$: a proof of “there exists x in A such that $B(x)$ ” consists in exhibiting a witness $a : A$ together with a proof of $B(a)$.

Dependent type theory is, therefore, the necessary step that allows one to fully capture first-order logic through the Curry-Howard isomorphism.

A delicate point when describing a system of this kind is that of *universes*. If we wanted to speak of the “type of all types” we would face the typed equivalent of Russell’s paradox. The usual

solution is the same one that we have already seen in Chapter 2 in its set-theoretic version through Grothendieck universes: stratifying the universe in a hierarchy

$$\text{Type } 0 : \text{Type } 1 : \text{Type } 2 : \dots,$$

in such a way that Type 0 is a term of Type 1, the latter of Type 2, and so on. A type like \mathbb{N} lives in Type 0, a type of types like $\text{Type } 0 \rightarrow \text{Type } 0$ lives in Type 1, and so on. To avoid the duplication of definitions throughout the hierarchy, modern systems incorporate *universe polymorphism*: the possibility of defining an object at a generic level u from which any concrete instance is obtained by specializing u .

The most influential dependent type system, and the canonical reference on the subject, is Martin-Löf's *intuitionistic type theory* [Mar84], developed from the 1970s onwards. A modern perspective on these ideas, with additional emphasis on the notion of equality, can be found in another of the foundational texts, *Homotopy Type Theory* [The13].

In the context of proof assistants, the most widespread variant is the *Calculus of Inductive Constructions* (CIC), introduced by Coquand and Huet and subsequently extended with inductive types. CIC distinguishes a predicative hierarchy of universes $\text{Type } u$ and a special universe Prop , impredicative and with proof irrelevance, reserved for propositions. This organization is the one adopted by Lean, on a variant of its own of CIC whose exact details can be consulted in [Car19].

Before moving on to the concrete system, it is worth flagging a point to which we will return. In dependent type theories, the notion of equality has nuances different from those in the case of simple types. There coexist, in particular, two distinct notions of equality: the *definitional* one, which the system recognizes automatically through computation, and the *propositional* one, which is proved like any other proposition. To these is added an additional notion, *heterogeneous equality*, for comparing terms of a priori distinct types. We mention its existence here only to anticipate that it is the origin of the technical obstacles that we already warned of at the close of Chapter 5; the details will be discussed alongside the code in Chapter 7.

§ 6.5

Lean 4

With dependent type theory now in place, we are in a position to present the concrete system on which the formalization of Chapter 7 will rest. It is worth specifying from the outset what we understand by *Lean*, since the name simultaneously designates two things. On the one hand, Lean is a functional programming language with a dependent type system; on the other, it is a proof assistant. This dual nature is no accident: it is, precisely, the materialization of the Curry-Howard isomorphism that we have just discussed, according to which programming and proving are, at bottom, one and the same activity.

The system was conceived by Leonardo de Moura at Microsoft Research starting in 2013. The first versions (Lean 1, 2 and 3) gradually refined the language and the ecosystem, and on them much of the community's formalization effort was developed for years. Lean 4 [MU21], presented in 2021 and with its first stable release in 2023, is a complete rewrite of the system with a smaller

kernel, self-hosting and new facilities for metaprogramming. In this work we will refer to Lean 4 simply as *Lean*, except when the distinction matters.

The architecture of Lean fits the general description that we gave when speaking of proof assistants. At its base operates the *kernel*, deliberately small, whose sole responsibility is type-checking. Above it, the *elaborator* is in charge of translating the friendly syntax that the user writes into the language of the kernel, resolving implicit arguments, instantiating classes and filling in the gaps of the term. The *tactics*, which we will see later, are nothing more than metaprograms that the elaborator runs to construct terms that the kernel finally verifies.

In what follows, we broadly follow the presentation of *Theorem Proving in Lean 4* [Avi+24], which is the standard reference for approaching Lean as a proof assistant. We limit ourselves, however, to what is necessary to follow the formalization of Chapter 7: this section does not aim to be a detailed guide on Lean. For a deeper exposition on the topic, the canonical references are [Avi+24], together with the language reference manual [The24]. The purely programmatic aspect is covered in *Functional Programming in Lean* [Chr23].

6.5.1 Types and terms

We take the first steps in Lean by situating, on its concrete syntax, the notions that we introduced in the previous sections.

The first command worth knowing is `#check`. Applied to any expression, it returns the type that the system assigns to it. The response of the command is, precisely, a typing judgement of the form $a : A$, which was the central notion of type theory, written here in Lean syntax.

```
TUTORIAL.LEAN
3 #check 0 -- Nat
4 #check true -- Bool
5 #check "hello" -- String
```

In the response to `#check Nat` one can also appreciate the role of universes. Each type lives, in turn, in another type, called a *universe*, and the universes form the hierarchy indexed by natural numbers that we already described in the previous section. Lean writes `Type` as an abbreviation for `Type 0`, the first level of the hierarchy. One level above is `Type 1`, where `Type` itself lives, and so on.

```
TUTORIAL.LEAN
7 #check Nat -- Type
8 #check Type -- Type 1
9 #check Type 1 -- Type 2
```

To introduce and manipulate terms, Lean has three keywords that are worth having from the start. The keyword `def` introduces a named definition. On the other hand, `example` allows one to state a term without naming it, which is convenient for illustrations that are not going to be reused. Finally, `#eval` reduces a term to a concrete value when this makes sense, as in the case of a natural number built from arithmetic operations.

```
TUTORIAL.LEAN
11 def double (n : Nat) : Nat := n + n
```

```

12
13 #eval double 21 -- 42
14
15 example : Nat := double 5

```

We note that both `#check` and `#eval` return a result in what we call the *infoview*, a panel that displays contextual information about the state of the code. This panel will be of special interest in the tactic mode that we introduce later on.

As for compound types, the *function types* are written with the arrow $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$, exactly as in mathematical notation. A function is constructed by abstraction with `fun x => b` (or, in more mathematical contexts, with `fun x ↦ b`) and is applied by juxtaposition. We consider the polymorphic identity as an example:

```

TUTORIAL.LEAN
17 def id' {α : Type u} (a : α) : α := a
18
19 #check @id' -- {α : Type u} → α → α

```

It is worth commenting on two new elements. In the first place, the braces in `{α : Type u}` mark α as an *implicit* argument, so that the system infers it automatically from the context at each application, and the sign `@` prepended to the name in `#check @id'` forces the system to also display the implicit arguments in its response. In the second place, the parameter `u` that appears in `Type u` is a *universe level*. Thanks to it, a single definition serves for types at any level of the hierarchy without the need to duplicate it. This is what is called *universe polymorphism* and what we were already referring to in the context of dependent type theory.

The product and sum types are obtained through their own constructors. The product $A \times B$ is written $\alpha \times \beta$ (internal name `Prod`), with pairs given by `(a, b)` and projections `.1` and `.2`. The sum $A + B$ is written $\alpha \oplus \beta$ (internal name `Sum`), with injections `Sum.inl` and `Sum.inr`. The extreme types, in turn, also have their counterpart in Lean: `Unit` for the unit type and `Empty` for the empty type.

```

TUTORIAL.LEAN
21 def pair : Nat × Bool := (3, true)
22
23 #check pair.1 -- Nat
24 #check pair.2 -- Bool
25
26 def inLeft : Nat ⊕ Bool := Sum.inl 7
27 def inRight : Nat ⊕ Bool := Sum.inr false

```

A final observation before moving on to propositions. Almost all the types that we have just presented (`Nat`, `Bool`, the product, the sum) are not primitive in the system, but instances of one and the same general scheme: that of *inductive types*, which we will address later on. The set of genuinely primitive constructors of the language is notably small, which contributes to the kernel being a small and auditable piece, in line with the de Bruijn criterion that we mentioned at the beginning of the chapter.

6.5.2 Propositions and proofs

Let us now see in Lean the reading of propositions as types. The idea, already described in connection with the Curry-Howard isomorphism, was to read each proposition as a type and each proof as a term of the corresponding type.

Lean reserves a distinguished universe, called `Prop`, to host propositions. A proposition is, formally, a term of type `Prop`. Proving it is equivalent to constructing a term of the corresponding type. There is no fundamental distinction between constructing a program and constructing a proof: in both cases what is offered is a term of the desired type.

This is clearly reflected in the keyword `theorem`. Syntactically, `theorem` is almost indistinguishable from `def`: both introduce a term of a given type. The difference lies in the fact that `theorem` requires the type to live in `Prop` and is reserved, by convention, for proofs. The system takes advantage of this mark to apply certain optimizations derived from *proof irrelevance*, proper to the `Prop` universe, according to which any two proofs of the same proposition are considered indistinguishable. As an illustration, the same statement can be introduced indistinctly with one keyword or the other:

```
TUTORIAL.LEAN
29 theorem id_theorem (A : Prop) : A → A := fun h => h
30
31 def id_definition (A : Prop) : A → A := fun h => h
```

Under this reading, proving an implication reduces to exhibiting a function. Given two propositions A and B , a proof of $A \rightarrow B$ is a function that transforms any proof of A into a proof of B . The projection onto the first argument, for instance, proves $A \rightarrow B \rightarrow A$:

```
TUTORIAL.LEAN
33 theorem const (A B : Prop) : A → B → A := fun a _ => a
```

For the remaining connectives it suffices to go through the dictionary of Table 6.3.1. The conjunction $A \wedge B$ is introduced through the constructor `And.intro` or, typically, through the anonymous constructor `<_, _>`, using the projections `.left` and `.right`. The commutativity of conjunction is then proved as one would expect, destructuring an argument and reconstructing it in the opposite order:

```
TUTORIAL.LEAN
35 theorem and_swap (A B : Prop) : A ∧ B → B ∧ A :=
36   fun h => <h.right, h.left>
```

The disjunction $A \vee B$, in turn, is introduced with the injections `Or.inl` and `Or.inr` and is eliminated, in term mode, through the method `.elim`, which receives a function for each case:

```
TUTORIAL.LEAN
38 theorem or_swap (A B : Prop) : A ∨ B → B ∨ A :=
39   fun h => h.elim Or.inr Or.inl
```

Truth and falsity receive the names `True` and `False`. The first is introduced with `True.intro`. The second has no constructors, which is coherent with the usual reading: there is no proof whatsoever of falsity. From here the *ex falso quodlibet* principle follows immediately, which in Lean is obtained by elimination with `False.elim`. Negation is defined as $\neg A := A \rightarrow \text{False}$, so that a proof of $\neg A$ is nothing more than a function that sends any hypothetical proof of A to a proof of falsity. The immediate application is *modus ponens* between A and $\neg A$:

```
TUTORIAL.LEAN
41 theorem absurd' (A : Prop) (h : A) (hn : ¬ A) : False := hn h
```

To close the tour through the Curry-Howard reading, it is interesting to observe how Lean treats quantifiers. Universal quantification $\forall x : \alpha, P x$ literally simplifies to the dependent function type $(x : \alpha) \rightarrow P x$. Consequently, a proof of a universal statement is nothing other than a dependent function, introduced with the usual `fun`. Analogously, existential quantification $\exists x : \alpha, P x$ is constructed with a dependent pair, written with the anonymous constructor `<a, h>`, in which a is the witness and h is a proof of $P a$:

```
TUTORIAL.LEAN
43 theorem forall_apply {α : Type u} (P : α → Prop)
44   (h : ∀ x, P x) (a : α) : P a :=
45   h a
46
47 theorem exists_intro {α : Type u} (P : α → Prop)
48   (a : α) (h : P a) : ∃ x, P x :=
49   <a, h>
```

It should be noted that, as soon as proofs grow a little, writing them by hand in this way becomes impractical: the tree of applications and destructurings ends up very far from the natural way of reasoning about the statement. This motivates the move to tactic mode, which we treat next.

6.5.3 Tactic mode

Every proof is, in the last instance, a term of the kernel. But, in practice, proofs are not written directly as terms. They are constructed in an interactive way, letting the system keep track, at each step, of which hypotheses are available and what remains to be proved. This way of working is what gives the name to the category of *interactive theorem provers*.

The syntax is simple. The keyword `by` introduces a sequence of *tactics*, metaprograms that the elaborator runs to generate the term that, once completed, fills the gap. It is worth insisting that the final result, once processed by the elaborator, is no different, for the kernel, from a term written by hand: tactics are a convenient way of constructing terms.

The central piece of the interactive flow is the *infocview*, which we introduced earlier. At each position of the cursor within tactic mode, the *infocview* displays the *proof state*, that is, the context of available hypotheses and the goals pending to be proved. It is through the *infocview* that we know at every moment what is left to do and what tools are at our disposal. In the listings of this section and of Chapter 7 we reproduce, below each proof, the relevant states of the *infocview* that appear highlighted in yellow in the code.

As an illustration, let us rewrite in tactic mode the commutativity of conjunction:

TUTORIAL.LEAN

```
51 theorem and_swap_tac (A B : Prop) : A ∧ B → B ∧ A := by
52   intro h
53   exact ⟨h.right, h.left⟩
```

LEAN INFOVIEW · Line 51

1 goal

A : Prop

B : Prop

⊢ A ∧ B → B ∧ A

LEAN INFOVIEW · Line 52

1 goal

A : Prop

B : Prop

h : A ∧ B

⊢ B ∧ A

LEAN INFOVIEW · Line 53

no goals

In the first state of the *infview*, the system indicates that we have the propositions A and B as free variables and that the goal is $A \wedge B \rightarrow B \wedge A$. The tactic `intro h` discharges the implication: it passes the hypothesis $h : A \wedge B$ to the context and leaves $B \wedge A$ as the new goal. The second state reflects this change. Finally, `exact ⟨h.right, h.left⟩` closes the goal by providing the explicit term that we already knew from before.

The previous block uses only two tactics. We describe, in what follows, other basic tactics that appear frequently in any formalization work:

- `intro` discharges an implication or a universal quantifier, passing the hypothesis (or the variable) to the context.
- `exact` closes the goal by providing a term of the required type.
- `apply` applies a lemma or a hypothesis backwards: if the goal is B and we have $f : A \rightarrow B$, then `apply f` leaves A as the new goal.
- `constructor` introduces the canonical constructor of the goal when this is unique. For a pair, it is equivalent to the anonymous constructor `⟨_, _⟩`.
- `rfl` closes an equality by definitional reflexivity, that is, when both sides reduce to the same term.
- `rw` rewrites in the goal (or in a hypothesis signalled with `at`) using an equality as a rewriting rule.

Let us see a second example, which illustrates backward chaining with `apply`. The transitivity of implication is naturally proved in this style:

TUTORIAL.LEAN

```
55 theorem imp_trans (A B C : Prop) (f : A → B) (g : B → C) : A → C := by
```

```

56  intro a
57  apply g
58  apply f
59  exact a

```

LEAN INFOVIEW · Line 55

```

1 goal

A : Prop
B : Prop
C : Prop
f : A → B
g : B → C
⊢ A → C

```

LEAN INFOVIEW · Line 57

```

1 goal

A : Prop
B : Prop
C : Prop
f : A → B
g : B → C
a : A
⊢ B

```

The initial state shows the goal $A \rightarrow C$ with the hypotheses $f : A \rightarrow B$ and $g : B \rightarrow C$ in the context. After introducing the implication with `intro a`, we apply the hypothesis `g` backwards with `apply g`, which leaves B as the new goal. The second state reflects this situation. Finally, we apply the hypothesis `f` backwards with `apply f`, which leaves us with the goal A , resolved with `exact a`.

We close this section with a tactic that follows a similar idea to that of `rw`. Instead of rewriting with a single given equality, the tactic `simp` *normalizes* the goal (or a hypothesis signalled with `at`) by iteratively applying a set of *simplification lemmas*, the equalities marked with the `@[simp]` attribute. If the normalization reduces the goal to a reflexive identity, the tactic closes it. Otherwise, it leaves a simpler goal on which to continue. The variants `simp [h1, ..., hn]` and `simp only [...]` allow, respectively, extending the active set with local lemmas and restricting the rewriting to an explicit list.

In the simplest case, a single invocation suffices to close the goal:

TUTORIAL.LEAN

```

61 example (n m : Nat) : n + 0 + (0 + m) = n + m := by
62   simp

```

LEAN INFOVIEW · Line 62

```
no goals
```

The occurrences of `+ 0` and of `0 +` disappear upon rewriting with `Nat.add_zero` and `Nat.zero_add`, equalities declared with `@[simp]` in Lean's core, and the resulting identity is closed by reflexivity.

When normalization is not enough, `simp` leaves a simpler goal on which to continue working:

```
TUTORIAL.LEAN
64 example (n m : Nat) (h : n = m) : n + 0 = m := by
65   simp
66   exact h
```

```
LEAN INFOVIEW · Line 65
1 goal

n : Nat
m : Nat
h : n = m
├ n = m
```

The tactic reduces the goal to $n = m$ without touching the hypothesis h , which we apply next with `exact h`.

Symmetrically, the variant `simp at h` applies the normalization to a hypothesis:

```
TUTORIAL.LEAN
68 example (n m : Nat) (h : n + 0 = m) : n = m := by
69   simp at h
70   exact h
```

```
LEAN INFOVIEW · Line 69
1 goal

n : Nat
m : Nat
h : n = m
├ n = m
```

The hypothesis $h : n + 0 = m$ becomes $h : n = m$ and closes the goal immediately.

This tactic is one of those we use most throughout the formalization and the base on which the automation tactics that we will see in Section 7.5 rest. In particular, the search performed by the `aesop` tactic uses precisely the lemmas declared with `@[simp]`.

6.5.4 Structures and inductive types

We close the tour through Lean with a basic mechanism for modelling mathematical structures, although not the only one nor the most widespread in Mathlib, for instance.

A *structure*, declared with `structure`, groups a collection of fields under the same name. The declaration simultaneously introduces a new type, a default constructor and an automatic projection for each field. A term of the structure can be constructed explicitly with its `.mk` constructor or, more commonly, with the anonymous constructor `<_, ..., _>`, where the order of the arguments follows the order of the fields in the declaration. Thus, one of the usual ways of giving a mathematical structure consists in giving different *data* fields accompanied by several *axiom* fields that state the required properties. A basic example is that of a monoid:

```
TUTORIAL.LEAN
72 structure Monoid' (α : Type u) where
73   mul : α → α → α
74   one : α
75   one_mul : ∀ a, mul one a = a
76   mul_one : ∀ a, mul a one = a
77   mul_assoc : ∀ a b c, mul (mul a b) c = mul a (mul b c)
```

Each term of type `Monoid' α` is, therefore, a structure with the operation, the unit and the three proofs of the axioms. The dot notation gives access to the fields: if `M : Monoid' α`, then `M.mul`, `M.one`, `M.one_mul`, and so on, denote the corresponding components.

Structures of this kind allow one to prove basic properties. As a compact illustration, we will prove the uniqueness of the left identity: if an element `e` acts as a left identity, then it coincides with the one of the structure:

```
TUTORIAL.LEAN
79 theorem Monoid'.one_unique {α : Type u} (M : Monoid' α)
80   (e : α) (he : ∀ a, M.mul e a = a) : e = M.one := by
81   have h : M.mul e M.one = M.one := he M.one
82   rw [M.mul_one] at h
83   exact h
```

```
LEAN INFOVIEW · Line 81
1 goal

α : Type u
M : Monoid' α
e : α
he : ∀ (a : α), M.mul e a = a
h : M.mul e M.one = M.one
⊢ e = M.one
```

```
LEAN INFOVIEW · Line 82
1 goal

α : Type u
M : Monoid' α
e : α
he : ∀ (a : α), M.mul e a = a
h : e = M.one
⊢ e = M.one
```

In the first state, we have introduced an auxiliary hypothesis `h` using the tactic `have`. As one can observe, we prove *in situ* in term mode the hypothesis that we want to introduce. Then, we use the axiom `M.mul_one` to rewrite the hypothesis that we have just introduced, so that this is exactly the goal that we want to close.

Beyond structures, Lean offers a general mechanism for defining types from their *constructors*: *inductive types*, introduced with the keyword `inductive`. A `structure` is, in fact, nothing more than the particular case of an inductive type with a single constructor, `.mk`. The declaration of an

inductive type enumerates the constructors together with their types, and from there the system automatically generates the principles of induction and recursion, as well as pattern matching on the constructors.

The canonical example is that of the natural numbers, which can be defined from the constructors `zero` and `succ`:

```
TUTORIAL.LEAN
85 inductive Nat' where
86   | zero : Nat'
87   | succ : Nat' → Nat'
```

In fact, the type `Nat` of the system that we have been using is defined in Lean's prelude with exactly this form, although with an internal representation optimized for large integers. Another paradigmatic example is that of lists, which are defined recursively by two constructors: the empty list and the insertion of an element at the front of a list. The length of a list is then naturally defined by pattern matching on the constructors:

```
TUTORIAL.LEAN
89 inductive List' (α : Type u) where
90   | nil : List' α
91   | cons : α → List' α → List' α
92
93 def List'.length {α : Type u} : List' α → Nat
94   | .nil ⇒ 0
95   | .cons _ xs ⇒ xs.length + 1
```

The conjunction `And`, the disjunction `Or`, the existential quantification `Exists`, equality itself `Eq`: all of them are inductive types in `Prop` with one or several constructors. An immediate consequence is that the associated proofs reduce, ultimately, to applying the appropriate constructor or destructuring an existing term, exactly as we were doing before.

§ 6.6

Mathlib

Lean, on its own, is the language and the proof assistant; mathematics is built on top of it. *Mathlib* is the library that fulfils this role: a single body of formalized and verified mathematics, developed collaboratively by the community of Lean users [Com20]. As opposed to the dispersion in independent developments that is usual in other environments, *Mathlib* aspires to be a unified and coherent library, in which each contribution integrates with the rest and reuses what already exists. It is an open-source project under constant evolution, without a single author, whose contributions go through a process of community review before being incorporated.

Its coverage is very broad and already encompasses a good part of undergraduate and graduate mathematics. Without being exhaustive, among the areas that are being formalized are:

- algebra, from the theory of groups, rings and fields to commutative and homological algebra;
- real and complex analysis, together with measure theory and functional analysis;

-
- topology, both general and algebraic;
 - number theory;
 - combinatorics and graph theory;
 - probability theory;
 - category theory.

Of all of them, the one that concerns us most, as we will discuss in Chapter 7, is category theory. Mathlib has a very extensive categorical library, although still growing, on which much of our formalization will rest.

It is worth pointing out, finally, that Mathlib is not limited to defining mathematics. Alongside the definitions and the theorems, it also provides numerous tactics and utilities (automation procedures, lemma search tools, instances and notations) that greatly facilitate the work of formalization and which we will make use of throughout Chapter 7.

CHAPTER SEVEN

7

The formalization in Lean

This chapter constitutes the core of the document and, in particular, the [formalization repository](#)¹⁶ is the main object of this work. In addition, the [project page](#)¹⁷ links to the web and PDF versions of the blueprint and to the website with the project’s API documentation. Both are tools that we will discuss at the end of this chapter.

The chapter does not aim to be a systematic tour through the codebase, but rather a thematic exposition of the various design decisions taken throughout the formalization, as well as of the Lean and Mathlib tools used along the way. We also discuss in more depth the technical obstacles that we have been warning about throughout the work. We refer once again to the repository for a detailed consultation of the code. Moreover, in Appendix A we document its structure, the auxiliary tools used, the development environment, and so on, with the aim of facilitating navigation through the code.

§ 7.1

Classes, instances and notation

Before entering into the specific decisions of the formalization, we introduce some Lean concepts that are somewhat more advanced than those introduced in the preliminaries. Lean offers several ways of modelling mathematical structures and the choice between one and another is important, since it conditions how definitions are written, how theorems are stated and how results are applied.

7.1.1 Classes

Let us first recall how we modelled a monoid in Chapter 6. We defined a `structure` that grouped together the operation, the unit and the corresponding axioms.

```
TUTORIAL.LEAN
72 structure Monoid' (α : Type u) where
73   mul : α → α → α
74   one : α
75   one_mul : ∀ a, mul one a = a
76   mul_one : ∀ a, mul a one = a
77   mul_assoc : ∀ a b c, mul (mul a b) c = mul a (mul b c)
```

A concrete monoid was, according to this definition, a term $M : \text{Monoid}' \alpha$ that was passed explicitly each time one wanted to use it. The operations were accessed with dot notation: $M.\text{mul}$, $M.\text{one}$, and so on.

This approach works and represents well the mathematical idea that a monoid is not just a set, but the “package” formed by that set and its operations. However, in practice, when we define a mathematical structure and, later on, endow a concrete set with that structure, we understand that the structure becomes a “property” of that set and not a piece of data that is passed explicitly each time.

¹⁶https://github.com/mariovagogmarzal/higher_category_theory

¹⁷https://mariovagogmarzal.github.io/higher_category_theory/

In Lean, this idea is materialized through *classes*. A class is declared with the keyword `class` and is, in essence, a `structure` registered in a table that the *elaborator* consults when it needs a term of that type. When the system encounters an argument marked as an *instance argument*, it looks in that table for a suitable instance and inserts it without the user having to name it. The difference between `class` and `structure` is not fundamental, since every class is, ultimately, a structure.

The word “class” carries connotations from object-oriented languages that are misleading here. A Lean *class* is not a class in the C++ or Python sense: there is no implementation inheritance, no mutable state, no dynamic dispatch, no objects exchanging messages. It is, simply, a structure with an associated inference mechanism, much closer to Haskell’s *type classes* than to any construct of object-oriented programming.

Let us now rewrite the example of Chapter 6 with this new tool. The declaration directly recalls that of Chapter 6: the five fields are the same and the only essential difference lies in the keyword `class` instead of `structure`. We accompany it with an `export`, which brings the names `mul` and `one` into direct scope, without the `Monoid.` prefix:

```
CLASSES.LEAN
3 class Monoid (α : Type u) where
4   mul : α → α → α
5   one : α
6   one_mul : ∀ a, mul one a = a
7   mul_one : ∀ a, mul a one = a
8   mul_assoc : ∀ a b c, mul (mul a b) c = mul a (mul b c)
9
10 export Monoid (mul one)
```

The change is appreciated in its usage. Let us compare how we stated a result about the monoid in Chapter 6 with the following version, in which we prove the same thing (uniqueness of the left identity) now on the class.

```
CLASSES.LEAN
12 theorem Monoid.one_unique {α : Type u} [Monoid α]
13   (e : α) (he : ∀ a, mul e a = a) : e = one := by
14   have h : mul e one = one := he one
15   rw [Monoid.mul_one] at h
16   exact h
```

```
LEAN INFOVIEW · Line 13
1 goal

α : Type u
inst : Monoid α
e : α
he : ∀ (a : α), mul e a = a
┆ e = one
```

Here appears the *bracket notation*, `[Monoid α]`, which marks the instance as an *instance argument*. Unlike explicit arguments in the style of `(M : Monoid' α)`, an instance argument is a way of telling

Lean “the type α is a monoid”. Thus, given terms of type α , Lean will automatically understand that operations like `mul` or the constant `one` refer to the operations of the monoid over the type in question, as illustrated in the previous code when writing `mul e one`, for instance.

7.1.2 Instantiation

We have spoken repeatedly of *instances* in the previous section. When we speak of an instance of a class, we refer to a term that is registered in the class’s table and that the elaborator can locate by inference. In practice, we can understand instantiation as specializing a class to a concrete type, as we will see next.

The keyword `instance` is what allows us to register an instance. Its syntax is similar to that of a definition, with the difference that it registers the resulting term in the table that the elaborator consults, as we mentioned. For example, we can declare the natural numbers as a multiplicative monoid, declaring their multiplication as the usual multiplication of the naturals and the unit as `1`. For the proofs of the axioms, we will cheat in this example and use the proofs that already exist in Lean’s core library for these properties.

```
CLASSES.LEAN
18 instance : Monoid Nat where
19   mul := Nat.mul
20   one := 1
21   one_mul := Nat.one_mul
22   mul_one := Nat.mul_one
23   mul_assoc := Nat.mul_assoc
```

From this moment on, the exported names become available for any term of type `Nat` without having to pass anything explicitly. The elaborator fills in the instance argument on its own.

```
CLASSES.LEAN
25 #eval mul 2 3 -- 6
26 #eval (one : Nat) -- 1
```

7.1.3 Notation

Using names like `mul` is functional but becomes verbose as soon as expressions grow. We prefer, whenever we can, symbols close to those of usual mathematical writing. Lean allows one to define new notation with as much flexibility as one defines functions, and throughout the chapter we will make frequent use of this to improve the readability and handling of the code.

The simplest case is the declaration of an infix operator. For our monoid we can introduce, for instance, a product `*` that is right-associative and of precedence `100`, which literally translates into a call to `mul`:

```
CLASSES.LEAN
28 infixr:100 "*" => mul
```

From here on, `2 * 3` types correctly and reduces to `6` under `#eval`. More importantly, the notation integrates automatically into visual records such as those of the *infview*:

```

CLASSES.LEAN
30 #eval 2 *' 3 -- 6
31
32 example (e : Nat) (he : ∀ a : Nat, e *' a = a) : e = one := by
33   apply Monoid.one_unique
34   exact he

```

LEAN INFOVIEW · Line 32

```

1 goal

e : Nat
he : ∀ (a : Nat), e*'a = a
├ e = one

```

7.1.4 Combination and extension of classes

In mathematics, a single object usually comes with several structures at once: an ordered group is a group and an order on the same set, a topological ring is a ring and a topological space, and so on. The translation to Lean is direct: it suffices to require as many instance arguments as structures one wants to assume, one per class.

Lean already provides, in its own core library, a minimal class for the *less than or equal* relation. It is called `LE` (from *less than or equal to*) and reduces, literally, to a binary relation on the type, with the usual notation \leq associated. Combining it with the `Monoid` from before we can capture, for instance, the notion of an *ordered monoid*: a monoid whose multiplication is compatible with the order on both sides, in the sense that $a \leq b$ implies $c \cdot a \leq c \cdot b$ and $a \cdot c \leq b \cdot c$ for every c . We split this into two predicates, one for left compatibility and one for right compatibility.

```

CLASSES.LEAN
36 def is_left_ordered_monoid (α : Type u) [Monoid α] [LE α] : Prop :=
37   ∀ a b c : α, a ≤ b → mul c a ≤ mul c b
38
39 def is_right_ordered_monoid (α : Type u) [Monoid α] [LE α] : Prop :=
40   ∀ a b c : α, a ≤ b → mul a c ≤ mul b c

```

The signatures of `is_left_ordered_monoid` and `is_right_ordered_monoid` are what matter. Each has two instance arguments, `[Monoid α]` and `[LE α]`, one per structure, and the body of each predicate mixes operations coming from each: the multiplication `mul` comes from `Monoid` and the relation \leq comes from `LE`.

To speak of `is_left_ordered_monoid Nat` or `is_right_ordered_monoid Nat` we do not need to do anything else. Lean's core library already registers `LE Nat` (with `Nat.le` as the relation) and we ourselves have registered `Monoid Nat` above. When the elaborator encounters each expression, it locates each instance separately and builds the corresponding predicate:

```

CLASSES.LEAN
42 #check is_left_ordered_monoid Nat -- is_left_ordered_monoid Nat : Prop
43 #check is_right_ordered_monoid Nat -- is_right_ordered_monoid Nat : Prop

```

There is a second pattern for combining classes that we will use extensively in the formalization. Instead of juxtaposing two instance arguments in each signature, we can *bundle* both structures (together with the axioms that relate them, if any) into a single new class that *extends* them, with the keyword `extends`. Returning to the example, we can promote the previous conditions to the two axioms of a class `OrderedMonoid` that extends `Monoid` and `LE`.

```
CLASSES.LEAN
45 class OrderedMonoid (α : Type u) extends Monoid α, LE α where
46   mul_le_mul_left : ∀ a b c : α, a ≤ b → mul c a ≤ mul c b
47   mul_le_mul_right : ∀ a b c : α, a ≤ b → mul a c ≤ mul b c
```

An instance of `OrderedMonoid α` is, by construction, an instance of `Monoid α` and an instance of `LE α`, plus the proofs of the two compatibility axioms. Conversely, as soon as the system has a `[OrderedMonoid α]`, the operations of the monoid and the order relation become available by inference, exactly as would happen with two separate instance arguments.

Juxtaposition and extension are not mutually exclusive alternatives but responses to different questions: the first combines structures that live over *distinct objects*, the second combines structures that live over *the same object*. In the presentation that follows the two will appear hand in hand: a `Category Index C` will combine a `[Preorder Index]` on the index type (juxtaposition) with its own hierarchy of classes that extends over `C` (extension).

§ 7.2

Single-sorted categories and functors

With the vocabulary of the previous section fixed, we tackle the first of the two presentations we are going to formalize. The mathematical definitions are developed in Chapter 3. Here we deal with how they are modelled in Lean and what design decisions we have taken at each step.

7.2.1 Single-sorted categories as classes

Definition 3.1.3 fixes a single-sorted category by its data (a type C , two maps $sc, tg : C \rightarrow C$ and a partial composition $\#$) and its four axioms (S1)-(S4). In the formalization, we split this description into several layers. First, we will define a class that contains only the data. Then, we define a class that extends the previous one and formulates the axioms that speak of each dimension separately. Finally, we extend the previous one and formulate the axioms that involve two dimensions at once.

Another important difference worth noting is that we will not define the one-dimensional and two-dimensional versions as concrete cases, as we did in Chapter 3, but rather we will define from the start a structure indexed by an arbitrary set of indices endowed with a preorder.

We now expose the reason for this decision. Suppose we have a class or structure that models the notion of one-dimensional single-sorted category. To define the multidimensional version, we would have to, given a type and a family of operations on it, assert that each dimension of operations together with the underlying type is of the type of the one-dimensional category. However, as we mentioned in Section 6.5, *being* of a type is not a proposition in type theory, it is a deterministic judgement on a concrete term.

An alternative to follow an approach more similar to that of Chapter 3 would be to use an approach similar to the one we take in Section 7.4, using “bundled types”. However, this adds unnecessary complexity and makes the code less readable. For all these reasons, we choose the representation mentioned.

The most basic layer is `CategoryStruct`, a class that groups the source operation, the target one and the partial composition together with a single technical axiom, `pcomp_dom`, that links the domain of definition with the composability condition:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/CATEGORY.LEAN
67 class CategoryStruct (Index : Type) (C : Type u) where
68   /-- Source operation at dimension `k`. -/
69   sc : Index → C → C
70   /-- Target operation at dimension `k`. -/
71   tg : Index → C → C
72   /-- Partial composition operation at dimension `k`. -/
73   pcomp : Index → C → C →. C
74   /-- The composition of `g` and `f` at dimension `k` is defined if and only if
75     the source of `g` at
76     dimension `k` equals the target of `f` at dimension `k`. -/
77   pcomp_dom : ∀ {k : Index} {f g : C}, (pcomp k g f).Dom ↔ sc k g = tg k f := by
78     hcat_disch
```

The partial composition is another of the important design points. Definition 3.1.3 fixes it exactly on the composable pairs, that is, the pairs (g, f) with $sc(g) = tg(f)$. Lean, by contrast, demands that every function be total. To reconcile both things we use the type `Part C` of `Mathlib` (through the abbreviation `PFun` for *partial functions*), a wrapper that encodes “a value of C together with a proof that it is defined”. The partial composition then returns a term of `Part C`, and the axiom `pcomp_dom` characterizes the domain: the composition of g and f is defined if, and only if, $sc(g) = tg(f)$. In this way, we recover the mathematical sense of partial function in Lean.

To write the partial composition concisely, we introduce a dedicated notation: given two morphisms g and f and a dimension k , we write $g \#.[k] f$ (with a dot) for `CategoryStruct.pcomp k g f`, which returns a term of type `Part C`.

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/CATEGORY.LEAN
84 @[inherit_doc]
85 scoped[HigherCategoryTheory.SingleSorted] notation g " #.[k] " f : 100 =>
86   CategoryStruct.pcomp k g f
```

Alongside it, we introduce an auxiliary definition `comp` for the total composition: given a composability proof `sc_tg_gf`, it extracts the value from the partial result and returns a term of type `C`. We give it its own notation $g \#[k] f \leftarrow sc_tg_gf$ (without dot).

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/CATEGORY.LEAN
103 /-- The (total) composition operation at dimension `k`, defined for composable
104     morphisms. Given
105     morphisms `f` and `g` with a proof of `sc_is_tg k g f`, this returns their
106     composite `g #[k] f`. -/
107 @[simp high]
```

```

106 def comp (k : Index) (g f : C) (sc_tg_gf : sc_is_tg k g f) : C :=
107   (g #.[k] f).get (dom_of_sc_is_tg sc_tg_gf)
108
109 @[inherit_doc]
110 scoped[HigherCategoryTheory.SingleSorted] notation g " #[" k "]" " f " ← "
111   sc_tg_gf:100 =>
112   CategoryStruct.comp k g f sc_tg_gf

```

In the `CategoryStruct` fragment, the `pcomp_dom` field already shows the default value `:= by hcat_disch`: the tactic `hcat_disch` is the project’s automatic discharge tool and is in charge of systematically closing these axioms in routine cases. We will come back to it in Section 7.5.

On top of `CategoryStruct` a second layer is built, `PreCategory`, which adds the axioms (S1)-(S4): idempotence of source and target, their interactions with composition, the identity laws and associativity. Each of them works with a single dimension, so this layer suffices to speak of a one-dimensional single-sorted category layer by layer:

```

HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/CATEGORY.LEAN
173 class PreCategory (Index : Type) (C : Type u)
174   extends CategoryStruct Index C where
175   /-- Applying source twice at dimension 'k' is idempotent. -/
176   sck_sck_eq_sck : ∀ (k : Index) (f : C), sc k (sc k f) = sc k f := by
177     hcat_disch
178   /-- The target of a source is itself. -/
179   tgg_sck_eq_sck : ∀ (k : Index) (f : C), tg k (sc k f) = sc k f := by
180     hcat_disch
181   /-- The source of a target is itself. -/
182   sck_tgg_eq_tgg : ∀ (k : Index) (f : C), sc k (tg k f) = tg k f := by
183     hcat_disch
184   /-- Applying target twice at dimension 'k' is idempotent. -/
185   tgg_tgg_eq_tgg : ∀ (k : Index) (f : C), tg k (tg k f) = tg k f := by
186     hcat_disch

```

The fragment shows the header of the class and the four equations of the idempotence axiom. Axioms (S2) (source and target of a composition), (S3) (identity laws) and (S4) (associativity) follow a similar syntactic pattern.

Alongside the “main” axioms, the class contains several fields marked as `protected` that serve as *auxiliary methods* for some axioms. Before stating associativity, for example, we need to know that the two triple compositions can be composed:

```

HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/CATEGORY.LEAN
199 /-- If 'g' and 'f' compose and 'h' and 'g' compose, then 'h #[k] g' and 'f'
200   compose. This is an
201   auxiliary method for the associativity axiom. -/
202   protected compl_assoc {k : Index} {f g h : C}
203     (sc_tg_gf : sc_is_tg k g f) (sc_tg_hg : sc_is_tg k h g) :
204     sc_is_tg k (h #[k] g ← sc_tg_hg) f := calc
205     _ = sc k g := sck_compk_eq_sck sc_tg_hg

```

```
206   _ = tg k f := sc_tg_gf
```

These composabilities are a formal consequence of the previous axioms: they are always true and we know in advance their proof. That is why they appear as fields of the class with a complete and always valid proof value (an explicit `calc` block), not as one more field with `:= by hcat_disch`. When an instance is provided, a proof for them does not need to be supplied each time.

We show the example of use in the associativity axiom:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/CATEGORY.LEAN
215   /-- The associative property: if 'g' and 'f' compose and 'h' and 'g'
216   /-- compose, then the two
217   /-- ways of composing 'h', 'g', and 'f' exist and are equal. -/
217   assoc : ∀ {k : Index} {f g h : C} (sc_tg_gf : sc_is_tg k g f) (sc_tg_hg :
218   sc_is_tg k h g),
218       ((h #[k] g ← sc_tg_hg) #[k] f ← (compl_assoc sc_tg_gf sc_tg_hg)) =
219       (h #[k] (g #[k] f ← sc_tg_gf) ← (compr_assoc sc_tg_gf sc_tg_hg)) := by
220   hcat_disch
```

The third and final layer, `Category`, extends `PreCategory` with the axioms that in Chapter 3 we called (SB1)-(SB3) and that already speak of pairs $j < k$ of dimensions:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/CATEGORY.LEAN
238   class Category (Index : Type) [Preorder Index] (C : Type u)
239   extends PreCategory Index C where
240   /-- Applying source at dimension 'k' to a source at a lower dimension 'j < k'
241   /-- yields the source
242   /-- at dimension 'j'. -/
242   sck_scj_eq_scj : ∀ {k j : Index} (f : C) (_ : j < k), sc k (sc j f) = sc j
243   f := by hcat_disch
243   /-- Applying source at dimension 'j' to a source at a higher dimension 'k > j'
244   /-- yields the source
245   /-- at dimension 'j'. -/
245   scj_sck_eq_scj : ∀ {k j : Index} (f : C) (_ : j < k), sc j (sc k f) = sc j
246   f := by hcat_disch
```

Unlike the two previous layers, `Category` brings an additional hypothesis on the index type, `[Preorder Index]`. The reason is clear: it needs to have the relation $j < k$ between dimensions available in order to state the interaction. Since the ordinal n , the type `Fin n`, and the ordinal ω have a preorder defined by `Mathlib`, we can use this class to define both finite-dimensional and infinite-dimensional categories without having to specialize the index type, as we will see later on.

We take this opportunity to define here the concept of cell, which we have already seen to be fundamental in the development of this presentation.

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/CATEGORY.LEAN
359   variable {Index : Type} [Preorder Index] {C : Type u} [Category Index C]
360
361   /-- A morphism 'f' is a cell if 'sc k f = f'. -/
362   @[simp]
```

```

363 def cell (k : Index) (f : C) : Prop :=
364   sc k f = f
365
366 /-- The set of all  $k$ -cells in a single-sorted category. -/
367 @[simp]
368 def cells (k : Index) (C : Type u) [Category Index C] : Set C :=
369   {f : C | cell k f}

```

The properties and equivalences for this definition are laid out in a separate module:

```

HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/CELLS.LEAN
28 variable {Index : Type} [Preorder Index] {C : Type u} [S : Category Index C]
29
30 /-- A morphism 'f' is a  $k$ -cell (via source) if 'sc k f = f'. This is an
31 abbreviation for 'cell k
32 f', the original definition of  $k$ -cells found in 'Category.lean'. -/
32 abbrev cell_sc (k : Index) (f : C) := cell k f
33
34 /-- A morphism 'f' is a  $k$ -cell (via target) if 'tg k f = f'. -/
35 @[simp]
36 def cell_tg (k : Index) (f : C) : Prop :=
37   tg k f = f
38
39 /--
40 The source-based and target-based definitions of  $k$ -cells are equivalent.
41
42 A morphism 'f' satisfies 'sc k f = f' if and only if it satisfies 'tg k f = f'.
43 This equivalence
44 relies on the idempotency axioms 'tgk_sck_eq_sck' and 'sck_tgk_eq_tgk'.
45 -/
45 theorem cell_sc_iff_cell_tg (k : Index) (f : C) :
46   cell_sc k f ↔ cell_tg k f := by
47   apply Iff.intro
48   · intro sc_eq
49     calc
50     tg k f
51     _ = tg k (sc k f) := by rw [sc_eq]
52     _ = sc k f := S.tgk_sck_eq_sck k f
53     _ = f := sc_eq
54   · intro tg_eq
55     calc
56     sc k f
57     _ = sc k (tg k f) := by rw [tg_eq]
58     _ = tg k f := S.sck_tgk_eq_tgk k f
59     _ = f := tg_eq

```

The set `cells k C` has type `Set C`. In various points of the chapter we will also handle it as a *subtype*, in order to carry along explicitly the proof of membership when necessary.

7.2.2 The finite-dimensional case

The hierarchy that goes from the single-sorted pre- n -category (Definition 3.1.7) to the single-sorted n -category (Definition 3.1.10), passing through the bicategory (Definition 3.1.9) as an intermediate case, materializes in Lean by taking an appropriate finite type as the index. The natural type is `Fin n`, coming from Lean's core library and with an extensive library of results in Mathlib: its terms are pairs formed by a natural number i and a proof of $i < n$. Since i is chosen between 0 and $n - 1$, the type has exactly n elements and is the literal translation to Lean of the ordinal n that in Chapter 3 we used as the set of indices. As we mentioned, the type `Fin n` has a natural strict preorder. Thus, we can use it directly as the index type in `Category Index C` to obtain the hierarchy of finite-dimensional categories.

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/CATEGORY.LEAN
345 abbrev NCategory (n : ℕ) (C : Type u) := Category (Fin n) C
```

An `NCategory n C` is, thus, a `Category` over `Fin n`. Here another Lean keyword has appeared: `abbrev`. It is a way of defining a new name for an already existing type, without introducing a new layer of abstraction. It is a technical resource that helps Lean automatically discover instances and properties about the new class.

When $n \geq 2$, the preorder admits pairs $j < k$ and the interdimensional axioms have content: Definition 3.1.9 appears exactly as the case $n = 2$. When $n = 1$, on the other hand, there are no pairs $j < k$ and the condition is satisfied vacuously. The function `PreCategory.lift` materializes precisely that observation: given a `PreCategory` over `Fin 1`, it automatically constructs the complete `NCategory 1` without us having to pass proofs for the interdimensional axioms.

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/CATEGORY.LEAN
355 def PreCategory.lift {C : Type u} [S : PreCategory (Fin 1) C] : NCategory 1 C :=
    {S with}
```

Our automation system is capable, in this case, of finding the contradictions automatically and closing the interdimensional axioms.

This example also introduces another utility: naming concrete instances. Although `[PreCategory (Fin 1) C]` is already enough to treat `C` as a pre-1-category, if we want to access the instance object itself, that is, the underlying Lean structure, we can use `[S : PreCategory (Fin 1) C]` to name it. This is also useful if we have several instances of the same class on the same types and we want to be able to address the fields of one and the other precisely.

7.2.3 The infinite-dimensional case

To move to Definition 3.1.11 it would suffice to substitute the index type: instead of `Fin n` we use `ℕ`. However, since this structure in the single-sorted case has an additional axiom, we cannot use an abbreviation again as with `NCategory`.

We model this class by making `OmegaCategory` a class that extends `Category ℕ C` with an additional axiom:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/CATEGORY.LEAN
377 class OmegaCategory (C : Type u) extends Category N C where
378   /-- Every morphism is a  $k$ -cell for some  $k : \mathbb{N}$ . -/
379   is_cell :  $\forall f : C, \exists k : \mathbb{N}, \text{cell } k f$ 
```

The field `is_cell` is the literal translation of (ω S1): for every morphism f there exists a k such that f is a k -cell.

7.2.4 Functors

Definition 3.2.1 specifies a single-sorted n -functor as a single map $F : C \rightarrow D$ that preserves source, target and composition at each dimension. The infinite-dimensional case (the ω -functors) is formally identical, substituting n by ω .

A design question arises again: do we use a structure or a class? The answer in this case is different from the previous; now we will use structures. A functor is *data* that is passed explicitly: there is no canonical functor between two categories that the elaborator should locate by inference, and often we will want to speak of several different functors between the same C and D . That is precisely the use case of a `structure` versus a `class`.

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/FUNCTOR.LEAN
45 structure Functor (Index : Type) [Preorder Index] (C : Type u1) [Category Index
   C]
46   (D : Type u2) [Category Index D] where
47   /-- The underlying function on morphisms. -/
48   map : C  $\rightarrow$  D
49   /-- The map preserves sources. -/
50   map_sc_eq_sc_map :  $\forall (k : \text{Index}) (f : C), \text{map } (\text{sc } k f) = \text{sc } k (\text{map } f) := \text{by}$ 
   hcat_disch
51   /-- The map preserves targets. -/
52   map_tg_eq_tg_map :  $\forall (k : \text{Index}) (f : C), \text{map } (\text{tg } k f) = \text{tg } k (\text{map } f) := \text{by}$ 
   hcat_disch
```

The field `map` is the underlying map; `map_sc_eq_sc_map` and `map_tg_eq_tg_map` are the axioms (SF1) of preservation of source and target. The preservation of composition is captured in an analogous field, `map_comp_eq_comp_map`, accompanied by an auxiliary field that proves that the image under `map` of a composable pair is again a composable pair.

Proposition 3.2.3 establishes that the identity map and the ordinary composition of maps fit into this structure. In the code we realize them as `Functor.id` and `Functor.comp`, with notations id_s and \circ respectively. These two facts are what will enable, in Section 7.4, the construction of the *category of single-sorted categories* itself.

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/FUNCTOR.LEAN
83   /-- Composition of functors. Given functors ' $F : C \rightarrow D$ ' and ' $G : D \rightarrow E$ ', their
   composite ' $G \circ F : C$ 
84    $\rightarrow E$ ' is defined by ' $(G \circ F) f = G (F f)$ '. This operation preserves all the
   required functor
85   properties. -/
86   @[simp]
```

```

87 def comp (G : Functor Index D E) (F : Functor Index C D) :
88   Functor Index C E where
89   map f := G (F f)
90   map_sc_eq_sc_map := by
91     intro k f
92     calc
93       G (F (sc k f))
94       _ = G (sc k (F f)) := by rw [F.map_sc_eq_sc_map k f]
95       _ = sc k (G (F f)) := G.map_sc_eq_sc_map k (F f)
96   map_tg_eq_tg_map := by
97     intro k f
98     calc
99       G (F (tg k f))
100      _ = G (tg k (F f)) := by rw [F.map_tg_eq_tg_map k f]
101      _ = tg k (G (F f)) := G.map_tg_eq_tg_map k (F f)
102   map_comp_eq_comp_map := by
103     intro k f g sc_tg_gf
104     calc
105       G (F (g #[k] f ← sc_tg_gf))
106       _ = G ((F g) #[k] (F f) ← F.comp_map sc_tg_gf) := by rw
[F.map_comp_eq_comp_map sc_tg_gf]
107       _ = (G (F g)) #[k] (G (F f)) ← G.comp_map (F.comp_map sc_tg_gf) :=
108         G.map_comp_eq_comp_map (F.comp_map sc_tg_gf)
109
110 @[inherit_doc] scoped[HigherCategoryTheory.SingleSorted] infixr:100 " ∘ " ⇒
111   Functor.comp
112
113 /-- The identity functor on a single-sorted category `C`. It maps each morphism
114 to itself and
115 trivially preserves all structure. -/
116 @[simp]
117 def id (C : Type u1) [Category Index C] : Functor Index C C where
118   map f := f
119
120 @[inherit_doc] scoped[HigherCategoryTheory.SingleSorted] notation "ids" ⇒
121   Functor.id

```

Finally, we note that, since both the finite-dimensional and infinite-dimensional versions have this time exactly the same axioms, we can define both as an abbreviation.

```

HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/FUNCTOR.LEAN
122 /-- A functor between single-sorted  $n$ -categories. -/
123 abbrev NFunctor (n : ℕ)
124   (C : Type u1) [NCategory n C]
125   (D : Type u2) [NCategory n D] :=
126   Functor (Fin n) C D
127
128 /-- A functor between single-sorted  $\omega$ -categories. -/
129 abbrev OmegaFunctor

```

```

130   (C : Type u1) [OmegaCategory C]
131   (D : Type u2) [OmegaCategory D] :=
132   Functor ℕ C D

```

§ 7.3

Many-sorted categories and functors

The second presentation, the many-sorted one, is developed in Chapter 4. The essential difference with the single-sorted one is structural: instead of a single type of morphisms, now there is an *indexed family of types*, one per dimension, and the operations, consequently, cease to act within a single set and start to relate distinct components of the family. The modelling decisions inherit, however, the same skeleton as in the single-sorted presentation: three chained layers (CategoryStruct, PreCategory, Category) declared as *classes* so that the operations become available by inference, with functors apart as *structure*.

We discuss next the two decisions that are specifically many-sorted: how the indexed family is modelled and how the inequalities of dimensions that now appear in each operation are transported. We close with the infinite-dimensional case and functors.

7.3.1 Indexed families of types

The family $(C_k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}+1}$ of Definition 4.1.1 materializes in Lean as a function from the index type to `Type u`, wrapped in an abbreviation so that the signatures stay readable:

```

HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/NOTATION.LEAN
32  /-- Abbreviation for 'Fin (n + 1)', used as the index type for $n$-categories in
    the many-sorted
33  presentation. -/
34  abbrev FinSucc (n : ℕ) := Fin (n + 1)
35
36  /-- A family of types indexed by a preordered type, used as the carrier for many-
    sorted categories.
37  -/
38  abbrev TypeFamily (Index : Type) := Index → Type u
39
40  /-- A family of types indexed by 'FinSucc n', used as the carrier for many-sorted
    $n$-categories. -/
41  abbrev NTypeFamily (n : ℕ) := TypeFamily.{u} (FinSucc n)
42
43  /-- A family of types indexed by 'ℕ', used as the carrier for many-sorted $
    \omega$-categories. -/
44  abbrev OmegaTypeFamily := TypeFamily.{u} ℕ

```

Three details deserve comment. The first, that the index type is parametrized just as in the single-sorted presentation: an `Index : Type` with a `[Preorder Index]` when needed. Specializing it to a finite type or to `ℕ` is, once again, a later specialization. The second, the choice of `FinSucc n := Fin (n + 1)` as the index of the finite-dimensional many-sorted n -categories: a many-sorted n -category involves $n + 1$ levels (the dimensions $0, 1, \dots, n$), not n , and the name `FinSucc` captures that shift

explicitly. The third, that `TypeFamily` is an abbrev and not a `def`: the system unfolds it automatically when needed, which saves type annotations in each signature.

7.3.2 Operations indexed by ordered pairs

The lowest layer, `CategoryStruct`, gathers the data: the source and target operations between levels, the *identity* that ascends from one level to the next and the partial composition, together with the same link `pcomp_dom` between the domain of definition and the composability condition:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/MANYSORTED/CATEGORY.LEAN
64 class CategoryStruct (Index : Type) [Preorder Index] (C : TypeFamily.{u} Index)
   where
65   /-- Source operation at dimensions `(k, j)`. Maps `k`-morphisms to `j`-
      morphisms. -/
66   sc : {k j : Index} → j < k → C k → C j
67   /-- Target operation at dimensions `(k, j)`. Maps `k`-morphisms to `j`-
      morphisms. -/
68   tg : {k j : Index} → j < k → C k → C j
69   /-- Identity operation at dimensions `(k, j)`. Lifts `j`-morphisms to `k`-
      morphisms. -/
70   idm : {k j : Index} → j < k → C j → C k
71   /-- Partial composition operation at dimensions `(k, j)`. -/
72   pcomp : {k j : Index} → j < k → C k → C k → C k
73   /-- The composition of `g` and `f` at dimensions `(k, j)` is defined if and
      only if the source of
74   `g` at `(k, j)` equals the target of `f` at `(k, j)`. -/
75   pcomp_dom : ∀ {k j : Index} {j_lt_k : j < k} {f g : C k},
76     (pcomp j_lt_k g f).Dom ↔ sc j_lt_k g = tg j_lt_k f := by
77     hcat_disch
```

The visual difference with the single-sorted version is immediate: each operation now carries two indices and an inequality as arguments, and the domain and codomain move between distinct components of the family (C_k and C_j). The identity `idm`, which goes up in dimension, is the new piece of data that in the single-sorted presentation did not appear: there the identity morphisms were identified with the cells and there was nothing to add as data.

On top of `CategoryStruct` are built, exactly as in the single-sorted presentation, the two following layers. The class `PreCategory` adds the axioms that act on pairs of dimensions. Their names in the code (`sckj_compkj_eq_sckj`, and so on) reflect the indices involved in the suffix. The class `Category`, in turn, adds the interdimensional axioms, which quantify over triples $i < j < k$ and, as happened in the single-sorted case, require `[Preorder Index]`. The automation `:= by hcat_disch` remains the default value of the axiom fields and the **protected** auxiliaries appear with their explicit `calc` whenever the following axiom needs them. The stratification is, therefore, the same, what changes being the typing of each operation.

A specific decision of this presentation, and one worth noting, is the convention on how the dimension inequalities are passed. In the previous fragment one observes the pattern: the indices k and j are declared as implicit `{k j : Index}`, but the inequality `j_lt_k : j < k` is an *explicit and named* argument, not implicit nor discharged by a tactic. The consequence is that each operation is invoked, in its typical form, as `sc j_lt_k f` or `g #[j_lt_k] f ← sc_tg_gf`: the indices are

inferred, but the proof of the inequality is supplied in full view. It is a deliberate choice in favour of readability, versus the alternative of making it implicit and discharging it afterwards with a tactic.

The previous decision has an obvious cost. As soon as an axiom combines two pairs (i, j) and (j, k) , the transitivity $i < k$ appears as data and the two available inequalities have to be composed. Doing it by full name, with `lt_trans i_lt_j j_lt_k`, saturates the signatures and the terms with applications of one and the same lemma reused everywhere. The project's solution is to introduce a specific notation for that composition:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/NOTATION.LEAN
46 /-- Notation for 'lt_trans', used to compose strict inequality proofs when
    passing index arguments
47 to source, target, or composition operations in the many-sorted presentation. In
    any other context,
48 prefer using 'lt_trans' directly. -/
49 scoped infixr:100 ">" => lt_trans
```

From here on, given `i_lt_j : i < j` and `j_lt_k : j < k`, it suffices to write `(i_lt_j > j_lt_k) : i < k` in each call to invoke the operation at the composed pair. It is the minimal syntactic sugar that can be expected for this presentation not to become intractable as soon as the interdimensional axioms enter the picture. The following axiom of `Category` illustrates the use:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/MANYSORTED/CATEGORY.LEAN
270 /-- Applying source at '(j, i)' to a source at '(k, j)' yields the source at
    '(k, i)'. -/
271 scji_sckj_eq_scki : ∀ {k j i : Index} (j_lt_k : j < k) (i_lt_j : i < j) (f : C
    k),
272     sc i_lt_j (sc j_lt_k f) = sc (i_lt_j > j_lt_k) f := by
273     hcat_disch
```

The head of the axiom quantifies over three indices and two inequalities `j_lt_k` and `i_lt_j`, and the conclusion mentions the source at the two intermediate dimensions and at the composed pair through `>`.

7.3.3 The infinite-dimensional case as an abbreviation

The step to the many-sorted ω -categories is, as in the single-sorted presentation, a change of index. But this time it is not necessary to add any extra axiom: each k -morphism lives by construction in its own `C k` and the dimension is guaranteed by the underlying family.

The consequence is direct: the many-sorted ω -category is not a new class, but an abbreviation:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/MANYSORTED/CATEGORY.LEAN
447 /-- A many-sorted  $\omega$ -category is a 'Category' with index type 'N',
    representing a category
448 with infinitely (countably) many dimensions. -/
449 abbrev OmegaCategory (C : OmegaTypeFamily.{u}) := Category N C
```

7.3.4 Functors as indexed families

The many-sorted functors are, just as in the single-sorted case, a `structure`. The difference is the expected one: now `map` is a *family* of maps, one per dimension, not just one:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/MANYSORTED/FUNCTOR.LEAN
43 structure Functor (Index : Type) [Preorder Index] (C : TypeFamily.{u1} Index)
   [Category Index C]
44   (D : TypeFamily.{u2} Index) [Category Index D] where
45   /-- The underlying family of functions on morphisms. -/
46   map : (k : Index) → C k → D k
47   /-- The map preserves sources at dimensions `(k, j)`. -/
48   map_sc_eq_sc_map : ∀ {k j : Index} (j_lt_k : j < k) (f : C k),
49     map j (sc j_lt_k f) = sc j_lt_k (map k f) := by
50     hcat_disch
51   /-- The map preserves targets at dimensions `(k, j)`. -/
52   map_tg_eq_tg_map : ∀ {k j : Index} (j_lt_k : j < k) (f : C k),
53     map j (tg j_lt_k f) = tg j_lt_k (map k f) := by
54     hcat_disch
```

The fragment covers the data and the two axioms (MF1) of preservation of source and target; the preservation of the identity (MF2) and that of composition (MF3) follow the same pattern, with an auxiliary field `protected comp_map` that proves that the image under `map` of a composable pair is again composable. As in single-sorted, an instance of `CoeFun` allows the functor to be applied by writing `F k f` instead of `F.map k f`, so that the notation resembles that of the document.

Definition 4.2.1 guarantees that the identity family and componentwise composition fit into this structure. The concrete realizations are, once again, `Functor.id` and `Functor.comp`, with notations id_m and \circ : the same symbols as in single-sorted except for the subscript that distinguishes the many-sorted identity id_m from the single-sorted one id_s . These two facts will be, once again, what will enable the construction of the *category of many-sorted categories* that we will see next.

§ 7.4

The categories of categories

At this point we have formalized the two presentations separately. In both, the n -categories and the n -functors organize themselves in turn into a category, just as with their infinite-dimensional versions. Seen from the side of the code, the construction is similar in both presentations: a `structure` that bundles the underlying type (or the family of types) with its category instance, and an instance of Mathlib's classical category class on that bundled object. We discuss next the most relevant details.

7.4.1 Categories in Mathlib

Mathlib's category class is also presented at different levels. The first, `Quiver`, defines the families of *hom-sets* between objects. It includes no operations or axioms.

```
1 class Quiver (V : Type u) where
```

```

2  /-- The type of edges/arrows/morphisms between a given source and target. -/
3  Hom : V → V → Type v

```

The second, `CategoryStruct`, extends the first with the composition operation and the identity morphisms:

```

1  class CategoryStruct (obj : Type u) : Type max u (v + 1) extends Quiver.{v} obj
   where
2  /-- The identity morphism on an object. -/
3  id : ∀ X : obj, Hom X X
4  /-- Composition of morphisms in a category, written 'f » g'. -/
5  comp : ∀ {X Y Z : obj}, (X → Y) → (Y → Z) → (X → Z)

```

Here, `Mathlib` defines the notation $X \rightarrow Y$ for the morphisms between X and Y and $f \gg g$ for the composition. `Mathlib` uses *diagrammatic* composition, that is, on the left we write the morphism that acts first and on the right the one that acts afterwards.

The complete category class, `Category`, extends the previous one with the identity and associativity axioms:

```

1  class Category (obj : Type u) : Type max u (v + 1) extends CategoryStruct.{v} obj
   where
2  /-- Identity morphisms are left identities for composition. -/
3  id_comp : ∀ {X Y : obj} (f : X → Y), 1 X » f = f := by cat_disch
4  /-- Identity morphisms are right identities for composition. -/
5  comp_id : ∀ {X Y : obj} (f : X → Y), f » 1 Y = f := by cat_disch
6  /-- Composition in a category is associative. -/
7  assoc : ∀ {W X Y Z : obj} (f : W → X) (g : X → Y) (h : Y → Z), (f » g) » h = f »
   g » h := by
8  cat_disch

```

This fragment shows the default value `:= by cat_disch`: `Mathlib`'s automatic discharge tool for the routine axioms of its category library. It is the analogue of our `hcat_disch`. The difference is one of scope, since `hcat_disch` extends the search with the rules of our higher-categorical library.

7.4.2 Bundled families

Before showing code, it is worth noting what problem we want to solve. The constructions $n\text{Cat}$, ωCat , $n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ and $\omega\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$ of Chapter 3 and Chapter 4 have as objects categories, that is, pairs formed by an underlying type and a category structure on it. `Mathlib`'s `Category` class, by contrast, expects in its first argument a single type. And as long as our categories remain *classes*, their instances are, for the system, an invisible property of the type that the elaborator locates by inference, not a piece of data over which we can quantify: by itself, the class does not give us a type of objects to organize as a category. The pattern that `Mathlib` follows in these cases is that of *bundled structures*, that is, a new `structure` whose terms bundle, as explicit data, the type and the instance. We develop this next.

The base structure is `Cat Index` and reduces to those two fields:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/CAT.LEAN
45 structure Cat (Index : Type) [Preorder Index] where
46   /-- Build a 'Cat' from a carrier type with a 'Category' instance. -/
47   of ::
48   /-- The underlying carrier type. -/
49   carrier : Type u
50   /-- The single-sorted category structure on the carrier. -/
51   [str : Category Index carrier]
52
53 attribute [instance] Cat.str
```

A term $C : \text{Cat } \text{Index}$ contains, on the one hand, the underlying type $\text{carrier} : \text{Type } u$ and, on the other, the category instance $[\text{str} : \text{Category } \text{Index } \text{carrier}]$, marked as an instance argument via the brackets. The line `attribute [instance] Cat.str` that follows the declaration exposes that second field as an automatic instance of the system: given a $C : \text{Cat } \text{Index}$, the elaborator finds on its own the instance $\text{Category } \text{Index } C.\text{carrier}$, so that the categorical operations become available without passing it by hand. The structure thus recovers, from the object side, the inference behaviour that the class had before.

Next, a coercion allows us to use $\text{Cat } \text{Index}$ wherever a type is expected:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/CAT.LEAN
60 instance : CoeSort (Cat Index) (Type u) := ⟨Cat.carrier⟩
61
62 attribute [coe] Cat.carrier
```

The instance $\text{CoeSort } (\text{Cat } \text{Index}) (\text{Type } u)$ lets us write $C : \text{Type } u$ (and iterate over its elements) instead of $C.\text{carrier}$ everywhere, and `attribute [coe] Cat.carrier` makes the coercion show up in the goals as such, not as a projection. With this, the API of the structure is closed: a $\text{Cat } \text{Index}$ is, for the purposes of use, a type endowed with a category over it, with no need to distinguish between the bundle and its content.

On top of that API we now build the Mathlib category:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/CAT.LEAN
70 instance category : CategoryTheory.LargeCategory.{u} (Cat Index) where
71   Hom C D := Functor Index C D
72   comp F G := G ∘ F
73   id C := ids C
```

The morphisms between two objects C and D are the single-sorted functors $\text{Functor } \text{Index } C D$, the identity is id_s and the composition integrates with Mathlib's diagrammatic convention in a single line: $\text{comp } F G := G \circ F$ passes the first argument of the diagrammatic composition as the second to the project's applicative composition \circ . From here on, the rest of Mathlib's categorical apparatus applies without further ado.

The specialization to the finite-dimensional case is immediate: $\text{NCat } n := \text{Cat } (\text{Fin } n)$ is an abbrev with its own category instance that brings the morphisms to the concrete type $\text{NFunctor } n$.

For the ω version the asymmetry that we have already seen between the two presentations appears. In single-sorted, `OmegaCategory` is not a mere abbrev of `Category` \mathbb{N} , since it has the extra field corresponding to `(ω SI)`, so that `OmegaCat` is defined as an independent `structure` that replicates the same carrier-plus-instance pattern. In many-sorted, where `OmegaCategory` is already an alias, it suffices to write `abbrev OmegaCat := Cat` \mathbb{N} . The two cases coexist without friction because the generic construction `Cat` `Index` is the common piece.

It is interesting to note that the proofs of Mathlib’s category axioms close automatically with the tactic `cat_disch`, which is Mathlib’s analogue of our tactic `heat_disch`. Again, we will discuss this tool in Section 7.5. We emphasize that this shows that the design choices made so far are “compatible” with Mathlib’s architecture.

7.4.3 Universe levels

In Chapter 2 we made an explicit effort to keep the notion of *small category* bounded, restricting the underlying set to live in a Grothendieck universe \mathcal{U} . In Lean, that role is played by the *universe levels* that we already described in connection with universe polymorphism in Chapter 6. An object of `Cat` `Index` contains a `Type` `u`, so that `Cat` `Index` lives in `Type` `(u + 1)`. The category that is built on it, consequently, a `CategoryTheory.LargeCategory` `{u}`, as can be seen in the previous fragment. It is the same phenomenon that distinguishes `Cat` as a *large category* versus the ordinary categories: here it is expressed by the universe levels.

7.4.4 Unification of finite-dimensional and infinite-dimensional cases

In Remark 3.3.4 we fixed the convention of writing $n \in \omega + 1$ to treat uniformly the finite-dimensional and the infinite-dimensional cases. In Lean, this ordinal is modelled with \mathbb{N}_∞ (the `WithTop` \mathbb{N} of Mathlib), where the element \top (the maximum of the order) plays the role of ω . The project introduces two notations that replace Mathlib’s names and keep the syntax close to that of the document.

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/NOTATION.LEAN
24 /-- Notation for the top element of an order with top ('Top.top'). In our
    context, it represents the
25 index of an  $\omega$ -category in ' $\mathbb{N}_\infty$ '. -/
26 scoped notation " $\omega$ " => Top.top
27
28 /-- Notation for the injection into a 'WithTop' type ('WithTop.some'). In our
    context, it represents
29 the index of an  $n$ -category in ' $\mathbb{N}_\infty$ '. -/
30 scoped notation "fin" => WithTop.some
```

With those notations, the abbreviation `ICat` (from *indexed*) is defined by case analysis on the dimension, which recovers the finite-dimensional version or the ω version as appropriate:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/CAT.LEAN
141 abbrev ICat (dimension :  $\mathbb{N}_\infty$ ) : Type (u + 1) := match dimension with
142   | fin n => NCat n
143   |  $\omega$  => OmegaCat
144
```

```

145 /-- Category instance for 'ICat dimension', where the category instance for each
146    is inferred from the corresponding category instance of 'NCat n' or 'OmegaCat'.
147    -/
147 instance ICat.category {dimension : ℕ∞} : CategoryTheory.LargeCategory.{u} (ICat
148    dimension) :=
148   match dimension with
149   | fin _ ⇒ NCat.category
150   | ω ⇒ OmegaCat.category

```

The analysis is done with `match` on the two cases `fin n` and `ω`, and the category instance of `ICat` is built, in parallel, also by `match`. The gain is to state in a single go results indexed over \mathbb{N}^∞ without having to duplicate the finite-dimensional case and the infinite-dimensional one. We will see it in use in Section 7.6, when the unified discretization and underlying functors appear.

§ 7.5

Proof automation

Throughout the previous sections we have seen the tactic `hcat_disch` appear in every axiom of `PreCategory`, `Category` and the functors. We have presented it as the project’s *discharge tool* and we have used it, without detailing it, in each of them. It is time to explain it. The idea, before entering into the code, is simple. A good part of the proofs that appear when formalizing mathematics reduce to applying definitions, normalizing by rewriting with a few basic lemmas and letting the system recognize the result. *Automatic discharge tactics* deal precisely with this, closing these goals without us having to write the complete details. The benefit is double: we free up the “by hand” proofs for the steps that do say something new and, in addition, we reduce the size of the code without losing guarantees, since whatever the tactic closes will still be checked by the kernel anyway.

7.5.1 General-purpose discharge tactics

In Lean there coexist two general-purpose discharge tactics that are worth keeping in mind. The first is `grind`, native to the language since version 4.22 and still evolving. It combines congruence closure, linear arithmetic, reasoning about rings and other techniques.

The second is `aesop` (*Automated Extensible Search for Obvious Proofs*) [LF23], an external tactic but more mature and, above all, *extensible*¹⁸. It works by proof search guided by rule sets that the user can declare and populate with their own lemmas. `Mathlib` uses it intensively; in particular, its category library exposes a specific variant, `aesop_cat`, that discharges the routine categorical axioms and on which the `cat_disch` tool we saw earlier is built. It is precisely this pattern that the project adopts.

7.5.2 The project’s discharge tactic

The tactic provided by the project, `hcat_disch`, is not a new tool, but the composition of the previous ones with a tailor-made rule set. Its logic is described in its elaborator.

¹⁸Although `grind` also has extension systems, they are still weaker than those of `aesop` and it keeps receiving constant improvements in the different Lean updates.

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/TACTIC.LEAN
57 private meta def higherCategoryTheoryDischarger (suggest : Bool) : TacticM
   Unit := do
58   let suggest := suggest || hcat.tactic.suggest.get (← getOptions)
59   let wrap (tac : TSyntax `tactic) : TacticM (TSyntax `tactic) :=
60     if suggest then `(tactic| try_this $tac) else pure tac
61   let mut tactics : Array (TSyntax `tactic) := #[]
62   tactics := tactics.push (← wrap (← `(tactic| (intros; rfl))))
63   if hcat.tactic.omega.get (← getOptions) then
64     tactics := tactics.push (← wrap (← `(tactic| (intros; omega))))
65   tactics := tactics.push (← if suggest then `(tactic| aesop_hcat?) else
     `(tactic| aesop_hcat))
66   evalTactic (← `(tactic| first $[] $tactics:tactic*))
```

The first two routes are cheap attempts at trivial goals: `intros; rfl` closes everything that reduces to reflexivity after introducing the hypotheses, and `intros; omega` (when the option `hcat.tactic.omega` is active) discharges the arithmetic obligations over \mathbb{N} or Fin . If none prospers, we fall back on `aesop_hcat`, a wrapper around `aesop` that triggers the search with the project's specific rule set:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/INIT.LEAN
15 declare_aesop_rule_sets [HigherCategoryTheory]
```

The rule set is called, simply, `HigherCategoryTheory`. The axioms of `PreCategory`, `Category` and `Functor` are marked, by means of an `attribute [simp]` subsequent to the declaration of the class, as *simplification lemmas*. The corresponding line for the many-sorted `PreCategory` appears right after the closing of the class:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/MANYSORTED/CATEGORY.LEAN
238 -- Use axioms of `PreCategory` as simp lemmas.
239 open PreCategory in
240 attribute [simp] sckj_compkj_eq_sckj tgkj_compkj_eq_tgkj sckj_idmkj tgkj_idmkj
241   compkj_idmkj_sckj_eq_id compkj_tgkj_idmkj_eq_id assoc
```

Besides these, there are many other points of the formalization that are marked as simplification lemmas and that enrich the project's rule set. The result is a cascading effect: each new axiom automatically feeds the search and most of the routine obligations of the subsequent constructions close without writing a script. This is what makes viable the pattern that we have been using in all the classes of the chapter: declaring the axioms with `:= by hcat_disch` as the default value. When a concrete instance is provided, one does not have to worry about proving the routine axioms; if a sequence of rewrites closes them, the tactic finds the path on its own.

There is a second role of the discharge tactics worth highlighting that goes beyond closing proofs. Both `aesop` and `simp` and `grind` admit an interrogative variant (`aesop?`, `simp?`, `grind?`) that, instead of merely closing the goal, *emits the concrete script* (the list of lemmas, the rewrites, the exact steps) that closed it. This changes the role of the tactic: it goes from being an opaque closure to being an exploration instrument. Faced with a complicated goal, running the interrogative version reveals which lemmas are the ones doing the work and then allows one to fix a stable proof (typically

a `simp only [...]`) that does not depend on the state of the rule set or on the evolution of the tactics. The project exposes this same idea for its own tactic: there is the variant `heat_disch?` and, symmetrically, `aesop_heat?`. In addition, the option `heat.tactic.suggest` activates this behaviour globally.

In practice, this “interrogative” use has been one of the most useful tools during the formalization. The combinations of lemmas that close the goals generated by `split_ifs` in Section 7.6, for instance, were discovered precisely by launching the interrogative variants on the pending goals, and the returned script was subsequently incorporated as an explicit proof. The tactic not only saves routine work, but also teaches us what is to be proved.

There are occasions, however, in which these discharge tactics are not sufficient and do not find the path. Nevertheless, they provide useful information, since in this exploration one discovers which rules and rewriting lemmas advanced the search the most and which did not, which guides the construction of a manual proof. Moreover, it is not necessary that the entire proof consist in applying the tactic. It is also possible to advance with manual steps and, in situations of blockage, launch the tactic to keep advancing.

§ 7.6

Discretization and underlying in the single-sorted case

With these two presentations in place, the category of categories and the automation already in place, we can work on the two transformations that connect different dimensions within a single presentation. We begin with the single-sorted case, where the mechanics are the most direct. The two constructions traverse the hierarchy in opposite directions: the *underlying* goes down in dimension, keeping the subset of cells of the original, while the *discretization* goes up in dimension, declaring the added levels to be trivial. The mathematical definitions are developed in Chapter 3, so here we deal with how they are modelled in Lean and with the technical difficulties exposed by each one.

7.6.1 Subtypes and the underlying transformation

The mathematical definition fixes the underlying at dimension m as the m -category over the subset C_m of m -cells of the original, with the operations birestricted to that subset. The translation to Lean replaces the subset with the corresponding *subtype*, `cells m C := {f : C // cell m f}`, and birestricts each operation. The good definition of these birestrictions is precisely what is proved by the auxiliary lemmas of the module on cells that we announced in connection with the cells in the single-sorted presentation: `underlying_source_is_cell`, `underlying_target_is_cell`, `underlying_comp_is_cell` and `underlying_functor_is_cell`. Once the birestrictions are defined, it remains to construct the `NCategory` instance and to check that it satisfies the axioms that make it up.

Here arises the first friction point: each axiom of the underlying is, *literally*, the corresponding axiom of the original category, read on the subtype. But in Lean an equality on the subtype `cells m C` is not syntactically the same thing as an equality on `C`, even though conceptually they coincide. So as not to write by hand the same chain of rewrites axiom by axiom, the project introduces a local macro that automates the pattern:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/UNDERLYING/FUNCTOR.LEAN
90 macro (name := inherit_axiom) "inherit_axiom" axiom_name:ident : tactic =>
91   `(tactic| (intros; rw [Subtype.mk.injEq]; try (apply $axiom_name <;> (simp at
   *; assumption))))
```

The macro `inherit_axiom` introduces the variables of the axiom with `intros`, brings the equality of subtypes down to equality of the underlying values with `Subtype.mk.injEq` and applies the axiom of the parent, discharging what remains with `simp at *` and `assumption`. The use, axiom by axiom, becomes particularly clean. We show the definitions of the operations and the first axioms. The rest follow the same pattern.

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/UNDERLYING/FUNCTOR.LEAN
104 @[simp]
105 def NCategory.underlying (S : NCategory n C) (m : Fin n) : NCategory m (cells m
   C) where
106   sc k := S.sc_birestriction ⟨k, lt_trans k.isLt m.isLt⟩ k.isLt
107   tg k := S.tg_birestriction ⟨k, lt_trans k.isLt m.isLt⟩ k.isLt
108   pcomp k := S.pcomp_birestriction ⟨k, lt_trans k.isLt m.isLt⟩ k.isLt
109   sck_sck_eq_sck := by inherit_axiom S.sck_sck_eq_sck
110   tgz_sck_eq_sck := by inherit_axiom S.tgz_sck_eq_sck
111   sck_tgz_eq_tgz := by inherit_axiom S.sck_tgz_eq_tgz
112   tgz_tgz_eq_tgz := by inherit_axiom S.tgz_tgz_eq_tgz
```

7.6.2 Dependent conditionals and the discretization transformation

Discretization goes up in dimension by declaring every level above the original to be trivial. The definition asks, for each level k of the new m -category, to distinguish two cases: if $k < n$, the operation coincides with that of the original n -category; if $n \leq k < m$, the operation is trivial (the identity for the source and the target, and composition defined only between equal morphisms). This dichotomy is transferred to Lean with a *dependent conditional*, `dite` (the `if h : P then ... else ...`), because the positive branch needs the proof $k < n$ in order to invoke the operation of the original category.

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/DISCRETE/FUNCTOR.LEAN
56 @[simp]
57 def NCategory.discrete (S : NCategory n C) (m : ℕ) (_n_lt_m : n < m) : NCategory
   m C where
58   sc k f := if k_lt_n : k < n then S.sc ⟨k, k_lt_n⟩ f else f
59   tg k f := if k_lt_n : k < n then S.tg ⟨k, k_lt_n⟩ f else f
60   pcomp k g f := if k_lt_n : k < n then S.pcomp ⟨k, k_lt_n⟩ g f else ⟨g = f, fun
   _ => f⟩
```

This introduces a layer of case reasoning into each axiom. The tactic `split_ifs` is the expected tool: it splits the goal according to the value of each `if` and leaves simpler goals per branch. When $k < n$, the branch reproduces the axiom of the original category; when $n \leq k$, the branch is trivial and is closed by `rfl` or `simp`. As an illustration, one of the discretization axiom proofs has the following shape:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/DISCRETE/FUNCTOR.LEAN
```

```
86   sck_compk_eq_sck := by
87     intro k f g sc_tg_gf
88     split_ifs with h
89     · simp only [CategoryStruct.comp, h]
90       apply S.sck_compk_eq_sck
91     simp [h] at sc_tg_gf
92     assumption
93     · simp [h]
```

```
LEAN INFOVIEW · Line 87
```

```
1 goal
```

```
n : ℕ
C : Type u
S : NCategory n C
m : ℕ
_n_lt_m : n < m
k : Fin m
f : C
g : C
sc_tg_gf : sc_is_tg k g f
⊢ (if k_lt_n : ↑k < n then sc ⟨↑k, k_lt_n⟩ (g #[k] f ← sc_tg_gf) else g #[k] f ←
  sc_tg_gf) =
  if k_lt_n : ↑k < n then sc ⟨↑k, k_lt_n⟩ f else f
```

```
LEAN INFOVIEW · Line 88
```

```
2 goals
```

```
case pos
n : ℕ
C : Type u
S : NCategory n C
m : ℕ
_n_lt_m : n < m
k : Fin m
f : C
g : C
sc_tg_gf : sc_is_tg k g f
h : ↑k < n
⊢ sc ⟨↑k, h⟩ (g #[k] f ← sc_tg_gf) = sc ⟨↑k, h⟩ f

case neg
n : ℕ
C : Type u
S : NCategory n C
m : ℕ
_n_lt_m : n < m
k : Fin m
f : C
g : C
```

```

sc_tg_gf : sc_is_tg k g f
h : ¬↑k < n
⊢ g #[k] f ← sc_tg_gf = f

```

The pattern, repeated axiom by axiom, leads to a long but flat definition. Where it gets a bit more complicated is in the interdimensional axioms, in which two indices appear and, therefore, two conditionals, so that `split_ifs` can generate up to four goals. The “main” branch invokes the original axiom; of the remaining ones, the genuinely trivial ones are closed with `rfl`, and those corresponding to impossible combinations of indices, with `omega`.

```

HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/DISCRETE/FUNCTOR.LEAN
196 interchange := by
197   intro k j f₁ f₂ g₁ g₂ j_lt_k sc_tg_k_g₂g₁ sc_tg_k_f₂f₁ sc_tg_j_g₂f₂
198   sc_tg_j_g₁f₁
199   simp only [CategoryStruct.comp]
200   split_ifs with h₁ h₂
201   · apply S.interchange
202   · assumption
203   · simp [h₁] at sc_tg_k_g₂g₁
204     assumption
205   · simp [h₁] at sc_tg_k_f₂f₁
206     assumption
207   · simp [h₂] at sc_tg_j_g₂f₂
208     assumption
209   · simp [h₂] at sc_tg_j_g₁f₁
210     assumption
211   · rfl
212   · rfl

```

The version that goes up to ω is structurally identical, except for the closing of the new axiom (ω S1): it suffices to take n as the witness index, since for every $k \geq n$ the construction itself declares $sc_k(f) = f$, so that f is an n -cell. The project closes it with a `use n` and a subsequent normalization.

7.6.3 Functoriality of the transformations

It remains to organize discretization and underlying as *functors* between the categories of Section 7.4. The basic pieces are `FinDiscretizationFunctor` and `OmegaDiscretizationFunctor`, which respectively cover the finite-dimensional case $n < m$ and the case $n < \omega$.

```

HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/DISCRETE/FUNCTOR.LEAN
470 /-- The discretization functor from the category of $n$-categories to the
471 category of
472 $m$-categories for finite dimensions, where $n < m$. Sends each $n$-category to
473 its discrete
474 $m$-category and each functor to its lift between the discrete categories. -/
475 def FinDiscretizationFunctor (n m : ℕ) (n_lt_m : n < m) : ICat.{u} n ⇒ ICat.{u}
476 m where
477   obj C := letI := NCategory.discrete C.str m n_lt_m; Cat.of C

```

```

475 map {C D} F := F.discrete m n_lt_m
476
477 /-- The discretization functor from the category of  $n$ -categories to the
478  $\omega$ -categories. Sends each  $n$ -category to its discrete  $\omega$ -category
479 its lift between the discrete categories. -/
480 def OmegaDiscretizationFunctor (n : ℕ) : ICat.{u} n  $\Rightarrow$  ICat.{u}  $\omega$  where
481   obj C := letI := NCategory.discreteOmega C.str; OmegaCat.of C
482   map {C D} F := F.discreteOmega

```

We highlight, once again, how Mathlib’s automation tactics automatically close the functoriality axioms. As we mentioned in the corresponding proofs of Chapter 3, the verifications were trivial.

The unified version, `DiscretizationFunctor`, uses the abbreviation `ICat` over \mathbb{N}^∞ that we introduced in Section 7.4: indexed by a pair $(n, m) : \mathbb{N}^\infty \times \mathbb{N}^\infty$ with $n \leq m$, a single `match` covers all the cases at once.

```

HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/SINGLESORTED/DISCRETE/FUNCTOR.LEAN
488 def DiscretizationFunctor (n m : ℕ $^\infty$ ) (n_le_m : n  $\leq$  m) : ICat.{u} n  $\Rightarrow$  ICat.{u}
   m :=
489   match n, m with
490   | fin n, fin m  $\Rightarrow$ 
491     if h : n < m then
492       FinDiscretizationFunctor n m h
493     else by
494       simp only [ENat.some_eq_coe, Nat.cast_le] at n_le_m
495       have : n = m := n_le_m.eq_of_not_lt h
496       rw [this]
497       exact 1 (ICat.{u} m)
498   | fin n,  $\omega$   $\Rightarrow$  OmegaDiscretizationFunctor n
499   |  $\omega$ ,  $\omega$   $\Rightarrow$  1 (ICat.{u}  $\omega$ )

```

It is worth observing that the cases $n = m$ finite-dimensional and infinite-dimensional return directly the respective identity functors. Even so, there is a notable difference from the finite-dimensional case to the infinite-dimensional one. In the latter, the pattern matching is capable of automatically identifying the source and target categories of the functor as equal, so that the identity functor works directly. However, in the finite-dimensional case, we have to manually unpack the case $n < m$, where we use `FinDiscretizationFunctor`, and from the case $n \not< m$, we have to deduce that, since $n \leq m$, $n = m$, instruct Lean that both categories, the source and the target one, are equal, and then use the identity functor.

§ 7.7

Discretization and underlying in the many-sorted case

This section is important for a different reason from the previous ones. In it appears for the first time in the formalization a technical phenomenon that we have been anticipating on many

occasions: the explicit handling of *transports* along equalities of types. It is the first issue that the many-sorted presentation transfers to Lean.

Moreover, here a simpler version of the problem that appears when speaking of the equivalence is presented. However, the fact that here it has been possible to successfully formalize the discretization transformation (which is the one that introduces the complexity) illustrates that one may consider a complete formalization of the equivalence as future work, as we will point out in the conclusions.

7.7.1 Reindexing and the underlying transformation

We begin with the more comfortable construction. The many-sorted underlying goes down in dimension by trimming the domain of the index: the underlying family is restricted to `fun k ↦ C ⟨k, by omega⟩`, a mere reindexing.

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/MANYSORTED/UNDERLYING/FUNCTOR.LEAN
37 /-- The restriction of a `NTypeFamily n` to `NTypeFamily m` for `m < n` -/
38 abbrev NTypeFamily.underlying {n : ℕ} (C : NTypeFamily.{u} n) (m : Fin n) :
   NTypeFamily m :=
39   fun k ↦ C ⟨k, by omega⟩
40
41 /-- The restriction of an `OmegaTypeFamily` to `NTypeFamily m` for any natural
   `m` -/
42 abbrev OmegaTypeFamily.underlying (C : OmegaTypeFamily.{u}) (m : ℕ) : NTypeFamily
   m :=
43   fun k ↦ C k
```

The categorical structure is inherited directly, operation by operation and axiom by axiom, with no complex wrappers. We show only some of the fields.

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/MANYSORTED/UNDERLYING/FUNCTOR.LEAN
57 def NCategory.underlying (S : NCategory n C) (m : Fin n) :
58   NCategory m (NTypeFamily.underlying C m) where
59   sc j_lt_k f := S.sc j_lt_k f
60   tg j_lt_k f := S.tg j_lt_k f
61   idm j_lt_k f := S.idm j_lt_k f
62   pcomp j_lt_k g f := S.pcomp j_lt_k g f
63   sckj_compkj_eq_sckj := S.sckj_compkj_eq_sckj
64   tgkj_compkj_eq_tgkj := S.tgkj_compkj_eq_tgkj
```

What is most relevant about this fragment is what *does not* appear. There is no `inherit_axiom`, no `Subtype.mk.injEq` and no transport of equalities. Each operation is the parent's with the index reindexed and each axiom is obtained by passing literally the corresponding one of `S`. The reason is structural: trimming dimensions does not touch the underlying types `C k`, which stay as they are, so that the operations are invoked under the same name and no syntactically distinct types that “should” be equal are generated.

7.7.2 Transports along equality of types and the discretization transformation

The situation changes when going up in dimension. The many-sorted discretization replicates the top type C_n at each new level. The natural way of encoding that replication in Lean is to define a *retract* from the index of the new category to that of the original which, at each dimension $k \geq n$, returns n ; on top of it the original underlying family is composed to obtain the new one:

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/MANYSORTED/DISCRETE/FUNCTOR.LEAN
47  /-- Retract of dimensions onto 'FinSucc n'. Sends 'k' to 'min k n' viewed as an
    element of
48  'FinSucc n', collapsing every dimension at or above 'n' onto the top. -/
49  abbrev retract (n k : ℕ) : FinSucc n :=
50    ⟨min k n, by omega⟩
```

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/MANYSORTED/DISCRETE/FUNCTOR.LEAN
85  /-- Extension of a many-sorted type family 'C : NTypeFamily n' to 'NTypeFamily m'
    by composing
86  with the retract 'retract n'. Dimensions $k \geq n$ all share the type 'C n'. -/
87  abbrev NTypeFamily.discrete {n : ℕ} (C : NTypeFamily.{u} n) (m : ℕ) :
    NTypeFamily.{u} m :=
88    fun k ↦ C (retract n k)
```

The retract is the map $k \mapsto \min(k, n)$ viewed as an element of $\text{FinSucc } n$: below n it behaves like the identity and above it it collapses to n . The new family $\text{NTypeFamily.discrete } C \ m$ is, simply, the composition of the original family with the retract.

This was the most natural option, and mathematically it is. Technically, however, it has an uncomfortable consequence. For a symbolic index k greater than or equal to n , the system knows *mathematically* that the associated type coincides with C_n , but the expressions $C (\text{retract } n \ k)$ and $C \ n$ are syntactically distinct until the equality of the indices is proved. For Lean, two terms with those two types do not admit direct comparison with the classical equality, $=$. It would have to be, in principle, a *heterogeneous equality*. The machinery that the project employs to circumvent the difficulty is that of the *transport along equality of types*, that is, the operator `cast`.

The operator `cast` transports a term from one type to another along an equality between them: given $h : \alpha = \beta$ and $a : \alpha$, one has `cast h a : β`. Its heterogeneous analogue, `HEq`, is designed to compare terms of types that are a priori distinct and, when both types turn out to be the same, it reduces to an ordinary equality. At this point in the code the project *does not* need `HEq`: each type incompatibility comes accompanied by an equality of indices ($\text{retract } n \ j = \text{retract } n \ k$ when $n \leq j < k$) that the lemma `retract.eq_of_ge` materializes, so that it suffices to transport with `cast` along `congrArg C eq`. We reserve `HEq` for Section 7.8, where it will indeed be needed.

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/MANYSORTED/DISCRETE/FUNCTOR.LEAN
77  theorem eq_of_ge {j k : ℕ} (j_lt_k : j < k) (n_le_j : n ≤ j) :
78    retract n j = retract n k := by
79    apply Fin.ext
80    change min j n = min k n
81    omega
```

LEAN INFOVIEW · Line 79

1 goal

case h

n : ℕ

j : ℕ

k : ℕ

j_lt_k : j < k

n_le_j : n ≤ j

⊢ ↑(retract n j) = ↑(retract n k)

LEAN INFOVIEW · Line 80

1 goal

case h

n : ℕ

j : ℕ

k : ℕ

j_lt_k : j < k

n_le_j : n ≤ j

⊢ min j n = min k n

The transport appears, firstly, in the very definition of the discretization. When j is not strictly less than n , the operations of source, target and identity reduce to the identity, wrapped in a cast along the equality of indices:

HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/MANYSORTED/DISCRETE/FUNCTOR.LEAN

162 @[simp]

163 def NCategory.discrete (S : NCategory n C) (m : ℕ) (_n_lt_m : n < m) :

164 NCategory m (NTypeFamily.discrete C m) where

165 sc {k j} j_lt_k f :=

166 if h : j < n then

167 S.sc (retract.strict_mono j_lt_k h) f

168 else

169 cast (congrArg C (retract.eq_of_ge j_lt_k (not_lt.mp h)).symm) f

170 tg {k j} j_lt_k f :=

171 if h : j < n then

172 S.tg (retract.strict_mono j_lt_k h) f

173 else

174 cast (congrArg C (retract.eq_of_ge j_lt_k (not_lt.mp h)).symm) f

175 idm {k j} j_lt_k f :=

176 if h : j < n then

177 S.idm (retract.strict_mono j_lt_k h) f

178 else

179 cast (congrArg C (retract.eq_of_ge j_lt_k (not_lt.mp h))) f

180 pcomp {k j} j_lt_k g f :=

181 if h : j < n then

182 S.pcomp (retract.strict_mono j_lt_k h) g f

183 else

184 ⟨g = f, fun _ => f⟩

It is worth observing the direction of each transport. The source and the target take a k -morphism to a j -morphism (they go down in dimension) and that is why they transport along $(\text{retract.eq_of_ge } \dots). \text{symm}$. The identity, by contrast, takes a j -morphism up to dimension k and transports in the opposite direction, along $\text{retract.eq_of_ge } \dots$ without symm . Composition is the only one that does not need cast : above n it is defined only between equal morphisms, by means of $\langle g = f, \text{fun } _ \rightarrow f \rangle$.

And the transport appears, secondly, in each axiom that shares the pattern. So that the proofs do not fill up with manipulations of cast , the project groups five private lemmas in a section, `DiscreteCategoryHelpers`. We show one of them, since the others are analogous.

```
HIGHERCATEGORYTHEORY/MANYSORTED/DISCRETE/FUNCTOR.LEAN
105 private theorem cast_sc {k k' j : FinSucc n} (eq : k = k')
106   (j_lt_k : j < k) (j_lt_k' : j < k') (f : C k') :
107   S.sc j_lt_k (cast (congrArg C eq.symm) f) = S.sc j_lt_k' f := by
108   subst eq
109   rfl
```

These five lemmas (`cast_sc`, `cast_tg`, `cast_idm`, `sc_tg_cast` and `cast_comp`) are the atoms with which the project manages all the transports in the subsequent proofs. The mechanism of each one is the same: a `subst` on the equality of indices substitutes it everywhere, which reduces the `cast` to a transport along `rfl` and leaves the goal resolved by `rfl`. The only exception is `sc_tg_cast`, which closes with the very composability hypothesis already transported.

The asymmetry with the single-sorted discretization of Section 7.6 is clear: there `split_ifs` and the original axioms sufficed, while here we have to add, in addition, a layer of transports that did not exist in single-sorted. The difference is not mathematical: both constructions reduce, conceptually, to the same equalities. The overhead appears in the encoding in dependent type theory.

We close with two observations. The two versions of the discretization are almost duplicated code: they share structure and differ only in the index type. Furthermore, the organization as a functor is unified again over \mathbb{N}_∞ , following exactly the pattern of `DiscretizationFunctor` from the single-sorted presentation: the `match` on (n, m) is identical, with the same unfolding of the case $n = m$ finite-dimensional that we already referred to in Section 7.6.

§ 7.8

Dependent types in the equivalence

As we proved in Chapter 5, the single-sorted and many-sorted presentations are equivalent by means of a pair of functors, the *graduation* $\text{Gd}^{(n)}$ and the *unification* $\text{Uf}^{(n)}$. The mathematical proof has no fundamental difficulty and presents an asymmetry in both directions. The composition $\text{Uf}^{(n)} \circ \text{Gd}^{(n)}$ is *literally* the identity of $n\text{Cat}$, while $\text{Gd}^{(n)} \circ \text{Uf}^{(n)}$ is only *naturally isomorphic* to the identity of $n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}$. Both facts reduce to substituting equals for equals and applying the relations between axioms that we already made explicit in the previous chapters. Their formalization in Lean, however, encounters obstacles that place it outside the scope of this work, and this section discusses them in detail.

Let us start by specifying what we would have to construct. The goal is to inhabit a term of `CategoryTheory.Equivalence (SingleSorted.NCat n) (ManySorted.NCat n)`, Mathlib’s category equivalence structure. An `Equivalence` is not constructed with equalities, but with two *isomorphisms*, the *unit* between the identity and one direction of the composition, and the *counit* between the other direction and the identity. The important observation is that the components of those isomorphisms are invertible morphisms, that is, functors between our categories, and a functor is built from honest maps between the underlying types.

Let us see it in the *counit* direction. Given C a many-sorted n -category with family $(C_k)_{k \in n+1}$, the composition $\text{Gd}^{(n)}(\text{Uf}^{(n)}(C))$ has an underlying family distinct from the starting one, since each C_k is replaced by C'_k , the subtype of C_n formed by the images of the inclusion $\text{id}^{(n,k)}$. The component of the isomorphism at dimension k is a map $C_k \rightarrow C'_k$; this is the conflictive point. Defining that map does not require transporting anything. It is, simply, $f \mapsto \text{id}^{(n,k)}(f)$ wrapped in the proof of membership in the subtype, with inverse $\text{sc}^{(k,n)}$ birestricted. In code it has the shape of an ordinary function between types, without `cast` or `HEq`:

```
1 def component (S : NCategory n C) {k : FinSucc n} (h : k < n) (f : C k) : C' k :=
2   ⟨S.idm h f, by ...⟩
```

That this family of maps is an isomorphism follows from the two identities $\text{sc}^{(k,n)} \circ \text{id}^{(n,k)} = \text{id}_{C_k}$ and $\text{id}^{(n,k)} \circ \text{sc}^{(k,n)} = \text{id}_{C'_k}$, which are equalities of *functions* between honest types and are proved pointwise with the argument of Chapter 5. None of this requires equality of types. The equivalence *itself*, therefore, is reachable up to isomorphism and without resorting at any moment to heterogeneous equality, also on the side of the *unit*, where the isomorphism is constructed in the same way even though Proposition 5.3.1 guarantees that the composition is the identity.

The cost, however, does not disappear, but is shifted elsewhere. Part of it is of the same nature as the one we already encountered in Section 7.7. So as not to step out of homogeneous equality, the subtypes and the inequalities between dimensions are again handled by transporting with `cast` (`congrArg C eq`) instead of comparing with `HEq`, and checking that each component respects the operations relies again on auxiliary lemmas like those there, which reduce the `cast` to the identity with a `subst` on the equality of indices.

That the pattern repeats does not mean, however, that the work is the same nor that it suffices to copy it. The definitions of the equivalence cross subtypes and changes of dimension at many more points than those of the discretization, so that the transports cease to appear in isolation in each operation and start to chain inside each component and each naturality square.

The genuinely new part appears in the infinite-dimensional case. The underlying set of $\text{Uf}^{(\omega)}(C)$ is built as the quotient of the coproduct $\coprod_{k \in \omega} C_k$ by the relation that identifies each morphism with its image upon going up in dimension. It is the inductive limit of the system $(C_k, \text{id}^{(k+1,k)})$ that Chapter 5 describes through its universal property. The natural encoding in Lean is a `Quotient` on $\Sigma k, C k$, and each operation on the unification is defined by choosing a representative at a sufficiently high dimension and discharging, with `Quotient.lift`, the proof that the result does not depend on the choice. Again it is formal work without new mathematical content, but each operation now drags along its own well-definedness obligation.

What remains is the other extreme, and it is where `cast` ceases to be sufficient. If, instead of an isomorphism, we wanted to state the strict equality of Proposition 5.3.1, that is, $\text{Uf}^{(n)}(\text{Gd}^{(n)}(C)) = C$ at the level of objects, the heterogeneous equality becomes unavoidable. The reason is structural. An object of `SingleSorted.NCat n` bundles an underlying type and a category instance on it, so that equating two of these objects forces equating their fields, and the fields are the operations, which live in types of functions over the respective underlying types. Now, in the representation with subtypes that we adopt throughout the work, the underlying type that the round trip returns is not C as such, but a subtype of C that coincides with it only by coercion, not *definitionally*. The operations of one side and the other then have distinct types, and comparing them with `=` does not even type. The only thing Lean admits in that situation is an `HEq`, exactly the phenomenon that occurs when equating terms of a `Sigma` with `Sigma.mk.injEq`.

```
1 example (S : NCategory n C) :
2   HEq (Unification (Graduation S)).sc S.sc := ...
```

In both cases the cost is purely technical and does not incorporate any new mathematical element. We leave for an eventual continuation of the work the formal version of this equivalence, whether by way of the isomorphism or by way of the strict equality, the latter conditioned on extensively using heterogeneous equality.

§ 7.9

The Lean ecosystem

We close the chapter with a brief mention of the tools that surround the code and that, without being part of the mathematical content, are utilities to facilitate the task of formalization. In Appendix A we make a detailed tour through the structure of the repository and the development environment, so here we limit ourselves to presenting the two tools that we have used: the blueprint and the API documentation.

7.9.1 The blueprint

The large formalization projects in Lean, such as the Liquid Tensor Experiment, the PFR or the Sphere Eversion, have been adopting a common tool to coordinate their development, the blueprint. A blueprint is a document, written in LaTeX, that gathers the informal statements (definitions, lemmas, theorems) and accompanies each one with the reference to its formal counterpart in the Lean code. From it a website is generated with two distinct views. On the one hand, the written version of the mathematics, with its proofs in prose. On the other, the *dependency graph* of the formalization, which shows, for each node, whether its statement is already written in Lean, whether its proof is complete, what other nodes depend on it and which ones it depends on in turn.

Figure 7.9.1 and Figure 7.9.2 show two fragments of that graph, the one of the single-sorted underlying constructions and the one of the hierarchy of many-sorted categories. In both, the boxes correspond to definitions that do not require a proof and the ellipses to results or definitions that do, and the green colour signals that the node is fully formalized.

FIGURE 7.9.1. Fragment of the dependency graph of the blueprint, with the single-sorted underlying constructions: the cells, the birestrictions of the operations and the underlying functors.

FIGURE 7.9.2. Fragment of the dependency graph of the blueprint, with the hierarchy of classes of the many-sorted presentation, from `ManySortedCategoryStruct` to `ManySortedNCategory`.

This format achieves two functions at the same time. For the reader of the project, it offers an orderly entry path, which goes from the informal statements to the formal definitions corresponding to them. For the developer, it allows keeping track of the work, that is, knowing what is done, what is missing and what depends on what, on a graph that can be navigated. In our case, the blueprint accompanies the formalization in its own page, linked from the project's page, as we already mentioned at the beginning of the chapter.

It is worth pointing out that, since it is LaTeX code, a PDF version can also be generated (which does not include the dependency graph). On the project's page that document can also be consulted.

7.9.2 The API documentation

The second tool is `doc-gen4`, the standard generator of API documentation in Lean. It gathers all the docstrings of the project, that is, the `/-- ... -/` blocks that accompany each declaration, and publishes them as a navigable website, with indices by namespace and links between related declarations. We have followed the docstring conventions of Mathlib, so that the generated documentation fits with the library's style.

We highlight, finally, that the blueprint has integration with this documentation. If the mathematical environments of the blueprint are appropriately linked to their counterparts in the code, the blueprint website shows, for each node, a direct link to the API documentation of the formal declaration that corresponds to it.

CHAPTER EIGHT

8

Conclusion

Beware of bugs in the above code; I have only proved it correct, not tried it.

— Donald Knuth, letter to Peter van Emde Boas (1977)

In this chapter we recap the work done. We first review what has been presented, distinguishing the exposition of others' work from what constitutes a contribution of our own. We then point out the lines that remain open for future work and close with a brief final reflection.

§ 8.1

Work done

The journey has been a double one, as we anticipated in the introduction. On the mathematical side, we have developed from scratch the two presentations of higher-order categories, the single-sorted and the many-sorted, both in their finite-dimensional version (the n -categories) and in their infinite-dimensional one (the ω -categories), together with their functors and the categories of categories that both determine. On this basis, we have treated the transformations between dimensions (the discretization and the underlying) and we have sketched the equivalence between the two presentations, first in the finite-dimensional case and then in the infinite-dimensional one. On the formal side, we have brought all these notions to Lean 4, relying on Mathlib only for the classical categorical part.

Most of the mathematical development has followed [CCR26], which we take as the central reference. Our work has been one of reorganization for the formalization. The mathematical contribution of our own focuses on presenting the discretization transformations as a mathematical object in itself, as well as the functoriality of these transformations.

The main contribution of the work is, however, the formalization of the work itself. With the exception of the equivalence, whose obstacle we have discussed throughout the work, we have formalized in Lean 4 the entirety of the previous definitions and results: both presentations in their two versions, their functors, the categories of categories and the discretization and underlying transformations with their functoriality.

§ 8.2

Future work

The most immediate line of continuation is the formalization of the equivalence between the presentations, the result of the mathematical development that we have left outside the formal scope. What remains is a considerable amount of encoding work, dominated by the chaining of transports across subtypes and changes of dimension.

On the other hand, we point out an observation that arises when viewing discretization as functors. The equivalence between presentations is, in particular, an adjunction: the graduation $\text{Gd}^{(n)}$ is a left adjoint of the unification $\text{Uf}^{(n)}$, as we saw in Chapter 5. In parallel, for $m, n \in \omega + 1$ with $m \leq n$, our discretization and underlying transformations between dimensions present all the signs of an analogous adjunction: the discretization $\mathcal{D}^{(n,m)}$, which raises the dimension declaring the new ones discrete, and the underlying $\mathcal{U}^{(m,n)}$, which lowers it by discarding them, fit into the classical pattern of adjunction between a discrete functor and a forgetful (underlying in our case) functor. Although we have not gone so far as to prove it, everything points to $\mathcal{D}^{(n,m)}$ being a left adjoint of $\mathcal{U}^{(m,n)}$. If this is confirmed, both adjunctions, the one mediating between presentations

and the one mediating between dimensions, would combine into an *algebraic square* situation (cf. Definition 2.3.12):

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 m\text{Cat} & \begin{array}{c} \xleftarrow{\text{Uf}^{(m)}} \\ \xrightarrow{\text{Gd}^{(m)}} \end{array} & m\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}} \\
 \begin{array}{c} \uparrow \\ \downarrow \end{array} \mathcal{D}^{(n,m)} & \begin{array}{c} \dashv \\ \dashv \end{array} \mathcal{U}^{(m,n)} & \begin{array}{c} \uparrow \\ \downarrow \end{array} \mathcal{D}_{\text{ms}}^{(n,m)} \\
 n\text{Cat} & \begin{array}{c} \xleftarrow{\text{Uf}^{(n)}} \\ \xrightarrow{\text{Gd}^{(n)}} \end{array} & n\text{Cat}_{\text{ms}}
 \end{array}$$

Finally, we raise the incorporation of large language models and of models specialized in mathematics and formal verification into the workflow itself. A good part of the cost that we have identified in the formalization (the mechanical transports, the case analysis that is mathematically trivial but tedious in formal practice) is precisely of the kind in which these tools can excel against humans. One can imagine, in fact, that this might be the route by which the equivalence that we leave pending is completed. During the development of this work, our use of these tools has been limited to occasional consultations, almost as a search resource. The qualitative leap in their capabilities for mathematical assistance is very recent, and their serious integration into formalization projects is still a field under exploration [Yan+25].

§ 8.3

Final reflections

We close with a reflection that has run through the entire work implicitly. Throughout the work, we have come across steps that in informal mathematics are trivial (substituting equals for equals, identifying a k -cell with its image at a higher dimension, restricting an operation to a subset) and that, nevertheless, in the formalization become explicit problems: a transport along an equality of types, a proof of membership in a subtype, a verification of well-definedness. The distance between what we take for granted when writing mathematics in prose and what a machine demands to be made explicit is, perhaps, one of the aspects that is shown most clearly in this work.

One of the lessons that we can draw from the work is that formalizing mathematics and, in particular, these structures, becomes strongly conditioned by the design choices that are made, such as families of dependent types, the use of subtypes, partial functions, and so on. These choices completely condition the development of the formalization, creating obstacles or facilitating the work later on. In this sense, we conclude that a good part of the formalization work is, not so much a purely mathematical task, but a *design work* at each step of the development, which requires a global vision of what one wants to achieve and of the tools available for it.

APPENDIX

A

Guide to the formalization
repository

This appendix complements Chapter 7 with a description of the [formalization repository](#)¹⁹. There we discussed the design decisions of the formalization itself. Here we deal with the support that surrounds it, that is, with the organization of the files, the auxiliary tools, the development environment and the conventions of the project. The aim is to facilitate navigation through the code and to document all the components of the repository.

§ A.1

General structure of the repository

The repository is organized around five functional blocks, which correspond to the subsequent sections of this appendix:

- The *Lean library*, materialized in the entry point `HigherCategoryTheory.lean`, the directory `HigherCategoryTheory/` with the bulk of the code, and the Lake configuration files (`lakefile.toml`, `lake-manifest.json` and `lean-toolchain`).
- The *documentation*, which lives in three complementary directories: `blueprint/` (with the LaTeX source of the blueprint), `docs/` (which contains only the shared bibliography) and `website/` (the project's Jekyll landing page).
- The folder `scripts/`, with the two Python scripts that assist in the construction of the documentation and in the formatting of references.
- The *continuous integration*, in `.github/workflows/`.
- The *development environment*, configured by means of `devenv.nix`, `devenv.yaml`, `devenv.lock` and the `justfile` that orchestrates all the tasks of the repository.

To these five blocks two header files are added: the `README.md`, which documents in a condensed form the purpose of the project and the usage instructions, and the `LICENSE`, which gathers the terms of the Apache 2.0 license under which the code is distributed.

§ A.2

The Lean library

The core of the repository is the formal library. Its declaration as a Lake project resides in the `lakefile.toml`, which fixes the name `HigherCategoryTheory`, the current version and a set of compiler options that deserve comment. The activation of `pp.unicode.fun` makes the arrow `→` be printed in its Unicode form, the options `autoImplicit = false` and `relaxedAutoImplicit = false` disable the automatic introduction of implicit variables (so that all variables must be declared explicitly, a discipline aligned with that of Mathlib), `weak.linter.mathlibStandardSet` enables Mathlib's standard set of linters, and `maxSynthPendingDepth = 3` widens the search depth of the elaborator, necessary because of the depth of the project's class hierarchy.

The `lakefile.toml` declares, in addition, four external dependencies, all of them pinned to a specific revision:

¹⁹https://github.com/mariovagomarzal/higher_category_theory

- `mathlib`, Lean’s standard mathematical library, on which the project’s classical categorical part and most of the tactics that we use rely.
- `doc-gen4`, the API documentation generator that we will discuss in the following section.
- `checkdecls`, a utility that verifies that all the declarations cited in the blueprint actually exist in the code.
- `subverso`, which the compilation pipeline of the thesis itself uses to extract the proof states that appear in the infoviews of Chapter 7.

The compiler version is fixed by the file `lean-toolchain` (pointing, at the time of writing this work, to Lean 4.28.0), and the exact revisions of each dependency are frozen in `lake-manifest.json`. These two files, together with the `lakefile.toml`, are what guarantee that anyone who clones the repository can reproduce exactly the same compilation environment.

The entry point of the library is `HigherCategoryTheory.lean`. Its contents reduce to a list of `import`, one per module of the library, so that importing this single file makes the entire formalization available. The internal organization of the `HigherCategoryTheory/` directory reflects the decisions exposed in Chapter 7:

- At the root, three transversal modules: `Init.lean`, which registers the rule set `HigherCategoryTheory` on which the project’s discharge tactic is built; `Notation.lean`, which defines the shared abbreviations and notations (`FinSucc`, `TypeFamily`, the notation `»` for the composition of inequalities, and so on); and `Tactic.lean`, where the tactic `hcat_disch` and its interrogative variants are elaborated.
- The subdirectories `SingleSorted/` and `ManySorted/`, with a parallel structure. Each one contains the modules `Category.lean`, `Functor.lean` and `Cat.lean`, corresponding to the category classes, the functors and the category of categories, together with the subdirectories `Discrete/` and `Underlying/` for the discretization and underlying transformations.
- In `SingleSorted/`, in addition, the modules specific to this presentation: `Cells.lean`, with the machinery on cells; `Order.lean` and `Monoid.lean`, with concrete examples of the theory; and the subdirectory `Types/`, with two auxiliary examples on the unit type and the product.

§ A.3

The blueprint, the API documentation and the project’s landing page

The documentary part of the repository is distributed across three closely related directories. The first, `blueprint/`, stores the LaTeX source of the blueprint already discussed at the close of Chapter 7. Within `blueprint/src/` two root files coexist, `web.tex` and `print.tex`, which generate respectively the web version and the PDF version of the document. Both include the common file `content.tex`, which orchestrates the chapters of the blueprint hosted in `chapters/`. The subdirectory `preamble/` contains the shared preambles and the ones specific to each format. The tool that processes these sources is `leanblueprint`, a wrapper around LaTeX that produces at once the PDF and the website with the dependency graph. Associated with it, the utility `leanblueprint checkdecls` verifies, thanks to the dependency `checkdecls`, that the blueprint’s references to the formal declarations of the code actually point to declarations that exist in the library.

The second directory, `docs/`, contains only the file references `.bib`. This bibliography is shared: both the blueprint and the API documentation use it, so that centralizing it in a single point avoids duplications.

The API documentation is generated with the dependency `doc-gen4`, already mentioned. The tool gathers the project's docstrings, that is, the blocks `-- ... -/` that accompany each declaration, and publishes them as a navigable website. The construction is not invoked directly with `lake`, but through the script `scripts/build_docs.py` that we will discuss in the following section, which takes care of some technical details of the process.

The third directory, `website/`, stores a small static landing page built with Jekyll, in which the three previous pieces are linked: the blueprint's website, its PDF version and the API documentation. The `justfile` packages the three outputs into the directory `website/_site/`, which is precisely what continuous integration deploys to GitHub Pages.

§ A.4

Scripts

The `scripts/` directory contains two Python scripts that assist with specific tasks of the project. The first, `build_docs.py`, builds the API documentation. The reason why it is not enough to invoke `doc-gen4` directly is double. On one hand, the script creates an auxiliary project (a `docbuild`) that includes `doc-gen4` as a dependency without affecting the main `lakefile.toml`, which keeps the project's dependency graph clean. On the other, it applies a patch to the transitive dependency `UnicodeBasic` to work around a known failure of the linking of static libraries on non-Windows platforms, documented in [fgdorais/lean4-unicode-basic#81](https://github.com/fgdorais/lean4-unicode-basic/issues/81)²⁰. Once the documentation has been generated, the script copies it to the directory that will serve the project's landing page.

The second, `bibtool_format.py`, wraps the `bibtool` tool to normalize the format of the `references.bib` file. It is invoked both by the `format-references` recipe of the `justfile` and by a pre-commit hook, so that any modification of the bibliography is automatically harmonized before being recorded.

§ A.5

Continuous integration

The repository's automation is concentrated in a single GitHub Actions workflow, `.github/workflows/build-and-deploy.yaml`, which is triggered on every push and every pull request to the main branch, as well as on manual invocation. The flow has two chained jobs. The first, `build`, installs Nix and `devenv` on the runner, restores the `.lake/` directory from GitHub's cache (with a key that combines operating system, architecture, toolchain version and the contents of `lake-manifest.json`, so that the precompiled dependencies are reused as long as they do not change), and runs within the `devenv` environment the four recipes that build the project, that is, `just build`, `just docs`, `just blueprint` and `just website`. The second job, `deploy`, runs only on push and is

²⁰<https://github.com/fgdorais/lean4-unicode-basic/issues/81>

in charge of publishing the resulting artifact on GitHub Pages, which is where the project's page resides.

Two details of the workflow deserve to be highlighted. The first is that all the construction happens within `devenv shell`, so that the reproducible environment that we use locally is exactly the same as the one available to continuous integration. The second is the presence of a concurrency group that cancels previous executions on the same branch or pull request, which avoids overlapping deployments when commits pile up in quick succession.

§ A.6

Development environment and conventions

The repository's development environment is built with Nix and the `devenv` utility, which automates the declaration of the set of tools, environment variables and Git hooks. The main file, `devenv.nix`, enables Lean 4 through `elan` (the official version manager of the compiler), Ruby with Bundler (for the Jekyll landing page), full TeX Live (for the blueprint), Python 3.13 (for the scripts in the `scripts/` directory) and a set of additional utilities, among which `just` and `leanblueprint` stand out. The exact versions of all these packages are pinned by `devenv.lock`, which ensures that anyone entering the shell with `devenv shell` obtains exactly the same environment, independently of their operating system.

On top of this environment, `devenv` installs a series of pre-commit hooks that watch over the consistency of the repository:

- `gitlint`, which checks that each commit message follows the [Conventional Commits](#)²¹ specification, that is, that it begins with a known type (`feat`, `fix`, `docs`, `style`, `refactor`, `test`, `chore`, `build`, `ci`, `perf` or `revert`) and respects a limit of 120 characters per line, both in the subject and in the body.
- `markdownlint`, which verifies the format of the repository's Markdown files, with the exception of the Jekyll landing page.
- `alejandra`, which formats the Nix files.
- The already mentioned `bibtool`, which normalizes the bibliography.

The tools associated with each hook are also provided by `devenv`, so that it is not necessary to install them separately.

The `justfile` at the root of the repository is the single entry point for the usual tasks of the project. The recipes are grouped into four blocks:

- `env`, with the environment initialization tasks for when Nix is not available, that is, `cache` (which invokes `lake exe cache get` to download the precompiled binaries of Mathlib and avoid long compilations) and `bundler` (which installs the Ruby dependencies of the landing page). The recipe `env` chains both.
- `lean`, with the recipe `build`, a wrapper around `lake build` with `HigherCategoryTheory` as default target.

²¹<https://www.conventionalcommits.org>

- *docs*, which groups the construction of the API documentation (*docs*), of the blueprint in its two formats (*blueprint*, with its subtasks *blueprint-print* and *blueprint-web*), the verification of declarations (*blueprint-check*), the local preview of the blueprint (*blueprint-serve*) and the construction and serving of the full website (*website* and *serve*).
- *style*, with *format-references*, which invokes the bibliography formatting script.

All the recipes come accompanied by a brief description, accessible by running just with no arguments.

Finally, the `.vscode/` directory gathers the recommended configurations for Visual Studio Code, the editor in which the Lean community concentrates most of the extensions and the integration with the language server. It includes the file `extensions.json` with the recommended extensions, the file `settings.json` with the project's default editor configuration and a `snippets` file with the copyright header that is inserted at the beginning of each new Lean module. These configurations are mere recommendations: any editor with Lean support (Neovim or Emacs, for instance) is perfectly valid.

As for the workflow, no strict branching policy is established, although the convention is followed of developing contributions on separate branches and merging them into `main` through a pull request. What matters is that each pull request is automatically validated by the continuous integration workflow described in the previous section, so that the state of the `main` branch is always reproducible and deployable.

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